
Discovering the Archaeologists of the United Kingdom 2012-14

Kenneth Aitchison and Doug Rocks-Macqueen

Landward Research Ltd

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Contents

Tables	5
Figures	8
Acknowledgements	9
Summary and recommendations	10
Executive Summary	10
Recommendations	14
Chapter 1: Introduction and Background	16
Introduction	16
Context and Background	16
Background	16
Aim and Objectives	17
UK Context	18
The Great Recession	18
Structure of the Report	18
Previous work	19
Introduction	19
Numbers of Professional Working Archaeologists	19
Profiling the Profession 1997-98	21
Profiling the Profession 2002-03	22
Profiling the Profession 2007-08	22
Breaking New Ground	22
Discovering the Archaeologists of Europe	22
Carter and Robertson 2002	23
The Invisible Diggers	24
RESCUE Surveys	24
Jobs in British Archaeology	25
IfA Pay Benchmarking	25
IfA Equal Opportunities Surveys	26
Archaeological Employment in Scotland	26
Survey of Archaeological Specialists	26
Survey of Archaeological Specialists 2010-11	27
Benchmarking Competence Requirements and Training Opportunities related to	
Maritime Archaeology	27
Archaeology and the Global Economic Crisis: multiple impacts, possible solutions	27
Job Losses in Archaeology and State of the Archaeological Market	28
A Fourth Report on Local Authority Staff Resources	28
Historic Environment Record Content and Computing Survey	28
Chapter 2: Methodology	30
Introduction	30
Project Team	30

Survey Methodology	30
Mailing List	31
Data collection	32
Data entry and analysis	34
Calculating workforce size	35
Past Methodology	35
New Methodology	36
Confidence in Estimated Size	43
Total Estimated Population	43
Self-reported losses	44
Recorded losses	45
Confidence in All Results	46
Levels of Response	46
Representative Sample	50
Salary data	52
Analysis and presentation of reported figures	52
Creation of post profiles	52
Electronic access to data	56
Chapter 3: Organisations	57
Introduction	57
Size of Organisations	57
Changes in Staffing Levels	60
Staff Turnover	63
Salaries	64
Quality Systems	64
Investors in People (IiP)	67
IfA Registration	70
Annual Turnover	74
Profit Margins	74
Business Confidence	76
Chapter 4: Archaeologists	78
Growth of the profession	78
New entrants to the profession	78
Supply from Universities	78
Geographical Distribution	87
Diversity	93
Gender balance	93
Age	94
Ethnic diversity	98
Disability status	99
Countries of origin	100
Staff qualifications	101
Unpaid volunteer archaeologists	103

Chapter 5: Jobs	105
Range of jobs	105
Salaries and earnings	106
Profiling the Profession and Jobs in British Archaeology.	110
IfA salary minima	111
Earnings in other occupations	113
Earnings by gender	113
Earnings by age	113
Salary scales	115
Employee rights and benefits	116
Paid holiday	116
Maternity leave	117
Paternity leave	117
Subsistence or subsidised accommodation	118
Other benefits	119
Trends in Employee Benefits	120
Additional benefits	120
Comments on rights and benefits	123
Pensions	125
Job security	126
Length of contract	127
Length of employment to date	129
Full-time and part-time work	131
Sources of funding	132
Vacancies	135
Trade Unions	136
Chapter 6: Training	138
Introduction	138
Training demand	138
Frameworks for training	139
National Occupational Standards	139
National Vocational Qualifications	140
QAA Benchmark Statement	140
Continuing Professional Development	141
Training delivery	141
Universities	141
Non-university training courses	141
Workplace learning and apprenticeships	141
Employers' commitment to qualifications and training	142
Organisational attitudes towards training	142
Preferred methods of training	144
Support for Vocational Qualification	145
Skills gaps and shortages	145
Skills lost	149

Skills gaps	150
Skills shortages	151
Perceived skills gaps or shortages across the archaeological sector	153
Bibliography	155
Appendix 1: Post Profiles	164
Appendix 2: Comments	201
Appendix 3: Planning Applications	211
Appendix 4: Questionnaire	215

Tables

Table 1: Estimated numbers of professional archaeologists working in the UK.	20
Table 2: Number of usable responses to all <i>Profiling the Profession</i> surveys.	33
Table 3: Numbers of archaeologists represented in survey responses.	33
Table 4: Post profiles completed in all <i>Profiling the Profession</i> surveys.	33
Table 5: Archaeologists represented in post profiles in all <i>Profiling the Profession</i> surveys.	34
Table 6: Archaeological staff at UK universities (February 2013).	36
Table 7: Distribution of numbers of staff, local government organisations providing advice only.	37
Table 8: Long tail model of commercial archaeological employer sizes.	42
Table 9: Estimated numbers of professional archaeologists in the UK.	43
Table 10: Organisational bases of respondent organisations.	47
Table 11: Organisational bases of respondents, 1997-98 to 2007-08.	47
Table 12: Organisational principal roles.	47
Table 13: Organisations with multiple roles.	48
Table 14: Organisation principal roles 2002-03 to 2012-13.	48
Table 15: Numbers of archaeologists reported by organisational roles.	49
Table 16: Percentages of archaeologists by organisations' primary roles over time.	50
Table 17: Response levels by organisational bases.	51
Table 18: Post profile categories.	56
Table 19: Size of organisations that responded to the questionnaire.	57
Table 20: Distribution of archaeological staff by organisational size.	58
Table 21: Size of organisations, 2002-03 to 2012-13.	59
Table 22: Past changes in staffing levels.	60
Table 23: Anticipated future changes in staffing levels.	61
Table 24: Anticipated future volunteer levels.	61
Table 25: Anticipated or reported changes in staff levels, 1992-2014.	62
Table 26: Levels of staff turnover during 2012.	63
Table 27: Former staff destinations.	63
Table 28: Salary changes.	64
Table 29: Use of quality systems.	64
Table 30: Use of quality systems by organisational principal roles.	65
Table 31: Use of quality systems by organisational constitutions.	65
Table 32: Use of different quality systems.	65
Table 33: Change in use of quality systems, 2002-03 to 2012-13.	66
Table 34: Investors in People.	67
Table 35: IiP accreditation status, 2002-03 to 2012-13.	67
Table 36: IiP accreditation by constitution.	68
Table 37: Reason for non-commitment to Investors in People, 2002-03 to 2012-13.	68
Table 38: IfA Registered Organisation status.	70
Table 39: IfA Registration status, 2002-03 to 2012-13.	70
Table 40: IfA Registered Organisations by constitution.	71
Table 41: IfA Registered Organisations by principal areas of activity.	72
Table 42: IfA Registration, reasons for non-commitment, 2002-03 to 2012-13.	72
Table 43: Average financial turnover, 2009-10 to 2011-12.	74
Table 44: Profit margins.	75
Table 45: Market conditions in 2013.	76
Table 46: Expectations of organisations ceasing operations in 2013.	76
Table 47: Expansion plans in 2013.	77
Table 48: Organisations intending to invest, by constitution.	77
Table 49: Organisations intending to invest, by primary role.	77
Table 50: Applications and acceptances to archaeology programmes, 2006-2012.	79
Table 51: HESA data on full-time first year archaeology students.	80
Table 52: HESA data on part-time first year archaeology students.	80

Table 53: Degrees awarded in Forensic & Archaeological Science and Archaeology.	80
Table 54: Full-time and part-time archaeology students - History and Philosophical Studies.	82
Table 55: Full-time and part-time students of archaeology – physical sciences.	83
Table 56: Archaeology – physical sciences student numbers by HESA subcodes.	85
Table 57: Estimated number of degrees awarded in archaeology, 2009/10 to 2011/12.	86
Table 58: Estimated numbers of graduates potentially interested in pursuing a career in archaeology.	86
Table 59: Geographical distribution of archaeologists.	87
Table 60: Geographical distribution of archaeologists working for universities.	88
Table 61: Geographical distribution of archaeologists working for local authorities.	88
Table 62: Geographical distribution of archaeologists working for national governments.	89
Table 63: Geographical distribution of archaeologists working for civil society organisations.	89
Table 64: Geographical distribution of archaeologists working in museum organisations.	90
Table 65: Geographical distribution of archaeologists working in commercial settings.	90
Table 66: Geographical distribution of all archaeologists.	91
Table 67: Geographical distribution of archaeologists, 1997-98 to 2012-13.	92
Table 68: Gender balance in professional archaeology.	93
Table 69: Gender balance of archaeologists and UK workforce, 1997-98 to 2012-13.	93
Table 70: Gender by employers’ organisational bases.	94
Table 71: Gender by principal individual roles.	94
Table 72: Average age by gender, 1997-98 to 2012-13.	95
Table 73: Age and gender.	95
Table 74: Age and gender of archaeologists, 1997-98 to 2012-13.	97
Table 75: Age by individual’s principal role.	98
Table 76: Age of archaeologists by employers’ organisational bases.	98
Table 77: Ethnicities of archaeologists.	98
Table 78: Ethnic diversity, 2002-03 to 2012-13.	99
Table 79: Disability status of archaeologists.	99
Table 80: Disability status of archaeologists 2002-03 to 2012-13.	100
Table 81: Countries of origin of archaeologists working in the UK, 2012-13.	100
Table 82: Countries of origin of archaeologists working in the UK, 2007-08 to 2012-13.	101
Table 83: Highest qualifications achieved.	101
Table 84: Highest qualifications achieved, 2002-03 to 2012-13.	102
Table 85: Qualifications by age.	102
Table 86: Salaries by highest level of qualification achieved, 2002-03 to 2012-13	103
Table 87: Age and gender of volunteers.	104
Table 88: Ethnic diversity of volunteers.	104
Table 89: Age and gender of volunteers, 2002-03 to 2012-13.	104
Table 90: Post role details received.	105
Table 91: Post role details received, 2002-03 to 2012-13.	106
Table 92: Earnings distribution in archaeology.	107
Table 93: Full-time earnings in archaeology and all UK occupations, 1997-98 to 2012-13.	107
Table 94: Earning distribution by organisation bases.	108
Table 95: Average and median earnings by organisational bases, 2002-03 to 2012-13.	108
Table 96: Salary distribution by individual roles.	109
Table 97: Average and median earnings by post role, 2002-03 to 2012-13.	110
Table 98: Median full-time gross earnings by major occupation groups.	113
Table 99: Earnings by gender.	113
Table 100: Earnings by age.	114
Table 101: Earnings by age and gender.	114
Table 102: Use of salary scales by organisations.	115
Table 103: Types of salary scale used.	116
Table 104: Paid holiday.	117
Table 105: Maternity leave.	117
Table 106: Paternity leave.	118
Table 107: Subsidised accommodation or subsistence allowance.	118

Table 108: Other benefits offered by numbers of archaeologists employed.	119
Table 109: Employee rights / benefits, 1997-98 to 2012-13.	120
Table 110: Employer pension contributions.	125
Table 111: Employer pension contributions by organisational bases.	125
Table 112: Level of seniority of posts and pension contributions.	126
Table 113: Pension contributions, 1997-98 to 2012-13.	126
Table 114: Length of contract, 1997-98 to 2012-13.	127
Table 115: Length of contract by working role.	127
Table 116: Proportion of permanent contracts by working role, 2002-03 to 2012-13.	128
Table 117: Length of employment to date.	129
Table 118: Length of employment to date by working role.	129
Table 119: Length of employment to date by organisation type, all staff.	130
Table 120: Length of employment to date, 1997-98 to 2012-13.	130
Table 121: Full-time and part-time work, all staff.	131
Table 122: Full-time and part-time work by role.	131
Table 123: Full-time and part-time work by organisation basis.	132
Table 124: Full-time and part-time work by gender.	132
Table 125: Post funding.	132
Table 126: Post funding, by job role.	133
Table 127: Post funding, by organisation basis.	133
Table 128: Post funding, by job role, 2002-03 to 2012-13.	134
Table 129: Difficult to fill vacancies by post role.	135
Table 130: Difficult to fill vacancies by organisational basis.	135
Table 131: Number of difficult to fill vacancies, 2002-03 to 2012-13.	135
Table 132: Trade Union recognition.	136
Table 133: Trade Unions recognised by archaeological employers.	136
Table 134: Archaeologists working for organisations which recognise trade unions, 1997-98 to 2012-13.	137
Table 135: Organisations' attitudes towards training.	143
Table 136: Preferred methods of training for paid staff.	144
Table 137: Preferred methods of training for unpaid staff.	144
Table 138: Organisational support for NVQ in Archaeological Practice.	145
Table 139: Identified skills gaps and shortages.	146
Table 140: Skills gaps, 2002-03 to 2012-13.	147
Table 141: Skills shortages, 2002-03 to 2012-13.	148
Table 142: Skills lost.	149
Table 143: Skills training investment.	150
Table 144: Skills bought in.	151
Table 145: Perceived skills gaps or shortages across the archaeological sector.	153
Table 146: Planning applications granted in England, June 2005 to December 2012.	211
Table 147: Planning applications by type in Scotland, 2006-07 to 2011-12.	212
Table 148: Planning Applications and decisions in Northern Ireland, 2002-03 to 2011-12.	213
Table 149: Planning application and decisions in Wales, 2008 to 2013.	214

Figures

Figure 1: Estimated numbers of professional archaeologists working in the UK.	21
Figure 2: Distribution of number of staff, local government organisations providing advice only.	38
Figure 3: Numbers of archaeologists employed by individual commercial organisations.	40
Figure 4: Changes in numbers of archaeologists working for individual employers, 2007-08 to 2012-13.	45
Figure 5: Numbers of archaeologists by organisations' primary and mixed roles.	49
Figure 6: Percentages of archaeologists by organisations' primary roles over time.	50
Figure 7: Response levels by organisational bases.	52
Figure 8: Distribution of archaeological staff by organisational size.	58
Figure 9: Size of organisations (just archaeologists), 2002-03 to 2012-13.	59
Figure 10: Past changes in staffing levels.	60
Figure 11: Reason for non-commitment to Investors in People, 2002-03 to 2012-13.	69
Figure 12: IfA Registration status, 2002-03 to 2012-13.	71
Figure 13: IfA Registration, reasons for non-commitment, 2002-03 to 2012-13.	72
Figure 14: Profit margins.	75
Figure 15: Applications and acceptances to archaeology programmes, 2006-2012.	79
Figure 16: Degrees awarded in Forensic & Archaeological Science and Archaeology.	81
Figure 17: Full-time and part-time archaeology students - History and Philosophical Studies.	82
Figure 18: Full-time and part-time students of archaeology – physical sciences.	83
Figure 19: Gender balance of archaeologists, 1997-98 to 2012-13.	93
Figure 20: Age and gender.	96
Figure 21: Highest qualifications achieved, 2002-03 to 2012-13.	102
Figure 22: Salaries by highest level of qualification achieved, 2002-03 to 2012-13.	103
Figure 23: Annual salaries in archaeology.	106
Figure 24: Salary distribution by individual roles.	109
Figure 25: Annual pay rates of archaeologists for the Jobs in British Archaeology series.	110
Figure 26: Comparison of salaries from Profiling the Profession and Jobs in British Archaeology.	111
Figure 27: Earnings by age and gender.	115
Figure 28: Proportion of permanent contracts by working role, 2002-03 to 2012-13.	128
Figure 29: Archaeologists working for organisations which recognise trade unions, 1997-98 to 2012-13.	137
Figure 30: Planning applications and decisions in England, June 2005 to December 2012.	212
Figure 31: Planning applications and decisions in Northern Ireland, 2002-03 to 2011-12.	213
Figure 32: Planning applications and decisions in Wales, 2008 to 2013.	214

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Summary and recommendations

Executive Summary

Comprehensive Labour Market Intelligence for the archaeological profession has now been gathered for the fourth time in the series of *Profiling the Profession* studies. This baseline survey used the same fundamental methodology that was previously employed in 1997-98, 2002-03 and 2007-08, and consequently a time-series dataset has been compiled which allows trends to be identified with increasing confidence.

The previous labour market intelligence gathering exercise for the sector (in 2007-08) was undertaken immediately before the effects of significant global and national economic changes began to affect archaeological employment. The economic transformation since 2007-08 significantly affected employment in archaeology, resulting in the sector being considerably smaller in 2012-13 than it was in 2007-08.

With an overall response rate of 224 from a population of 511 potential respondents contacted, at a confidence level of 95% this level of response is accurate to +/- 4.9%.

The estimated numbers of archaeologists working in the UK

The estimated archaeological workforce in 2012-13 was 4,792, a 30% decrease on the figure of 6,865 estimated for 2007-08 (and a 16% decrease over ten years on the estimated archaeological workforce in 2002-03 of 5,712).

A further estimated 1,148 people worked as dedicated support staff within archaeological organisations, giving an estimated total of 5,940 people directly earning their livings from archaeology.

Age, gender, ethnicity, disability status and country of origin

The average age of a working archaeologist in 2012-13 was 42; female archaeologists were on average aged 39, and male archaeologists 44. The average age of working archaeologists had increased by four years over the previous five years. By comparison, the average age of the whole UK workforce was 40.5.

The survey found that 46% of archaeologists were female and 54% were male. In 2007-08, the proportions were 41:59. 47% of the whole UK workforce in all occupations was female, 53% male.

Archaeology was not an ethnically diverse profession in 2012-13; 99% of working archaeologists were white. This was effectively unchanged since 2007-08 and from 2002-03 and contrasted with the entire UK workforce of whom 13% were of black or minority ethnic origins.

The proportion of people with disabilities working in archaeology continued to be very low; 98% of archaeologists were not disabled. This was effectively unchanged over time, while 7% of the entire UK workforce were disabled.

93% of archaeologists working in the UK in 2012-13 were from the UK, 3% were from elsewhere in the European Union, less than 1% were from non-EU Europe and 4% were from elsewhere in the world. This represented a relative decrease in the number of archaeologists from non-UK European Union countries (5% of the working population in 2007-08), and a relative increase in the number of archaeologists from elsewhere in the world (2% in 2007-08). However, as the total number of working archaeologists had fallen considerably, the absolute numbers of archaeologists from outside the UK had also fallen.

Anticipated growth of the sector

Despite experiencing a reduction in the size of the sectoral workforce in the previous five years, slightly more employers anticipated that their organisation would be larger one year in the future than expected to be smaller, with further optimistic forecasts for organisational sizes three years into the future. These expectations were noticeably more cautious than the ambitious forecasts returned in 2007-08.

Estimated numbers working in each job type

Of 4,792 archaeologists working in the UK in 2012-13, it is estimated that 2,684 (56%) of these people worked for organisations that provided field investigation and research services, 1,198 (25%) for organisations that provided historic environment advice, 96 (2%) provided museum and visitor services and 815 (17%) worked for organisations that provided education and academic research. These percentages changed relatively little over the five years from 2007-08, although the relative proportion working to provide museum and visitor services decreased while the relative proportion working in education and academic research rose.

545 (11%) worked for national government agencies, 485 (10%) worked in local government, 690 (14%) worked for universities, 2,812 (59%) worked for commercial private sector organisations and 260 (6%) worked for other types of organisations (civil society organisations or museums).

Overall, this represented a relative increase in the percentage of archaeologists working in the private sector over the five years from 2007-08 and a decline in those working in the public sector.

Geographical differences

More archaeologists worked in London and the south east of England than other areas, but this largely reflects the overall pattern of the UK population distribution. The geographical distribution of archaeologists has not changed significantly over the period of 15 years that the *Profiling the Profession* series of surveys have been undertaken.

Range of jobs

The survey collected detailed information on 888 archaeologists and support staff working in 389 jobs with 236 different post titles. This represented one post title for every 3.8 individuals; in 2007-08 there was one post title for every 5.3 individuals.

Average salaries

On average, full-time archaeologists earned £27,814 *per annum*. The median archaeological salary was £26,000 (50% of archaeologists earned more than this, 50% earned less). The average salary for those employed in the private sector, which employed 59% of the archaeological workforce, was £24,757. By comparison, the average for all UK full-time workers was £32,700 – so, overall, the average archaeologist earned 85% of the UK average as was the case in 2007-08.

Over the five years from 2007-08 to 2012-13, the average salaries of archaeologists increased by 19%. The national average for all occupations increased by 20% over that same period, so average archaeological salaries increased at approximately the same rate as the national average.

In calendar year 2012, 46% of archaeologists worked for organisations that reported that individual salaries had typically either fallen or remained unchanged.

Staff qualifications

Archaeologists were highly qualified, and over time the average levels of qualifications held have risen.

In 2012-13, one in five (20%) of archaeologists held a Doctorate or post-doctoral qualification (in 2007-08 the equivalent figure was 12%), a total of 47% held a Masters degree or higher (in 2007-08 the equivalent figure was 40%) and 93% of archaeologists held a Bachelors degree or higher (in 2007-08, the equivalent figure was 90%).

95% of archaeologists aged under 30 for whom qualifications data were available were graduates.

Potential skills shortages and skills gaps

Skills gaps (skills that existing staff need but lack) and shortages (where employers cannot find employees with the relevant skills) were identified in both technical, archaeological skills and in generic, professional skills. The severity of these gaps and shortages was categorised as significant, where more than 25% of respondents to the question had identified a problem, or serious, where more than 50% of respondents to the question had identified a problem.

A serious skills shortage was identified in post-fieldwork analysis.

Significant skills shortages were identified in fieldwork (invasive or non- invasive); artefact or ecofact conservation; and in information technology.

Significant skills gaps were identified in post-fieldwork analysis; fieldwork (invasive or non-invasive); information technology; people management; and in project management.

Employers' commitment to training and qualifications

Overall, archaeological employers demonstrate a high level of commitment to training their staff, although the levels of support shown by several key indicators have declined since 2007-08.

90% of employers identified training needs for individuals and provided training for paid staff (in 2007-08, 93% did). 46% had a formal training plan (52% did in 2007-08) and 45% formally evaluated the impact of training on individuals (48% did in 2007-08). 26% evaluated the impact of training on the organisation (28% in 2007-08), compared with 75% which identified needs for the organisation as a whole (76% in 2007-08).

Recommendations

The recommendations presented here are based on the authors' understandings of the interpreted data and are made by them to the sector and stakeholders on that basis.

Skills Issues

Recommendation for *sectoral stakeholders*: review sectoral training priorities (such as presented in the Archaeology Training Forum's *Vision* document) in light of the recognised skills gaps and shortages presented in this report, and ensure funding support is targeted on areas where there is a defined need for training.

Recommendation for *higher education institutions*: ensure that the report is used to enhance the employability of graduates as well as to inform students of potential employment opportunities within archaeology, of the level of competition that is likely to be encountered and the qualifications they are likely to be needed to enter employment.

Recommendation for *individual archaeologists* and for *archaeological employers*: continuing professional development should be focussed on delivering skills that contribute both to individuals' employability and to employers' business objectives. Commitment to provide support for such activity should be justified by both individuals and employers in terms of improving business performance. The outcomes of training should be routinely reviewed in terms of impact both upon the individual being trained and upon the organisation as a whole.

Recommendation for all *sector stakeholders*: maintain or increase investment in archaeological skills training.

Recommendation for *archaeological employers* and *training providers*: opportunities to improve business planning and delivery within the sector should be explored, such as developing bespoke business training courses for archaeologists (potentially within the context of wider cultural heritage / historic environment training). Public sector bodies are particularly weak in these areas.

Qualifications

Recommendation for *employers* and *higher education institutions*: review the relevance and impact of the *NVQ in Archaeological Practice*; while employers say that they value the qualification, there have been very few individuals who have obtained it. The ongoing existence of the qualification will rely on increased uptake, and very few of the candidates who have successfully obtained the NVQ did not already have equivalent or higher level qualifications (such as degrees), very little public funding has been able to be attracted to support candidates.

Employment

Recommendation for *the Institute for Archaeologists, the Federation of Archaeological Managers and Employers* and *national heritage agencies*: promote professionalism by encouraging archaeologists and archaeological employers to ensure that they and their staff undertake and document CPD in order to demonstrate that those staff members are both competent and that they maintain their levels of competence.

Recommendation for *archaeological employers* and *sectoral stakeholders*: positive action is required to diversify the archaeological workforce as the sector is socially exclusive and therefore archaeological practice is not reflecting the diversity of the UK population as a whole, and so is limiting the potential of the sector to attract the best people to work in it.

Future Research

Recommendation for *project funders*: the process of data collection, interpretation and dissemination of labour market intelligence for the archaeological profession should continue to be repeated on a five-yearly cycle. The value of the data gathered in the series of *Profiling the Profession* reports has been magnified by forming time-series datasets that illustrate trends., although potentially some questions which have not produced significant or significantly variable results (such as, for example, those relating to *Investors in People* accreditation) could be moved to being gathered only in alternate surveys. The research already interfaces with other work looking at labour market intelligence in other areas of cultural heritage / historic environment and future work should ensure that methodologies adopted in such work is comparable.

Recommendation for *the Institute for Archaeologists* and *the Federation of Archaeological Managers and Employers*: the *State of the Archaeological Market* research (gathering information from commercial providers of applied archaeological services) continues, gathering data on an annual basis. This is both the largest subsector within archaeology and the most likely to respond rapidly to changing economic circumstances, and so this work will both provide valuable data for business planning and will give advance indications of trends that are likely to affect the whole sector over time.

Recommendation for *project funders* and all *sectoral stakeholders*: commission or undertake qualitative research looking in greater depth at particular skills issues in archaeology (breaking macro-skills, such as 'post-fieldwork analysis' down into component parts, so increasing granularity) that particularly considers how needs have changed over time should be supported in order to gain a more detailed understanding of skills issues across the sector,

Chapter 1: Introduction and Background

Introduction

This report, *Archaeology Labour Market Intelligence: Profiling the Profession 2012-13*, is the fourth in a series of labour market intelligence surveys which have been carried out every five years since 1997-98. The data in the project reports, 1997-98, 2002-03, 2007-08 and 2012-13, characterise time series datasets which allow social, economic and education trends to be examined in professional archaeology in the United Kingdom.

Context and Background

This project has captured labour market intelligence for the archaeological sector, identifying the nature of archaeological employment in all subsectors across the UK in 2012-13., including data on employment conditions, staff qualifications, diversity and training issues. The data are coherent with previously collected data, allowing longitudinal time-series trends to be presented and analysed. These data are also presented by geographical region or nation as well as by the employment categories used in the predecessor studies.

Background

English Heritage has, together with other organisations, commissioned comprehensive labour market intelligence for the archaeological profession on a five year cycle since 1997-8. The *Profiling the Profession* series of reports, each of which has been led by Kenneth Aitchison, have provided a series of detailed snapshots of the archaeological workforce, its size and employment conditions. Taken together they form a body of data which has been used to develop training and CPD opportunities and qualifications, support funding applications, and inform a wide range of activities designed to improve standards of work and employment across the sector.

The scale and nature of employment in UK archaeology changed dramatically during the course of the 1990s and the first decade of the 21st century following the introduction of the developer-funding model to achieve the aims of sustainable development. The patterns of archaeological employment transformed again following the global economic decline which began in 2007-08.

These changes were captured, quantitatively and qualitatively, through three previous labour market intelligence (LMI) studies conducted at five-yearly intervals from 1997 to 2007 (Aitchison 1999, Aitchison & Edwards 2003, Aitchison & Edwards 2008).

These studies have produced longitudinal datasets tracking these changes, which have allowed individual and would-be practitioners to assess their own positions and to support their planning for the future. Moreover, these longitudinal datasets have supported employers in making business decisions and have helped policy makers plan for the future development of the sector.

The 2007-08 study was also part of a larger *Discovering the Archaeologists of Europe* project (Aitchison 2009a), which collected comparable data in twelve European states. This has allowed the UK profession's position within an international industry (and market) to be identified. The results of all of these surveys have been widely referred to in the professional and academic literature and are used to underpin policy proposals (eg Hunter & Ralston 2006, IfA 2007, English Heritage 2011a, Scanlon *et al* 2011).

The most recent predecessor study (Aitchison & Edwards 2008) captured data from employers in August 2007, immediately before the effects of global economic changes had serious and adverse effects upon archaeological practice and employment in the UK (eg Aitchison 2009b, 2011a).

Data capture and analysis in 2012-13 has continued the five-yearly cycle (as recommended in the 2007-08 report) and quantifies the further changes that have happened since the economic transformations that began in 2007 and 2008. The data presented should better inform employers, individual workers and training providers seeking to address the changes that the economic transformation has brought. Since 2007-08, Kenneth Aitchison has undertaken a series of surveys (initially directly for IfA as a series of *Job Losses* surveys, and subsequently for Landward Research Ltd on behalf of IfA and FAME as *State of the Archaeological Market* surveys) to capture headline data on the changes.

Aim and Objectives

The aim of this project was to gather, analyse and interpret labour market intelligence for the archaeological sector for the financial year 2012-13 in order to improve understanding of the needs and current state of employment for the archaeological profession.

The objectives of the project were to:

- generate a profile of the workforce, highlighting any diversity issues;
- gather and interpret information on training needs, skills shortages and skills gaps;
- gather and interpret details of the nature and extent of the archaeology sector, including accurate employment figures in different specialisms (defined sectorally and by post title);
- gather and interpret information on professional roles including potential recruitment and career progression difficulties;
- identify labour market trends and issues through producing and analysing time-series datasets by matching data generated to that produced in three predecessor projects (Aitchison 1999, Aitchison & Edwards 2003, Aitchison & Edwards 2008) including training investment and supply and other financial, business and staffing issues;
- identify potential barriers to employment;

- disseminate the results of this work;
- inform the archaeological sector of the outcomes of this research.

The project has also:

- contributed to a Europe-wide *Discovering the Archaeologists of Europe* macro-project, so contributing to a wider dataset about the archaeological profession across Europe.

UK Context

For archaeologists, archaeological employers and educators in the UK this project has relevance at individual, organisational and strategic levels. At the strategic level, the project offers an up to date and better understanding of the archaeological profession in the UK. Many of the organisations who supported or participated in this project, and some that did not, will use the statistics presented here to tackle issues such as skills gaps and shortages, and education and training providers will be able to use this report to support their delivery plans. Individuals will be able to use the summary of organisations, jobs and employment conditions for career planning.

The Great Recession

The 2007-08 *Profiling the Profession* project (Aitchison and Edwards 2008) collected data in the period immediately before the onset of global economic changes that can be referred to as the 'Great Recession' or as the 'Global Recession of 2009'. The period before those changes – defined by Aitchison (2012, Chapter Three Archaeological Employment 1990 – 2007) as the “long period of growth for the sector” between the publication of PPG16 (DoE 1990) and the onset of the global financial crisis – was a boom period for archaeological employment and work opportunities. This report will provide an examination of professional archaeological employment in the UK following the economic conditions of the downturn, and what effect these conditions have had on the archaeological profession.

Structure of the Report

Following some of the conventions of previous *Profiling the Profession* Reports, the first chapter in this report provides an introduction and background to the project and the second gives an overview of the methodology used. The following chapters review the collated 2012-13 data, each chapter covering the specific topics of organisations, archaeologists, jobs and training. In a break from previous reports this publication includes comparisons of the current (2012-13) results with those of the three predecessor projects within these chapters. In the past, these comparisons had been separated into a single

stand-alone chapter. The first appendix summarises post profile data and another contains the free text ‘further comments’ made by respondents, which is reproduced without any information that could identify the respondent who made the comment. The third appendix contains data obtained on planning applications that are discussed in Chapter 1: Introduction and Background. The questionnaire used to gather the data is also presented as the final appendix.

Previous work

The previous work reviewed here very specifically relates to previous labour market intelligence work for the archaeological sector and reviews of skills needs.

Introduction

The series of *Profiling the Profession* projects have not existed independently of other research. They have built upon and complemented other pieces of research into the social, economic and education aspects of archaeological employment in the UK. The summary which follows is based upon those presented in the three predecessor *Profiling the Profession* reports (Aitchison 1999; Aitchison and Edwards 2003; Aitchison and Edwards 2008) with the addition of material from more recent work.

Numbers of Professional Working Archaeologists

Table 1 and Figure 1 show previously published historical estimates of the numbers of professional archaeologists working in the UK. The earliest available data date from 1922 and comprehensive but partial information began to be collected systematically in the 1970s.

The drop in the late 1980s and early 1990s in the number of employed archaeologists is interpreted partly as a result of the end of the Manpower Services Commission's Community Programme in 1988. This programme was a governmental unemployment relief scheme which had provided a source of funding for archaeological research projects with greater individual participation (Chitty and Baker 1999, 51). That drop was also partly a consequence of an economic downturn in the early 1990s which led to a reduction in the amount of construction work being undertaken and a consequent drop in associated archaeological fieldwork.

year	number of professional archaeologists working in UK	source	notes
1922	24	Wheeler 1957, 122	
1925	30	Myres 1975, 5	
1930	40	Jones 1984, 5	
1952	117	Kenyon 1952, appendix IV	
1973	200	Thomas 1974, 10	
1975	632	Bishop, J. 1975	
1977	1,221	Dennis 1979	'Rescue' archaeologists only, excludes Northern Ireland
1978	1,594	Dennis 1979	'Rescue' archaeologists only, excludes Northern Ireland
1979	1,614	Dennis 1979	'Rescue' archaeologists only, excludes Northern Ireland
1987	2,900	Plouviez 1988	'Rescue' archaeologists only, excludes Northern Ireland
1991	2,200	Spoerry 1992	'Rescue' archaeologists only, excludes Northern Ireland
1996	2,100	Spoerry 1997	'Rescue' archaeologists only, excludes Northern Ireland
1998	4,425	Aitchison 1999	
2002	5,712	Aitchison & Edwards 2003	
2007	6,865	Aitchison & Edwards 2008	
2008	6,516	Aitchison 2012b	
2009	6,081	Aitchison 2012b	average of four 2009 figures
2010	6,014	Aitchison 2012b	average of four 2010 figures
2011	5,832	Aitchison 2012b	average of three 2011 figures
2012	4,792	this publication	

Table 1: Estimated numbers of professional archaeologists working in the UK.

Figure 1: Estimated numbers of professional archaeologists working in the UK.

Profiling the Profession 1997-98

Profiling the Profession: a survey of archaeological jobs in the UK (Aitchison 1999) was commissioned through the Institute of Field Archaeologists from Landward Archaeology by English Heritage and was the first comprehensive labour market intelligence review undertaken for the archaeological sector in the UK. This was conducted by postal questionnaire, and is the work on which the present survey and its predecessors in 2002-03 and 2007-08 were modelled. The data from that project related to financial year 1997-98 and have been used in the present survey to examine trends over the past fifteen years. The 1997-98 survey identified that there were an estimated 4,425 professional archaeologists working in the UK at that time. Respondents to the questionnaire believed that the profession had grown over the previous five years, particularly amongst archaeological ‘contractors’ – commercial practices delivering applied archaeology – with further growth anticipated over the five years to 2002-03. The survey identified the ranges of salaries being paid in different types of job in different parts of the UK, and found that average earnings for archaeologists in 1997-98 were £17,079 per annum, which compared with a national average for all occupations in 1997 of £19,167.

Profiling the Profession 2002-03

Archaeology Labour Market Intelligence: Profiling the Profession 2002-03 (Aitchison and Edwards 2003), undertaken by the Cultural Heritage NTO and the Institute for Archaeologists on behalf of the Sector Skills Development Agency, English Heritage and Cadw: Welsh Historic Monuments was the second comprehensive review undertaken for the full archaeological sector in the UK. This survey followed the model established in 1997-98, but expanded the range of data collected. The 2002-03 survey estimated that there were 5,712 professional archaeologists working in the UK, an increase of 29% over five years. More respondents reported that their organisations had grown than reported that their organisations had reduced in size over the previous five years. There was optimism for the future too, with further growth anticipated for the next five years. Average earnings for all archaeologists in 2002-03 were £19,161 per annum.

Profiling the Profession 2007-08

Archaeology Labour Market Intelligence: Profiling the Profession 2007-08 (Aitchison and Edwards 2008), undertaken by the Institute for Archaeologists on behalf of the European Commission through the Leonardo da Vinci II fund, English Heritage, Historic Scotland, Cadw and the Environment and Heritage Service (Department of the Environment, Northern Ireland), was the third comprehensive review undertaken for the archaeological sector. This collected data immediately before the economic changes of 2007-08 and stands as the benchmark for job losses in the profession following those changes. The 2007-08 survey estimated that there were 6,865 professional archaeologists working in the UK, an increase of 20% over the previous five years. Average earnings for all archaeologists in 2007-08 were £23,310 per annum.

Breaking New Ground

Breaking New Ground: how professional archaeology works (Aitchison 2012a) is a contemporary history of employment in professional archaeology between 1990-2010, using the data presented in the three previous *Profiling the Profession* reports as the evidence base. This work contextualises patterns of employment and analyses the data presented in those reports as historical changes over time.

Discovering the Archaeologists of Europe

Discovering the Archaeologists of Europe was a transnational project, part-funded the European Commission, that gathered labour market intelligence for the archaeological sector in twelve European countries between 2006 and 2008; *Profiling the Profession 2007-08* was the UK component of that project. A comparative review of the outcomes covering the twelve participating countries was published as Aitchison (2009). The underlying

intention of that project was to facilitate transnational mobility across Europe – supporting individuals’ opportunities to live, study and work in different European countries. The project identified particular barriers to transnational mobility within European archaeology, which related to language and to qualifications.

The project was repeated and expanded, again with part-funding from the European Commission, as *Discovering the Archaeologists of Europe 2012-14*. This expanded project involved participant organisations in twenty European states – including two that were not members of the European Union – gathering comparative data about the nature and scale of archaeological employment in those countries.

While the rationale for the original *Discovering the Archaeologists of Europe* project was to support transnational mobility, the funding priorities of the Lifelong Learning Programme of the European Commission changed in the intervening period, and in 2012 this funding stream sought to support individuals and businesses in the changed economic conditions following the ‘great recession’. Accordingly, the 2012-14 project was designed to follow the direction of the EC’s Employment, Social Affairs and Inclusion initiative, *New Skills for New Jobs* (EC 2009a) by promoting better anticipation of future skills needs, developing better matching between skills and labour market needs and bridging the gap between the worlds of education and work.

The project is also supporting the aims of the strategic framework for European cooperation in education and training, “*ET 2020*” (EC 2009b), specifically contributing to the strategic objectives of improving the quality and efficiency of education and training and of making lifelong learning and mobility a reality.

By contributing to the aims of ET 2020, the project is also directly contributing to the objectives of the EU’s *Europe 2020 Strategy* (EC 2010) by finding ways to support transnational mobility and so to reduce bottlenecks to cross-border activity and, through following the agenda for new skills and jobs, by making sure vocational education and training providers are able to equip people with the right skills for their current or future jobs in archaeology.

Participant organisations in the *Discovering the Archaeologists of Europe 2012-14* project are collecting and analysing national archaeological labour market intelligence in Austria, Belgium, Cyprus, the Czech Republic, Germany, Greece, Spain, the Republic of Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Norway, Estonia, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Bosnia-Herzegovina and the Netherlands.

Carter and Robertson 2002

As part of a wider project to develop National Occupational Standards for archaeological practice, Carter and Robertson’s (2002a, 14-16) report, produced by Q-West Consultants and Headland Archaeology, commissioned by the Archaeology Training Forum and funded through PSAG and English Heritage, on the occupational and functional mapping of the archaeological profession reviewed and re-assessed some of the data provided in the 1997-98 *Profiling the Profession* report (Aitchison 1999). This led to the numbers of archaeologists

that had been assigned to particular categories of working environment being usefully redistributed, to give perhaps a more realistic assessment of the numbers of archaeologists working in different areas of the profession. These figures suggested that archaeological contractors, those working for organisations that undertake field research and investigation on a commercial basis, represented a larger proportion of the whole sector than had been identified in Aitchison 1999. This reassessment was valuable, and provided more useful comparative data for the 2002-03 study than the figures presented in Aitchison 1999.

The Invisible Diggers

The Invisible Diggers (Everill 2009) was a project undertaken by Paul Everill towards his PhD research. Quantitative survey data were gathered between 2003 and 2005 using a non-systematic, open instrument distribution survey. These data were used alongside qualitative interviews and participant observation to provide a multi-faceted analysis of the commercial sector of British archaeology. Results indicated that the average British commercial archaeologist was a white male, 32.37 years old, with an undergraduate degree and 7.49 years of 'contract' field experience. This survey portrayed a profession with an exceedingly high turnover of staff, many of whom were becoming disillusioned and choosing to leave after about five years. It also demonstrated that there was still a core of staff remaining from the late 1980s Manpower Services Commission era. This survey suggested that there was a level of discontent among respondents with the system within which commercial organisations operate. 41% of contract archaeologists believed their profession was 'already in a crisis', and a further 36% believed that 'a crisis was inevitable unless changes are made'. It was also reported that both the IfA and trade unions were failing to recruit effectively from under-represented sections of the profession.

RESCUE Surveys

RESCUE: The British Archaeological Trust conducted surveys of archaeologists in the UK in 1978-79 (Dennis 1979), 1986-87 (Plouviez 1988), 1990-91 (Spoerry 1992), and 1995-96 (preliminary results published as Spoerry 1997), seeking to identify the numbers and geographical distribution of archaeologists working in 'rescue' archaeology.

These surveys covered a slightly restricted range of professional archaeologists, concentrating on '... those bodies that can be described as actively involved in rescue archaeology' (Spoerry 1992, 1). As a consequence, certain groups of organisations were not canvassed, including academic departments without consultancy services, museums, and any other organisations which did not (in the terms of the present survey) conduct field investigation and research services or provide historic environment advice and information services. No responses from Northern Ireland were received. The numbers of archaeologists reported by these surveys are included in Table 1. The RESCUE figures suggested that there was a rapid rise in the number of archaeologists employed in rescue archaeology through the 1970s and 1980s. The numbers employed in archaeology subsequently fell away rapidly

following the ending of Manpower Services Commission funding in the late 1980s, with an abrupt fall in 1990 in the first few months of an economic recession and associated reduction in the volume and scale of construction projects. Salaries were examined in the 1990-91 and 1995-6 surveys (Spoerry 1992, 1997). Pay levels were broken down by bands rather than figures, which did not allow for precise estimates of average archaeological salaries. Spoerry estimated that "... in 1990-91 three-quarters of archaeologists in Britain were paid less than £12,000 pa, when the national average earnings (both sexes) was about £13,000 pa, calculated from 1990 Government figures. In 1995-96, just over three-quarters of archaeologists were paid less than £16,000 pa, when the figure for national average earnings (both sexes) was about £17,500 pa, from the 1995 Government figures (most recent available when calculated)" (Spoerry 1997, 6).

Jobs in British Archaeology

An annual series of studies of the advertised jobs reported in the Institute for Archaeologists' Jobs Information Service (JIS) and BAJR has been carried out for the Institute for Archaeologists over the last twenty years (Aitchison and Anderson 1995; Turner 1996, 1997, 1998, 1999; Malcolm 2000, 2001; Drummond-Murray 2002, 2003, 2004, 2005, 2006, 2007, 2008; Rocks-Macqueen 2011, 2012, forthcoming). These surveys form a review of advertised posts from 1993-2013, including details of salaries and conditions. There is further discussion in Chapter 5: Jobs which compares advertised wages against the survey results. The results indicate that advertised salaries are a good indicator for actual pay levels in archaeology.

Fluctuations in the overall numbers of posts advertised and the average salaries offered have been considered to be directly (if crudely) related to archaeological practice's relationship with the construction industry. If this is the case, the increase in the numbers of jobs advertised and average starting salaries is likely to be related to the construction boom that began in the 1990s – although it has to be noted that there has been a paucity of junior fieldworking posts advertisements in the JIS over the years. This is presumably because of the cost of advertising in print media such as national newspapers. The remarkable drop in the number of jobs advertised in 2002 does not appear to have followed any downturn in the amount of construction work being carried out, but the author of the report in which those data were contained (Drummond-Murray 2003) considered that this might relate to an 'uncertain economic climate' in 2002.

IfA Pay Benchmarking

A project was undertaken by the Institute for Archaeologists with Frank Price Consultancy Ltd in 2007-08 to compare a sample of archaeological posts with similar posts in related and other sectors (Price and Geary 2008). The structured evaluation of sample archaeological posts led the authors to conclude that archaeological posts are relatively under-rewarded, with 'a significant gap between current IfA salary minima and external comparators when

matched against a) average range minima for posts with similar JEGS (Job Evaluation Grading System) scores in organisations which employ professional / specialist staff with similar levels of qualifications and skills and b) against published average salary levels for professional surveyors and environmental managers and assessors with similar levels of qualification and responsibility' (Price and Geary 2008, para 17). This report was updated in 2010 (Geary 2010) and the results presented in the updated report were used to set out the IfA required salary minima and salary expectations (IfA 2012).

IfA Equal Opportunities Surveys

Three surveys were carried out by the Institute of Field Archaeologists on equal opportunities; the first of these was conducted by the Institute's Equal Opportunities Working Party with the report published as *Women in Archaeology* (Morris 1992). The IfA subsequently published the results of a Quality of Work/Life Survey in 1995 (Reeve 1995).

These questionnaires covered a variety of issues; for comparison with this study, the relevant topics include gender, contracts, length of service and salaries. Information on pay received in this study was, like the RESCUE surveys, broken down by bands. The surveys all demonstrated that the gender balance in archaeology was approximately 1:2 female: male, the average female salary was lower than the average male salary, and that more women worked in part-time posts.

Archaeological Employment in Scotland

A survey of archaeological employment in Scotland was published by the Council for Scottish Archaeology in 1997 (Aitchison 1997). This was a very straightforward head-count of archaeologists in Scotland, asking for very few details beyond simple numbers, conducted by telephone and email. 37 organisations were contacted, all of which co-operated. The survey produced an estimate of 250 archaeologists working in Scotland in 1997.

Survey of Archaeological Specialists

A survey and analysis of the provision of specialist services in the archaeological profession was undertaken by Landward Archaeology Ltd in 1999 (Aitchison 2000), commissioned by the Institute of Field Archaeologists and jointly sponsored by Museum of London Specialist Services and English Heritage (Archaeology Division). This consisted of a postal survey of the providers and users of archaeological specialist services. The 85 specialisms identified by the survey were grouped into ten categories. Individual specialists returned 45% of responses, 13% came from small organisations (<= 5 employees) and 42% from large organisations (>5 employees). The larger organisations were typically able to provide a wider range of services, and appeared to provide the bulk of specialist services. The majority of specialist

services were provided as in-house services (81%). Far fewer were either out-sourced or provided as combined in-house / out-sourced services. The provision of many specialist services appeared to be either threatened or in under-supply. Rates charged by specialists and paid by users of specialist services were examined. Respondents considered that there was a lack of provision for training to undertake specialist services, both at entry-level and as continuing professional development.

Survey of Archaeological Specialists 2010-11

Commissioned by the Higher Education Academy subject centre for History, Classics and Archaeology and English Heritage, Landward Research Ltd undertook a survey of archaeological specialists in 2010-11 to provide trend data in that part of the heritage sector (Aitchison 2011b). It built upon the results of the earlier *Survey of Archaeological Specialists* and provided data on the profile of archaeological specialists, the charges for different specialist services in archaeology and the levels of competition encountered for the provision of specialist services. The report also identified gaps in the provision of these services, and the risk of potential skills losses in the provision of specialist skills across the range of archaeological services.

Benchmarking Competence Requirements and Training Opportunities related to Maritime Archaeology

English Heritage commissioned research that was undertaken by the Nautical Archaeology Society (NAS 2008) to define core skills for maritime archaeology, within three broad areas of intellectual skills; technical / practical skills; administrative / managerial skills. The study considered that there was a shortfall in training opportunities for maritime archaeological practice.

Archaeology and the Global Economic Crisis: multiple impacts, possible solutions

An edited volume (Schlanger & Aitchison 2010) originating from a session at the 15th annual meeting of the European Association of Archaeologists (EAA) which covered the effects of the great recession on archaeological practice in a range of countries, two of the papers covered UK archaeology – '*United Kingdom archaeology in economic crisis*' (Aitchison 2010) and '*The end of a golden age? The impending effects of the economic collapse on archaeology in higher education in the United Kingdom*' (Sinclair 2010). Each paper discussed different aspects of UK archaeology. Sinclair, using multiple data sources, including past *Profiling the Profession* reports, produced estimated numbers of students and archaeologists in the UK higher education sector. That paper estimated that in 2009 there

were 600 or more academic staff spread across approximately 30 institutions that offered archaeology as a single honours subject.

Job Losses in Archaeology and State of the Archaeological Market

Job Losses in Archaeology were a series of reports produced on a quarterly basis by and on behalf of IfA and FAME between 2009 and 2011 to assess the jobs losses occurring in archaeology following the economic changes of 2008-09. This work was continued in the *State of the Archaeological Market* reports, produced every six months from 2011 to April 2012 by Landward Research Ltd to monitor the employment and economic condition of commercial archaeology in the UK. These reports gathered data from IfA Registered Organisations and FAME members only. The April 2012 report (Aitchison 2012b) also summarises the results of all of the previous reports.

Importantly, these reports focussed on commercial, applied archaeological practice, and tracked estimated numbers of individuals working in that subsector; the calculated estimates were then added to figures from the 2007-08 *Profiling the Profession* report to generate estimates for the size of the entire workforce. The results of the present project now recognise that the non-commercial subsectors have reduced in size since 2007, and so that meant that the total workforce figures presented in the *State of the Archaeological Market* reports were increasingly overestimated.

A Fourth Report on Local Authority Staff Resources

This report (EH / ALGAO / IHBC 2012), produced by English Heritage, the Association of Local Government Archaeological Officers and the Institute of Historic Building Conservation, compared the levels of historic environment staff resources in local authorities in the early months of 2012 with those recorded since 2003. This survey covered England only but still provided valuable data that were used in this project to estimate employment numbers. The survey found that 342 archaeologists (full-time equivalents) were providing archaeological advice services to local planning authorities in England in 2012; this represented a drop of 16% in the number of archaeological advisory staff over the period from 2006-2012.

Historic Environment Record Content and Computing Survey

The objectives of these surveys (conducted in 2002, 2005, 2009 and 2012 by English Heritage) were to gather current information on Historic Environment Records (HERs) in England (mainly maintained by local authorities), data held under various categories such as buildings, archaeology, landscapes and maritime as well as information on the way this data was represented on the various textual database and geographic information systems (GIS) in use. These surveys also looked at the staffing of HER officers. The 2012 survey (MacLean

2012) found a dramatic reduction in the number of HERs being maintained by at least one full-time equivalent (FTE) member of staff.

In 2009, 41% of HERs were manned by at least one FTE; by 2012, this had dropped to 21%. Over the same period, the number of HERs maintained by less than one FTE member of staff had increased from 16% to 34% (MacLean 2012).

Chapter 2: Methodology

Introduction

As discussed in the introductory chapter, the 2012-2013 *Profiling the Profession* report is the fourth comprehensive survey of employment in UK archaeology, following those carried out in 1997-98 (Aitchison 1999), 2002-03 (Aitchison and Edwards 2003) and 2007-08 (Aitchison and Edwards 2008). As with the previous surveys, this *Profiling the Profession* project was designed to build on this previous work and produce additional information. This chapter describes the methodology of how data were collected and how analysis was undertaken on some of the datasets that were generated. Some of the methodology presented in this report differs from the methodology applied in the past *Profiling the Profession* projects.

Project Team

The project was undertaken by Landward Research Ltd on behalf of a consortium of project sponsors. The project was led by Kenneth Aitchison, who acted as project manager. Doug Rocks-Macqueen was the specialist research team leader. Doug Rocks-Macqueen undertook the data analysis and drafted the initial version of this report, which was then edited and approved by Kenneth Aitchison.

The project team reported to a Project Board, chaired by Bob Hook on behalf of English Heritage and also including representatives from Historic Scotland, Cadw, Northern Ireland Environment Agency: Built Heritage and York Archaeological Trust, together with advisors from the Institute for Archaeologists (IfA), Federation of Archaeological Managers and Employers (FAME), Association of Local Government Archaeological Officers (ALGAO), Archaeology Data Service (ADS) and Creative and Cultural Skills. Members of the Project Board provided *ad hoc* advice to the project team at significant stages of the work, meeting in person at a series of project board meetings, and submitting comments by email on the final draft of the report. However, any of the opinions presented within this report are those of the project team and do not necessarily represent those of the Project Board members or the organisations that they represented.

Survey Methodology

In common with the three predecessor projects, data collection was primarily undertaken through a survey of archaeological employers, including self-employed individual workers who were treated as individual business organisations; this was a quantitative demand-side labour market intelligence project.

Unlike previous *Profiling the Profession* projects, this survey was circulated electronically only. As with past surveys, this digital survey consisted of a two-part questionnaire with the first part asking a series of questions about organisations and individual respondents as a

whole. The second section collected information on individual posts within the organisations. As this was a survey of employers, data relating to the employees who filled these posts was supplied by the employers, not the employees.

The survey was designed and delivered using the *Novisystems* online hosted *Novisurvey On Demand* package, a commercial application that automatically sent linked invitations and reminders to the potential respondents on the mailing list. This system allowed the data to be born digital and so avoid unnecessary data entry costs.

All organisations that were believed to employ – or to possibly employ – archaeologists and all known self-employed archaeologists in the UK were sent specific links to the digital survey. This aimed to cover all subsectors of applied and academic archaeological activity, research and management. In some cases no contact email address was available; there were only a small number of such organisations and individuals and these organisations were contacted by phone.

A concern of the project team was that a level of non-response error would be introduced into the project because the survey relied on voluntary responses. Nonetheless, checking the returns against sources of archaeology employers has given both the authors and the project board confidence that the non-responding organisations would not have significantly altered the outcomes.

The questionnaire was based on the questionnaire used in 2007-08, with a number of minor amendments to clarify or gather additional data. The final questions and survey layout were constructed with input from the Project Board.

Emails with links to the survey were sent out from early January 2013 with reminder emails being sent periodically until early February 2013 to encourage completion. A 'census date' of the 14th December 2012 was used, and respondents were asked for data that applied to their organisation on that date. This was thought to be recent enough to the dates that the questionnaire was circulated to remain relevant but far enough from the New Year holiday period to make sure that these did not affect reported staffing numbers. Using a specific census date ensured that no employees were omitted or counted twice as a result of changing jobs. Respondents were specifically asked to include temporary staff, support staff and any unpaid volunteers.

Mailing List

A mailing list of contact email addresses were compiled from a variety of sources including the addresses of 2007-08 respondents, job advertisements on BAJR and the IfA's Jobs Information Service. The primary sources were organisational lists including:

- IfA databases of Registered Archaeological Organisations and Directory of Members' work addresses
- ALGAO member list

- TORC Directory
- BAJR list of archaeologists and archaeology employers
- FAME's list of members
- List of Museum Archaeologists
- List of Specialists from the 2011 specialists survey

Messages were also sent out on listserv lists, such as BritArch, posted in fora such as BAJR and through various social media outlets including blogs, Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn, etc. A request for survey links was posted on the project website where individuals could provide email contact details. Because of the way the survey was designed each person filling it out had to obtain a unique URL to take the survey. This feature allowed people to start and stop completing the survey at any time but also meant multiple URL links to the survey had to be created.

In some cases these lists produced organisational names but no email contacts. These organisations were followed up through checks of their websites and other searches. A variety of organisations and individuals that responded to the 2007-08 survey were found to have ceased trading, in some cases through retirement or by being merged or bought out by other organisations. Duplicate entries from these various sources were removed from the final list. Where two or more emails existed for an individual or organisation, all were sent surveys. In total, over 935 contact addresses were initially entered into the email list to receive the survey. A further 31 emails were added later when organisations were called to follow up on why they had not completed the survey, creating a mailing list with a total of 966 addresses.

Data collection

Beginning at the end of December 2012 the survey went live but most email inviting contributions were sent out after the New Year holiday period. The deadline for responses was set as 28th January 2013, but was subsequently extended for several weeks after that. During the time of the extension, phone calls were placed to almost every organisation that had not filled in the survey up to that point. Additional emails were gathered as the 'best email to send the survey to'. Some of the organisations or individuals were not reached as they did not answer phone calls. Other organisations were found to have ceased trading. Some organisations and individuals declined to fill in the survey with most citing 'survey fatigue'. However, all of those who declined to fill in the survey were willing to provide current employment numbers. These numbers were factored into the final counts and estimates of the workforce totals.

Of the 966 emails sent with invitation links to the survey 213 were returned as undeliverable. In total 234 usable responses from the 753 delivered invitations were received; usable were defined as those that were completed, partially completed or were not duplicates. Sending multiple emails to a single organisation resulted in some duplicate

responses, mainly because of different offices of the same organisation filling out the survey.

These response numbers are relatively in line with the past surveys. The first *Profiling the Profession* survey receiving a much higher response than the rest but over the ten years from 2002-03 to 2012-13 the number of usable responses has been between 234 and 242 (Table 2).

year	total
1997-98	349
2002-03	236
2007-08	242
2012-13	234

Table 2: Number of usable responses to all *Profiling the Profession* surveys.

Given that this survey was the first in the series to be an all-digital survey (2007-08 was both hard copy and digital), the project team was satisfied to observe that this did not dramatically change the response rate. The results of the survey and outside data sources confirmed that the sector has shrunk significantly and the number of archaeologists represented by the responses to this survey was actually proportionally higher than in the 2007-08 survey, because there were fewer archaeologists working (Table 3).

	archaeologists represented in survey responses	estimated total number of archaeologists in employment	% of total
1997-98	2,829	4,425	64%
2002-03	2,771	5,712	49%
2007-08	2,665	6,865	39%
2012-13	2,630	4,792	55%

Table 3: Numbers of archaeologists represented in survey responses.

Conversely, the number of post profiles completed for 2012-13, 389, represented a significantly lower proportion than that received by previous surveys.

year	total
1997-98	not known
2002-03	906
2007-08	519
2012-13	389

Table 4: Post profiles completed in all *Profiling the Profession* surveys.

However, this lower number of post profiles still provided data that represented a significant proportion of the workforce, even if it is not as high as previous surveys (Table 5).

year	total	% of archaeologists
1997-98	2,132	49%
2002-03	2,427	40%
2007-08	2,733	40%
2012-13	889	19%

Table 5: Archaeologists represented in post profiles in all *Profiling the Profession* surveys.

What these figures mean in terms of interpreting the results of the survey are that data provided by organisations answering the questionnaires represented over half of the total number of archaeologists in employment (Table 3) and are representative of the whole sector. On the other hand, while still statistically significant, the data obtained from post profiles came from a smaller population of responses.

Data entry and analysis

The data received were analysed statistically to produce synthetic tables of results, accompanied by commentary. The commentary draws out conclusions from the received data on current workforce provision and future staffing and skills needs.

It is recognised that the survey data are imperfect – they always are in any survey project. “Survey data can be imperfect in various ways. Sampling, noncoverage, interview error, and features in the survey design and administration can affect data quality. In particular, surveys typically have missing data problems due to nonresponse” (Rässler, Rubin & Schenker 2008, 370).

Nonresponse can be either unit nonresponse – where an organisation has not answered the survey, or item nonresponse – where a respondent has not answered a question.

The level of unit nonresponse in this project (234 responses were received from 753 successfully delivered invitations to contribute) did not lead to the quality of the data being seriously affected. Throughout the survey, there were questions that respondents chose not to answer, leading to a level of item nonresponse throughout (some reasons for individual item non-response are given in Appendix 2: Comments). The levels of response were satisfactory to allow analysis to be undertaken, and this is noted by the presentation of sample numbers accompanying the data tables in this report. There was a high level of item non-response to the post profile element of the questionnaire.

Calculating workforce size

A key outcome of this and all past *Profiling the Profession* projects has been the generation of an estimate of the actual number of archaeologists working in the UK.

As the survey has been answered by many but not all of the employers of archaeologists in the UK, the one area where unit nonresponse has had to be addressed through an extrapolation from the data has been made is in the calculation of estimated figures for the total number of archaeologists working in the UK.

Past Methodology

In the predecessor studies, organisations on the mailing lists were ascribed to categories of structural basis and organisational role before the questionnaire was circulated to respondents. This blind assignment was undertaken by examining the source used to add the organisation to the mailing list, through the personal knowledge of the research team and, in the case of non-responding IfA Registered Organisations, from staff numbers published in the *IfA Yearbook and Directory*. Ascribed organisational categories and structures were then compared with those given on the actual returns to test the accuracy of the results. The total figure was extrapolated by using a regressive imputation procedure, whereby estimated figures for the numbers of archaeologists working for each non-respondent were calculated on the basis of conditional means. These figures were generated from the average of the figures provided by respondents that were considered to be 'similar' to the nonrespondent – eg the imputed number of archaeologists working for a university archaeology department was generated from the average numbers of archaeologists working for university archaeology departments that had answered the survey, etc. This is described by Rässler, Rubin & Schenker (2008, 376) as “a regression of the variable with missing values on other observed variables is estimated from the complete cases, and then the resulting prediction equation is used to impute the estimated conditional mean for each missing value”.

Results were variable; for example, the assumption of organisational role was found to be 74% accurate in the 2007-08 survey. However, the Historic Environment Advice and Information Services category was only 43% accurate, while other categories averaged 84%. More important in terms of estimating numbers of archaeologists is that all organisations were ascribed to anticipated categories of size (0-1 individuals, 2-5, 6-10, 11-20, 21-50, 51-100 and 101+) and when compared with the returns, this was found to be 60% accurate.

In the past this was felt to be a satisfactory outcome (categorisation being more important than the ascribed size for this process), with estimated sizes being calculated for all the organisations that did not return questionnaires and that were believed to employ archaeologists. These ascribed numbers were then combined with results from the returned organisations to produce final estimates of workforce size.

New Methodology

While the basic principles of the previously used methodology continued to be applied, for this survey, the decision was made to produce estimates of organisations' size for each sub-sector of professional archaeology in different ways. This was to reflect both the diversity of archaeological employment and the differences in the quality of the data returned and other datasets that were available.

Academic Subsector

Contract lengths in academia tend to be relatively longer than other areas of archaeological employment and university websites normally list all of the staff that they employ. Instead of having to estimate numbers, it was possible to simply look up the actual numbers on departmental websites and be confident that it is an accurate reflection of the number of academic archaeologists.

There are drawbacks to this method, one being that many websites do not distinguish whether an employee is full-time, part-time or on some other working scale. Another problem is that titles are not always clear as to whether a person holds an honorary title or is a paid employee. Finally, these websites are not always updated regularly. Those caveats being acknowledged a comparison of website listings verses the returns from universities found websites to normally be accurate within one or two positions.

Using this methodology, the project thus found that across 40 universities (not all offering a full archaeology degree but still employing archaeologists) there were 440 teaching and research staff. Teaching and research staff were considered to be those with titles such as lecture, instructor, reader or professor. There were found to be 200 research-only staff, with post titles such as researcher, post-doctorate or project assistant. It should be noted that this includes staff from academic departments that are not archaeology departments but who employ staff whose primary area of activity is in archaeology. This determination of primary activity was based on descriptions of primary research interests on the person's department profile.

Finally, approximately 50 support staff with titles such as administrator or lab manager were also identified. This number does not capture the complexities of these positions, as some departments or schools incorporate other disciplines alongside archaeology and presumably some of the posts would be shared across disciplines.

teaching and research	research only	other support staff	total
440	200	50	690

Table 6: Archaeological staff at UK universities (February 2013).

Local government subsector

Several sources were used to determine the estimated size of local government archaeological organisations. There was a very high response rate to the survey with 76 responses, 73 of which gave numbers of employees. These organisations were either within local authorities or were commissioned by a local authority to manage its archaeological responsibilities. These responses were from an estimated 114 such organisations throughout the UK.

These responses reported details of 158 employees in organisations that acted as HERs or SMRs only and of a further 197 employees of organisations that carried out fieldwork and / or had other responsibilities. The average size of the organisations that provided advice only employees was 2.6 archaeologists per organisation, with a median of 2.5. Organisations that offered field and other services in addition to advisory services had average workforce sizes of 15 archaeologists.

size of organisation – staff numbers (advisory service only)	count
<1	4
1	17
2	14
3	10
4	7
5	6
6	0
7	1
8	1

Table 7: Distribution of numbers of staff, local government organisations providing advice only.

Figure 2: Distribution of number of staff, local government organisations providing advice only.

Calculating on the basis of the 37 local government organisations that did not respond, plus the three that did not provide numbers of staff, and multiplying this total by 2.6 (the average size of such organisations) the authors estimate there were an additional 104 archaeologists working in this sub-sector.

An examination of all the local planning authorities that did not respond found two that also offered fieldwork services. Based on an average of 15 archaeologists working for such organisations it was estimated an additional 30 archaeologists were employed by local authorities in both field work and advisory capacities. Taking this number together with the advisory only estimates, in total there were estimated to be 130 additional local authority archaeologists. This produced a total of 485 archaeologists employed by local authorities or organisations charged with carrying out similar functions. The *Fourth Report on Local Authority Staff Resources* (EH / ALGAO / IHBC 2012) considered that the number of individuals providing local authority archaeological advisory services was 342 in England in 2012. *Scotland's Historic Environment Audit 2012* estimated that there were 25-30 full time equivalent archaeologists employed by Scottish local authorities, numbers in line with the data collected and estimates made in this report. (Historic Scotland 2012, 26); Peart & Arup (2009) estimated that there were 37 FTE archaeological services staff advising Scottish local planning authorities in 2009. Considering this together with totals for Wales (Northern Ireland and the Crown Dependencies do not delegate archaeological resource management to local government) this survey's estimate of 485 archaeologists providing advice to local authorities seems reasonable.

National government subsector

For national government agencies and related organisations, almost all that were contacted responded to the survey. Estimates for archaeological staff sizes had to be generated for two agencies on the basis of comparable organisations in other countries. Phone calls to other major potential government employers confirmed that they did not employ archaeologists leaving only RCAHMS, RCHAMW, DOE (NI), Cadw, Historic Scotland and English Heritage as the major employers of archaeologists in the national government agency sub-sector. A small number of other government agencies with responsibilities either at the UK or England-only levels employ small numbers of archaeologists.

Museums subsector

The survey received a low level of responses from museums but phone calls to the museums determine that few employed archaeologists. A total of 42 museums were contacted through phone calls, three museums were found to no longer exist and a further 19 could not be reached to confirm if they had archaeologists or not. These museums had either responded to previous *Profiling the Profession* surveys or had been indicated by other sources as employing archaeologists.

The museums that did employ archaeologists had 25 archaeologists working for them. Moreover, the museums that did employ archaeologists did so in what the museums considered to be “non-archaeological” settings. Essentially, they were museums employees who happen to have archaeology degrees.

Working on the number of museums confirmed to have or not to have archaeological staff we estimate that there were only 90 archaeologists in this sector, mainly undertaking non-archaeological work. This estimate was reached by combining the known number of archaeologists identified from survey responses and phone calls with the 50 curators of archaeology noted in the Society of Museum Archaeologists’ survey of archives (Edwards 2012, 61) (some overlap), plus curators of archaeology and archaeologists found on National Museums websites and those who were part of the Portable Antiquities Scheme. It should be noted that the commercial fieldwork teams operating from museums were calculated in the commercial sector section of estimates.

Civil society organisations

Many membership-based civil society organisations (NGO / charity / ‘third sector’) such as the Council for British Archaeology, the National Trust and Archaeology Scotland responded to the survey. Societies such as the Society of Antiquaries of Scotland also responded to this survey, giving details of 60 archaeologists employed in this sub sector. Based on these responses and lists of similar organisations it is estimated that an additional 95 archaeologists are employed in this subsector.

Organisations that did not fit any category such as ADS accounted for 15 archaeologists and an additional 15 are estimated for this sector.

It is important to note that many organisations which are Registered Charities have not been tallied under this heading – charitable organisations that operate as commercial archaeological field research organisations have been tallied under the commercial subsector heading.

Commercial sub-sector

The final subsector that numbers were estimated for was the commercial sector. This involved those working to provide both advisory and field work services. It was observed in the results from these organisations that workplace sizes in this subsector tended to follow a long tail model.

Figure 3: Numbers of archaeologists employed by individual commercial organisations.

This meant that there were a few very large employers, slightly more medium size employers and lots of small employers / self-employed archaeologists in this sub-sector. On the basis of returns from respondents and known characteristics of large organisations e.g. figures published in previous *IfA Annual Reports*, it was determined that only one large organisation, of 120 employees (confirmed with the company) had not provided response data and that all other commercial providers that had not responded had 40 employees or fewer. This was further confirmed by phone calls to organisations which confirmed the employment of a further 31 individuals at 10 companies / individual practitioners, all small organisations. Furthermore, some organisations and individuals were found to have ceased trading (some sole traders had retired or found employment elsewhere); a total of 31 organisations and individuals contacted fell into this category. This left 124 organisations and individuals that had not responded to the survey and 13 organisations and individuals

that had responded. These numbers were then mapped against the long tail distribution of organisations below 50 employees (Table 8) to generate an estimated number of archaeologists missed by the survey.

However, this does not consider individuals or organisations that were not contracted by the survey because they were not listed in any of the directories consulted. When considering the relative returns that have been consistently mapped over the previous five years by the *State of the Archaeological Market* reports, and adapting the extrapolation that was used in those reports (identifying the proportion of the commercial sector that was made up of organisations that were neither IfA Registered nor headed by a member of FAME), best estimate figures for the numbers of additional organisations were produced (Table 8, last column). These additional organisations are likely to include recently formed or ‘phoenix’ organisations (that had emerged directly from a recently defunct organisation) together with the potential existence of ‘hobbyist consultants’, experienced individuals who had recently left the formal labour market (often through early retirement) and who were still seeking to provide advisory services on an opportunistic basis.

In total, the majority of the total numbers of “estimated additional organisations” were solo operators, such as individual consultants.

It should also be noted that although the survey aimed to include those working in a voluntary capacity within professional archaeological organisations, these numbers specifically excluded wholly voluntary organisations and these estimates do not include volunteers.

number of employees	survey and phone response	% of total survey responses	estimated additional organisations from known sources	total additional archaeologists from known sources	estimated unlisted archaeologists
1	54	47%	65	65	245
2	17	15%	20	40	110
3	7	6%	8	24	25
4	3	3%	4	16	16
5	4	4%	5	25	25
6	2	2%	2	12	12
7	5	4%	6	42	15
8	3	3%	4	32	
9	2	2%	2	18	
10	2	2%	2	20	
11	1	1%	1	11	
12	1	1%	1	12	
13		0%	0	0	
14		0%	0	0	
15		0%	0	0	
16	1	1%	1	16	
17		0%	0	0	
18		0%	0	0	
19		0%	0	0	
20 – 25 (avg 23)	8	7%	10	230	
26 – 30 (avg 28)	1	1%	1	28	
30 – 40 (avg 35)	3	3%	4	140	
large non-respondent organisation			1	120	
Total	114		137	851	448

Table 8: Long tail model of commercial archaeological employer sizes.

Total estimated population

The survey received responses that provided information on 2,576 archaeologists, with a further 54 confirmed through phone calls.

Table 9 presents estimates for the numbers of additional archaeologists believed to have been working in the UK at the time of the survey:

subsector	responded	estimated additional numbers	total	
university (academic)	185	505	690	14%
local authority	355	130	485	10%
national government	477	68	545	11%
civil society	75	95	170	4%
museums	25	65	90	2%
commercial	1,513	1,299	2,812	59%
total archaeologists	2,640	2,152	4,792	

Table 9: Estimated numbers of professional archaeologists in the UK.

Figure 4: Estimated numbers of professional archaeologists in the UK.

Confidence in Estimated Size

Total Estimated Population

Overall it was estimated that 4,792 archaeologists were employed in archaeology in the UK in 2012-13, a drop of 30% from the total five years before. Great effort was taken in confirming this number considering the large drop in numbers. Phone calls were made to organisations to confirm numbers and externally gathered data such as the *Fourth Report on Local Authority Staff Resources* (EH / ALGAO / IHBC 2012) was used to confirm these estimates. A possibility is that the 2007-08 survey over estimated some of the numbers.

That report listed an estimated 724 archaeologists employed by local authorities for Historic Environment advice but based off the ALGAO survey numbers this appears to be too high but only by about 200. This survey puts the number of archaeologists working at museums significantly lower than the 2007-08 survey by about 200. However, even if the 2007-08 survey overestimated numbers by 800 the difference is still a 30% loss in archaeology jobs.

An examination of under estimating numbers in this survey found that to be an unlikely event given that some sub-sectors were hand counted and others confirmed against outside data sources. Unless an employer of several hundred archaeologists was missed or several hundred self-employed archaeologists were missed, an unlikely event, the numbers would not change greatly. Even then under estimating by several hundred would still leave significant job losses.

Self-reported losses

As well as being asked general questions about whether their staff complement had increased or decreased over the previous five years, respondents were also asked to provide specific figures for the numbers of individual employees at their organisation in both 2012 and 2007. This allowed examination of staffing changes in finer detail, particularly in the local authority and commercial subsectors.

Recorded losses

There had been significant numbers of job losses in archaeology between the two survey dates. A total of 66 respondents reported employing 968 fewer archaeologists in 2012 than they did in 2007. 50 respondents reported no changes in staff numbers and 58 reported an increase in aggregate staffing by 175 positions (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Changes in numbers of archaeologists working for individual employers, 2007-08 to 2012-13.

Local Government

An examination of changes in reported staff numbers from 2007 to 2012 found that local authority organisations providing advice and SMR/HER services lost an aggregate total of 100 positions (some gained and some lost positions). On average, these organisations reported losing 25% of their staff over this period.

Commercial

49 commercial organisations that responded to the survey reported that they had lost staff over the previous five years, and they employed a total of 696 fewer individuals in 2012 than they had in 2007. This, combined with 13 respondents reporting growth in the number of staff they employed (representing 73 archaeologists) and 11 reporting no change, represented an aggregate loss of 623 jobs.

It should also be noted that 31 organisations and individuals contacted for this survey were no longer undertaking archaeology or had ceased trading. These numbers, combined with

the loss of local authority positions represent an overall total of 900 fewer archaeological jobs at the responding organisations.

RESCUE Documentation of Job Losses

RESCUE – The Trust for British Archaeology documented job cuts and losses of heritage organisations from October 2010 onwards with a searchable map (RESCUE 2013). This has recorded major job losses across all sectors of archaeology.

Confidence in All Results

Taking these primary and proxy data sources into account it is believed that the 30% loss in number of archaeologists employed in the UK over the five years prior to 2012-13 can be considered to be an accurate estimate of the change in the sector's working population.

Levels of Response

All respondents were asked to describe their organisation's constitutional basis. In predecessor surveys the categories used were:

- national government or agency
- local government
- university
- private sector
- other

However, for this project the possible categories that participants could choose from were slightly altered to:

- private limited company (ltd)
- public limited company (plc)
- registered charity
- constituent part of a local planning authority
- constituent part of a university
- other

The results of which can be seen in Table 10.

organisational basis	number of responses	% of responses
private limited company (ltd)	44	19%
public limited company (plc)	2	1%
registered charity	22	9%
constituent part of a local planning authority	69	29%
constituent part of a university	25	11%
other / not indicated	72	31%
Total	234	100%

Table 10: Organisational bases of respondent organisations.

While category nomenclature has changed, the 2012-13 survey captured data from comparable numbers of organisations to the previous surveys.

organisational bases	1997-98		2002-03		2007-08	
national government	13	4%	19	8%	13	5%
local government	122	35%	89	38%	76	31%
university	49	14%	27	12%	25	10%
private (charity / trust / company)	105	30%	73	31%	109	45%
other	60	17%	24	10%	19	8%
total	349		232		242	

Table 11: Organisational bases of respondents, 1997-98 to 2007-08.

Respondents were also asked to identify their organisation's principal role of activity, as shown in Table 12 (together with the numbers of archaeologists working for those organisations).

organisation principal role	organisations		archaeologists employed	
field investigation and research services	66	28%	602	56%
historic environment advice and information services	67	29%	269	25%
museum and visitor / user services	4	2%	23	2%
educational and academic research services	21	9%	180	17%
other / mixed	76	32%		
total	234		1074	

Table 12: Organisational principal roles.

Some organisations had roles that combined different areas of activity, as seen in Table 13. Considerable numbers of organisations that provided museum and visitor / user services or educational and academic research did these as minority working roles, with field

investigation and research or provision of historic environment advice and information more likely to be their principal roles.

% organisation role	count	0-24%	25-49%	50-74%	75-100%
field investigation and research	74	22	9	24	19
provision of historic environment advice and information	73	15	15	13	30
museum and visitor / user services	31	19	8	3	1
educational and academic research	56	37	9	2	8

Table 13: Organisations with multiple roles.

Over the series of *Profiling the Profession* surveys the levels of response from organisations undertaking different activities have fluctuated. The most significant change in the 2012-13 survey responses was that museum and visitor/ user services had a much lower response rate.

organisation principal role	2002-03		2007-08		2012-13		2012-13 with 'other' recombined into categories
field investigation and research services	76	33%	46	19%	66	28%	42%
historic environment advice and information services	95	41%	135	56%	67	29%	42%
museum and visitor / user services	45	19%	35	14%	4	2%	3%
educational and academic research services	16	7%	26	11%	21	9%	13%
other / mixed					76	32%	
total	232		242		234		

Table 14: Organisation principal roles 2002-03 to 2012-13.

Overall the organisational bases and roles have stayed relatively consistent over time, although there has been a steady decrease in the number of local government organisations reporting.

organisation principal role	primary		mixed roles		total	
field investigation and research services	602	56%	745	50%	1,347	52%
historic environment advice and information services	269	25%	317	21%	586	23%
museum and visitor / user services	23	2%	187	13%	210	8%
educational and academic research services	180	17%	246	16%	427	17%
total	1,074		1,496		2,570	

Table 15: Numbers of archaeologists reported by organisational roles.

Figure 5: Numbers of archaeologists by organisations' primary and mixed roles.

Over time, the relative percentages of archaeologists working to provide historic environment advice and information, and to provide museum and visitor / user services have declined while the relative percentage providing educational and academic research services has increased. The percentages of archaeologists providing field investigation and research services have fluctuated.

organisation role	2002-03	2007-08	2012-13
field investigation and research services	49%	57%	56%
historic environment advice and information services	31%	27%	25%
museum and visitor / user services	8%	4%	2%
educational and academic research services	12%	12%	17%

Table 16: Percentages of archaeologists by organisations' primary roles over time.

Figure 6: Percentages of archaeologists by organisations' primary roles over time.

Representative Sample

The levels of response received indicate that the survey obtained a representative sample across nearly all of the subsectors of professional archaeology, with the one exception being the museum sector. It must be noted that this subsector represented a very small percentage of the total number of archaeologists in employment.

The importance of a representative sample is to ensure that the results are indicative of the opinions of archaeologists as a whole. With almost half of the individual entities (self-

employed and organisations) covered in most of the subsectors, representing a majority of all employed archaeologists, there is a high level of confidence that the views discussed in this survey represent the views of the profession.

With an overall response rate of 224 from a population of 511 potential respondents contacted, at a confidence level of 95% this level of response is accurate to +/- 4.9% (survey confidence calculated using spreadsheet provided by Frederick van Bennekom pers. comm. 3rd May 2013, as detailed in van Bennekom 2002). Some questions attracted a smaller number of responses (as indicated in the sample size recorded for each) and so the confidence level differs by individual questions.

The estimated numbers of additional organisations are those discussed in this Chapter but which did not respond to the survey.

subsector	responses	additional known number	total	% response
university (academic)	13	27	40	33%
local planning authority	76	38	114	67%
national government heritage agency	5	1	6	83%
civil society	7	8	15	47%
museum	3 (plus 42 contacted by phone)	25	70	4%
commercial	114 (plus 10 contacted by phone)	137	251	45%
other	6	9	15	40%
total	224	245	511	

Table 17: Response levels by organisational bases.

Figure 7: Response levels by organisational bases.

Salary data

The second part of the questionnaire asked for the gross salary scale of each post. Respondents were asked to provide minimum, maximum and average salary figures. For calculation purposes the averages were used. If the average was not provided a new average was calculated from the minimum and maximum provided. In some cases, the minimum or maximum was used in place of the average if that was the only figure provided.

Analysis and presentation of reported figures

Collation and analysis of the data reported to the survey was carried out using Microsoft Access 2003 and 2010. Some additional work was carried out in Microsoft Excel 2007 and 2010. Where applicable the figures and percentages presented in the report have been rounded up to the nearest integer from 0.5 or higher. With percentages, the un-rounded figures total 100%, even if rounding has meant that the tallied figures do not always appear to total 100%.

Creation of post profiles

Information was received about 389 different posts, including archaeologists and support staff. These were aggregated to produce 41 post profiles, following the methods used in the previous two surveys. These methods involved searching the database for specific words.

For example, the Academic Staff profile consisted of all posts whose titles included the words 'academic', 'fellow', 'lecturer', 'postgraduate', 'professor', 'reader' or 'tutor'. The post profile title 'Academic Staff' was then added to the database records for the posts selected. It was necessary to follow a careful sequence when carrying this out, to ensure that staff ended up in the most appropriate profile. For example, the profile for Photographer was created before that for Senior posts, so the post title 'Head of Photography' would be grouped with other Photographers, rather than in the less specific Senior posts profile, in which other 'Head of' posts were included. The selection criteria and sequence of selection are listed in Table 18 below. Asterisks * are used as wildcards, so *photo* will select 'Photographer' or 'Head of Photography' or 'Photographic Assistant'. After completing 38 of the post profiles using the Access database programme Update Query with the selection criteria described below, the three remaining profiles 'Other support posts', 'Junior posts' and 'Other posts' were assigned manually. Further several additional posts were applied manually, for example 'Applications Developer' was added to Computing Officer. Four of the categories, Investigator, Surveyor, Photographer and Financial Posts, had no responses to the post profiles.

post profile	words Included within post title
Computing Officer	*multi media* or *data* or *geomatics* or IT* or *network* or *comput* or *systems*
Administrator	*admin* or *clerical* or *secretar* or *personal assistant* or *receptionist* or *office assistant* or *office manager*
Archaeological Assistant	*archaeological assistant* or archaeology assistant
Academic Staff	*academic* or *fellow* or *lecturer* or *postgraduate* or *professor* or *reader* or *tutor*
Education and outreach posts	*community* or *education* or *outreach* or *interpret* or *access* or *exploring* or *open day* or *teaching*
Characterisation posts	*characterisation*
Inspector	*insp*
Buildings Archaeologist	*building* or *blg*
Finds Officer	*artefact* or *brick* or *ceramic* or *coin* or *finds* or *pottery* or *wood* or *timber* or *medieval pot* or *lithic* or *samian* or *glass*
Consultant	*consultant*
Project Manager	*project manager*
Illustrator	*graphic* or *design* or *drafts* or *draughts* or *illustrator* or *CAD*.
Investigator	*investigator*
Surveyor	*geophys* or *survey* or *geomatic*
Historic Environment Record Officer	*sites and monuments* or *record* or *information* or *UAD* or *SMR* and not *archive*. *HER* and all posts that were spelled out in full.
Planning Archaeologist	*development control* or *DC* or *plann* or *historic environment*. A range of posts including the term 'historic environment' were still unaccounted for, and it was considered more appropriate to locate them as Planning Archaeologists than as HER staff or as County or Regional Archaeologists.

Conservator	*conservator*
Warden	*warden*
Excavator or Site Assistant	*excavator* or *site assistant*
Photographer	*photo*
County or Regional Archaeologist	*borough* or *city archaeologist* or *county* or *district archaeologist* or *regional* or *territory* or *national park* or [placename omitted] archaeologist
Conservation Archaeologist	*conservation*
Archives Officer	*archiv* and not *conserv*
Museum Archaeologist	*curator* or *collection* or *museum* or *exhibition* or *keeper*
Senior Archaeologist	*senior archaeologist*
Archaeological Scientist	*animal bone* or *archaeobot* or *archaeozoo* or *geoarchaeol* or *oste archaeo* or *osteolog* or *human bone* or *laborat* or *environment* or *palynol* or *petrographer* or *biologist* or *scien*. Excluded Technician as last time, as word is now used for a variety of different post profiles.
Financial posts	*financ* or *book keeper* or resource* or *credit controller* or *treasurer*
Field Officer	*field officer*
Project Officer	*project officer*
Archaeological Officer	*archaeological officer* or *archaeology officer* or *cathedral archaeologist*
Archaeologist	*archaeologist* or *project archaeologist* or field archaeologist or contract archaeologist excluding those included in other profiles
Supervisor	*archaeological supervisor* or *assistant supervisor* or *project supervisor* or *site supervisor* or supervisor or *field

	supervisor* or excavation supervisor
Project Assistant	assistant archaeologist or *project assistant*. Replaces Assistant Archaeologist profile.
Director or Manager	*director* or *manager* and not *assist* and not *deputy* and not *project*
Researcher	*research*
Senior posts	*director* or *head* or *proprietor* or *principal* or *senior* or *chief* or *team leader* or *partner*
Other support posts	Selected manually, to include all remaining posts with titles implying a support role
Junior posts	Selected manually, to include all remaining archaeological posts in junior role, including unpaid volunteers
Other posts	All posts not already assigned to a post profile.

Table 18: Post profile categories.

Electronic access to data

Data received by this project are curated by the Archaeology Data Service. Information that would allow the direct identification of any particular individual or organisation has been removed.

Chapter 3: Organisations

Introduction

234 organisations (including some self-employed archaeologists, which were treated as individual organisations for the purpose of this part of the report) completed at least one question about how their organisation operated, or in the case of self-employed respondents how they personally operated. Further details of how the questionnaire was compiled, distributed and level of response are given in Chapter 2: Methodology.

Size of Organisations

In terms of the numbers of archaeologists employed in a workplace, small organisations are very much the norm, as shown in Table 19.

number of archaeological staff	number of employing organisations	
no response	32	
1	58	29%
2 to 10	98	49%
11 to 49	37	18%
50 to 99	3	1%
100 to 249	5	2%
250+	1	0%
total responding	202	

Table 19: Size of organisations that responded to the questionnaire.

The average number of archaeologists employed per respondent organisation was 13 (rounded); the median response was 6, meaning half of the employers had six or fewer employees; 78% of archaeological workplaces had ten or fewer archaeologists working in them.

However, the actual numbers of archaeologists employed are distributed in two peaks of relatively very large organisations (very large for archaeology, with 100+ archaeologists employed) and medium size organisations (again, relative to archaeology) as shown in Table 20. As noted in the comments in Appendix 2 some of the respondents only work with several volunteers daily but hundreds over the year so they responded with large number of volunteers. The actual number of volunteer positions is very low but many volunteers fill them as seen in Table 20.

number of arch. staff	total archaeological staff				total non-archaeological staff			
	paid		Volunteers		paid		volunteers	
1	44	2%	0.2	0%	0	0%	0	0%
2 to 10	295	11%	38	6%	40	6%	14	22%
11 to 49	784	30%	105	20%	125	20%	20	31%
50 to 99	213	8%	183	36%	79	13%	30	47%
100 to 249	835	32%	103	20%	372	60%	0	0%
250+	401	16%	85	17%	0	0%	0	0%
	2,571		514		616		74	

Table 20: Distribution of archaeological staff by organisational size.

Figure 8: Distribution of archaeological staff by organisational size.

Essentially, in terms of organisational size, UK professional archaeology is dominated by very small enterprises but there are more posts within ‘medium-sized’ organisations. This definition of medium-sized is in terms of the number of archaeological employees, rather than by the total number of employees in the workplace; some organisations employ thousands of people but with only a handful of archaeologists. This trend had not changed over the previous 10 years.

total employees per organisation	2002-03		2007-08		2012-2013 (all employees)		2012-2013 (just archaeologists)	
	Count	Percentage	Count	Percentage	Count	Percentage	Count	Percentage
1	85	37%	111	46%	45	22%	58	29%
2 to 10	88	38%	77	32%	94	45%	98	49%
11 to 49	51	22%	40	17%	43	21%	37	18%
50 to 99	1	0%	6	3%	8	4%	3	1%
100 to 249	6	3%	4	2%	8	4%	5	2%
250+	0	0%	1	0%	11	5%	1	0%
total responses	231		239		209		202	

Table 21: Size of organisations, 2002-03 to 2012-13.

Figure 9: Size of organisations (just archaeologists), 2002-03 to 2012-13.

Changes in Staffing Levels

Organisations reported that typically they had fewer staff in 2012-13 than they had in 2007-08, before the great recession.

12% of respondent organisations had been newly established in the five years since the 2007-08 survey date and so did not have any employees at that time. These numbers also do not include organisations that were no longer operating in archaeology. 31 organisations that were contacted were found to have ceased working in archaeology. If those organisations were included in Table 22, the proportion of organisations with fewer employers in 2012-13 than in 2007-08 would be 48%.

	2007-08		2009-10		2011-12	
more than 2012-13 (organisation has shrunk)	77	39%	60	30%	36	18%
the same as 2012-13	55	28%	77	38%	133	65%
less than 2012-13 (organisation has grown)	38	19%	49	24%	30	15%
none	23	12%	13	6%	5	2%
don't know	2	1%	2	1%	0	0%
total	195		201		204	

Table 22: Past changes in staffing levels.

Figure 10: Past changes in staffing levels.

Most organisations anticipated their staff levels would not change in the year following the survey. Beyond this first year fewer respondents were confident in predicting the future, although more anticipated growth over three years than contraction.

staff numbers	2013-14		2015-16	
more than now (organisation will grow)	29	14%	45	23%
the same as now	139	68%	72	36%
less than now (organisation will shrink)	21	10%	27	14%
none	5	2%	6	3%
don't know	10	5%	48	24%
total	204		198	

Table 23: Anticipated future changes in staffing levels.

Even with cautious expectations of growth in the number of future employees, most organisations did not anticipate increasing the numbers of volunteers working alongside their paid staff.

volunteer numbers		
more than now	13	9%
the same as now	32	23%
less than now	19	13%
none	66	46%
don't know	12	8%
total	142	

Table 24: Anticipated future volunteer levels.

Historically, employers have typically had more confidence in future growth than proved to be the case.

anticipated or reported change	growth	no change	reduction	net	
1992-93	33%	28%	26%	7%	reported in 97-98
1995-96	29%	38%	25%	4%	reported in 97-98
1997-98	45%	31%	24%	21%	reported in 02-03
1998-99	25%	63%	8%	17%	anticipated in 97-98
1999-00	42%	41%	17%	25%	reported in 02-03
2000-01	33%	37%	8%	25%	anticipated in 97-98
2001-02	26%	59%	15%	11%	reported in 02-03
2002-03	41%	36%	23%	18%	reported in 07-08
2003-04	29%	59%	12%	17%	anticipated in 02-03
2004-05	36%	44%	20%	16%	reported in 07-08
2005-06	42%	45%	13%	29%	anticipated in 02-03
2006-07	24%	63%	13%	11%	reported in 07-08
2007-08	19%	28%	39%	-20%	reported in 12-13
2008-09	25%	64%	11%	14%	anticipated in 07-08
2009-10	24%	38%	30%	-6%	reported in 12-13
2010-11	33%	51%	15%	18%	anticipated in 07-08
2011-12	15%	65%	18%	-3%	reported in 12-13
2013-14	14%	68%	10%	4%	anticipated in 12-14
2015-16	23%	36%	14%	9%	anticipated in 12-13

Table 25: Anticipated or reported changes in staff levels, 1992-2014.

Table 25: Anticipated or reported changes in staff levels, 1992-2014.

Staff Turnover

Respondents were asked “what level of staff turnover have you experienced in the last year (since the start of 2012) - in terms of how many of your members of staff are new?” Note that there was an inconsistency within this question – while the respondents were initially asked about changes over a twelve month, the actual options presented made reference to the number of individuals working for them “six months ago”.

	organisations		archaeologists employed	
none (all of our current staff were working for us)	144	71%	557	25%
some (up to 10% of our current staff were not working for us six months ago)	37	18%	1,237	55%
moderate (up to 25% of our current staff were not working for us six months ago)	12	6%	187	8%
considerable (over 25% of our current staff were not working for us six months ago)	10	5%	266	12%
total	203		2,246	

Table 26: Levels of staff turnover during 2012.

The majority of organisations had experienced very low levels of staff turnover. However, the organisations that reported low levels of staff turnover tended to be small, with limited scope for change and the majority of archaeologists did work for organisations that had at least 10% staff turnover or ‘churn’. Of those organisations that reported turnover the majority believed that their former employees found work elsewhere in archaeology. Splitting the figures presented on former staff destinations (Table 27) into just two categories of left (all left, mostly left and half of split) and stayed (all stayed, mostly stayed, and half of split) suggests that about 13% of all archaeologists leaving archaeological employment in 2012 were believed to have left the profession.

	organisations		arch, employed	
all left the profession	10	14%	72	4%
most left the profession	10	14%	87	5%
even split between leaving the profession and finding work in archaeology	10	14%	141	8%
most found alternative employment within archaeology	19	26%	1,136	66%
all found alternative employment within archaeology	25	34%	283	16%
total	74		1,718	

Table 27: Former staff destinations.

Salaries

Just over half - 54% - of archaeologists worked for organisations that reported that individual salaries had typically risen in line with inflation or higher in 2012, and so therefore 46% of the profession's wages fell or remained unchanged (a loss in real terms) in 2012.

have salaries at your organisation typically risen or fallen since January 2012? (this is thinking about individual salaries, not the total salary bill)	responses		archaeologists employed	
risen above inflation	26	13%	271	12%
risen by inflation	41	20%	940	42%
unchanged	103	51%	879	39%
fallen by up to 10%	20	10%	143	6%
fallen by over 10%	12	6%	12	1%
total	202		2,243	

Table 28: Salary changes.

Quality Systems

Just under half of respondent organisations used at least one quality system.

do you employ a quality system?	organisations		archaeologists employed	
yes	87	47%	1,229	58%
no	84	46%	846	40%
don't know	13	7%	39	2%
total	184		2,114	

Table 29: Use of quality systems.

A significant factor affecting the responses appears to be whether the organisation was part of a local planning authority or university (Table 31). More respondents whose primary role was in providing advice responded yes to this question (Table 30) but given the correlation between planning authorities and this role it is assumed that these two responses are the result of organisation-wide commitments. Larger organisations were slightly more likely to respond positively to this question.

	principal role			
	field investigation and research	provision of historic environment advice and information	museum and visitor / user services	educational and academic research
yes	19	36	2	7
no	32	18	0	5

Table 30: Use of quality systems by organisational principal roles.

	constituted as					
	private limited company (ltd)	public limited company (plc)	registered charity	constituent part of a local planning authority	constituent part of a university	other
yes	19	0	6	39	14	9
no	20	1	10	15	3	33

Table 31: Use of quality systems by organisational constitutions.

Respondents were asked to indicate which quality systems they used. Four alternatives were presented (although respondents could check more than one) together with the option to enter an 'other' system.

quality systems used	organisations		archaeologists employed	
Investors in People	56	42%	478	24%
Registered Museum	13	10%	269	14%
IfA Registered Organisation	35	26%	753	38%
ISO 9001	16	12%	294	15%
other system	13	10%	186	9%
total	133		1,980	

Table 32: Use of different quality systems.

Of those organisations using a quality system, the most commonly applied system was Investors in People (42% of respondents) and just over a quarter were IfA Registered Organisations. The 'other' systems listed as being used (not all of which would be universally considered to be 'quality systems') and comments made were:

- PQASSO
- Cabinet Office Customer Service Excellence standard
- Achilles
- GMB
- Institute of Conservation (ICON)
- Customer Service Excellence (The Government Standard)
- Prince 2 Project Management
- QAA
- Council-specified internal performance indicator monitoring and reporting
- Accredited for quality, environmental and health and safety through Achilles UVDB
- SQA (Scottish Qualifications Authority)
- My organisation used to be an IfA RO, and still retains the Quality Systems in use as an RO. I resigned from the scheme as it was not providing significant benefits in my work.
- Bespoke QMS

The responses to this question stayed relatively stable over the period from 2002-03 to 2012-13. There was a significant drop in the number of organisations reporting that they were a Registered Museum in 2012-13, but, as discussed in Chapter 3: Organisations, fewer museums responded to this survey.

quality systems	2002-03		2007-08		2012-13	
Investors in People	69	34%	72	35%	56	42%
Registered Museum	47	23%	45	22%	13	10%
IfA RO	42	21%	39	19%	35	26%
ISO 9000, 9001	22	11%	20	10%	16	12%
other	24	12%	28	14%	13	10%
Total	204		204		133	

Table 33: Change in use of quality systems, 2002-03 to 2012-13.

Investors in People (IiP)

A specific question regarding Investors in People (IiP) was asked and the results are summarised in Table 34. IiP is the national standard which sets a level of good practice for the training and development of people to achieve business goals. There have been fluctuations in responses from archaeological organisations over the period since 2002-03, but for the most part the levels of commitment have stayed comparable.

	2002-03		2007-08		2012-13	
IiP accredited	58	29%	65	42%	51	30%
working towards IiP accreditation	25	12%	14	9%	3	2%
considered, not yet working towards it	44	22%	12	8%	19	11%
considered and rejected	36	18%	7	4%	15	9%
not considered	12	6%	36	23%	51	30%
don't know	26	13%	22	14%	32	19%
Total	201		156		171	

Table 34: Investors in People.

Table 35: IiP accreditation status, 2002-03 to 2012-13.

Of respondents that were liP accredited, the majority were parts of local planning authorities or universities (Table 36). Those respondents only employed 466 archaeologists; local planning authorities tended to employ fewer archaeologists than other organisations.

	constituted as					
	private limited company (ltd)	public limited company (plc)	registered charity	constituent part of a local planning authority	constituent part of a university	other
accredited	2	0	3	31	10	5

Table 36: liP accreditation by constitution.

Organisations that had not committed to Investors in People were asked why and the results are presented in Table 37. A range of answers were given in the 'other' responses from those who had no control over following it to 'ticking boxes' mentality. Others were self-employed and considered that this was a reason for them to not see it as relevant.

reason for non-commitment to Investors in People	2002-03		2007-08		2012-13	
too much paperwork	1	1%	6	8%	1	1%
seemed irrelevant	10	11%	32	43%	22	23%
time not available	12	14%	13	18%	18	19%
could not identify funding to support work towards Recognition	2	2%	0	0%	6	6%
benefits not clear	21	24%	13	18%	19	20%
other reason	41	47%	10	14%	31	32%
total	87		74		97	

Table 37: Reason for non-commitment to Investors in People, 2002-03 to 2012-13.

Figure 11: Reason for non-commitment to Investors in People, 2002-03 to 2012-13.

Comments on reasons for non-commitment to IIP:

- Many IIP accredited organisations seem to tick boxes rather than provide support for employees on an individual basis
- All volunteers
- Reason unknown, decision taken by local authority
- I work at home for myself only
- Never heard of it
- Already achieving targets
- self-employed
- If we need additional experienced people we know who to contact.
- Never heard of it! - (self-employed)
- Assessments and decisions made at corporate level - progress unknown to me.
- Sole operator
- I'm self-employed and invest in myself continuously
- No idea what it is or what positive benefits it would confer
- Been through it with previous employer and its a waste of time
- Too small
- Irrelevant to my business
- Not relevant to single-person organisation.
- Council did not renew our IIP. It's not our decision to change this.
- Viewed with cynicism by senior management
- Not something we have in Ireland but we have an active work placement scheme for secondary level students
- Deferred until there are more employees than me!

- we already meet most if the criteria and do not see the benefit but rather it adds yet more cost and bureaucracy
- Only one employee - self-employed
- Department has been accredited in the past but wasn't carried over to new unitary authority in 2009. Not sure if there are plans to reapply
- We are both self employed
- only single director/employee
- Don't know enough about it
- We have very many more pressing priorities
- Other priorities at present
- Hadn't considered it at all

IfA Registration

Respondents were asked about the Institute for Archaeologists' Registered Organisation (RO) scheme.

position on IfA Registration	organisations		archaeologists employed	
an IfA Registered Organisation	43	24%	1,437	69%
working towards Registration	11	6%	111	5%
considered, not yet working towards it	35	20%	169	8%
considered and rejected	35	20%	95	5%
not considered	49	28%	276	13%
don't know	3	2%	8	0%
total	176		2,097	

Table 38: IfA Registered Organisation status.

Just under a quarter of the respondent organisations were ROs, a further 20% had considered it but were not taking any steps to obtain IfA RO status. Just under half had either not considered seeking RO status or had rejected it.

position on IfA Registration	2002-03		2007-08		2012-13	
an IfA Registered Organisation	45	21%	40	21%	43	24%
working towards Registration	13	6%	29	15%	11	6%
considered, not yet working towards it	30	14%	83	43%	35	20%
considered and rejected	25	12%	10	5%	35	20%
not considered	88	41%	21	11%	49	28%
don't know	14	7%	12	6%	3	2%
total	215	100%	195	100%	176	100%

Table 39: IfA Registration status, 2002-03 to 2012-13.

Over time, awareness of the scheme has increased as has the percentage of respondents who have achieved IfA RO status.

Figure 12: IfA Registration status, 2002-03 to 2012-13.

While organisations which were liP accredited tended to be local planning authorities and universities, this was not the case for IfA Registered Organisations. Most IfA ROs' primary role was in field investigation and research and very few were constituted as part of a local planning authority or university (Table 40 and Table 41). IfA Registered Organisations are primarily medium and large size organisations with the median reported size of 18 members of staff. In 2012-13 these organisations employed 1,437 archaeologists.

	constituted as					
	private limited company (ltd)	public limited company (plc)	registered charity	constituent part of a local planning authority	constituent part of a university	other
number Registered	18	1	11	6	3	4

Table 40: IfA Registered Organisations by constitution.

	primary role			
	field investigation and research	provision of historic environment advice and information	museum and visitor / user services	educational and academic research
Number registered	19	4	0	0

Table 41: IfA Registered Organisations by principal areas of activity.

When asked why organisations had not pursued the IfA RO scheme a wide range of answers were provided. Historically, the two most frequent responses given have always been that the respondent saw the RO scheme as irrelevant or that the benefits were not clear.

reason for non-commitment to IfA Registration	2002-03		2007-08		2012-13	
	Count	%	Count	%	Count	%
too much paperwork	3	2%	2	1%	7	5%
too expensive		0%		0%	13	10%
seemed irrelevant	30	20%	75	50%	30	23%
time not available	16	11%	17	11%	9	7%
part of a larger organisation that will not commit	15	10%	15	10%	12	9%
benefits not clear	37	25%	21	14%	26	20%
other reason (please specify)	48	32%	19	13%	33	25%
Total	149		149		130	

Table 42: IfA Registration, reasons for non-commitment, 2002-03 to 2012-13.

Figure 13: IfA Registration, reasons for non-commitment, 2002-03 to 2012-13.

Respondents could also supply free text details to explain 'other' reasons:

- A pointless expenditure given that we employ only 1 archaeologist (me) who is MIFA anyway.
- It would be inconceivable for the IfA to audit the finances and working practices of the [organisation name]
- Registration is an incredibly bureaucratic waste of space. It certainly does not guarantee quality of archaeological work, just indicates that an organisation is one in which box ticking is the norm
- Benefits not clear and not convinced IfA working in best interest of archaeology in the UK
- Not applicable
- Too expensive, and when investigated it was apparent that the fees are not fairly distributed and are proportionally more expensive the smaller the organisation. Since the top turnover is still set at £1million or more this means that a company turning over
- All members of staff are individual members so seen as irrelevant and unnecessary extra expense
- Most of those in positions of authority in IfA are not really field archaeologists and have little idea of what it takes to be a field archaeologist these days!
- RO process not tailored for Loc Govt advisory & info services.
- [organisation name] is a government organisation; it employs individual IfA members but is not a RO
- Not appropriate
- Too Small
- Am an individual member but was not aware I could be an RAO as a sole trader
- My organisation was previously an IfA RO, but given the nature of my work, Registration does not bring any benefits.
- Self employed, Member, no need for further accreditation at this stage
- Do not agree that IfA has monopoly on best practice
- Not appropriate
- Utterly and completely irrelevant and, indeed, misleading in that it implies conformity with standards which either do not exist or are not enforced
- Because the ifa pursues a policy of seeking to restrict work to members of the ifa; we would seek to join if this practice was abandoned
- Negative overall view of IfA and its RO's
- Sole trader without sufficient turnover to make worthwhile
- I am a full member of the IfA
- Not happy about aims of IfA - the organisation is moving away from democratic principles
- We don't carry out fieldwork, and our only member of staff is non-archaeological
- Benefits to wider organisation not clear enough to justify investment in time
- Not a member of the IfA
- The RAO scheme is meaningless

- Individual staff are members of the IfA or IHBC
- Not thought to be appropriate at that time for a comparable national body
- Personal Membership only
- Is irrelevant
- Only the Principal is a member of IfA
- It is discriminatory for the IfA to push work towards its Registered organisations at the expense of its other members.

Most of the free text answers mirror the general categories though additional detail was given in some cases. For instance, one respondent felt that the process was not tailored to local governments or that it would not work for large organisations of which archaeology is only one department or subset of the work undertaken. These responses mirror the current constitutions of RO organisations with few organisations that are parts of universities or local planning authorities involved in the scheme. There were also negative views of the IfA or the RO scheme that were cited as reasons for non-participation. These views had not changed over the previous ten years. In every survey almost half of the respondents have considered that the IfA was irrelevant or that the benefits were not clear.

Annual Turnover

Respondents were asked about their turnover over the three years up to 2011-12. The responses ranged from a few thousand to several million pounds annual turnover. Several larger organisations reported turnover much higher than this but they were large organisations and this did not solely relate to their archaeological activity.

The average turnover of respondents had decreased slightly over the three years prior to the survey to an average of £1m annual turnover. This was skewed by a few organisations turning over considerably more than £1m. The median annual turnover in 2011-12 was £300,000.

	2009-10	2010-11	2011-12
average turnover	£1.17m	£1.06m	£1.01m
Responses	59	64	66

Table 43: Average financial turnover, 2009-10 to 2011-12.

Profit Margins

Of more importance than turnover to most organisations and individual traders are profit (or surplus) margins. The majority of organisations reported very low profit margins of less than 5%.

margins	responses
---------	-----------

<5%	51	60%
5-10%	15	18%
10-25%	9	11%
>25%	10	12%
total	85	100%

Table 44: Profit margins.

Figure 14: Profit margins.

Business Confidence

Respondents were asked a series of questions about business confidence.

More respondents expected market conditions to deteriorate in 2013 than expected improvement.

do you believe that market conditions - in the sense of the environment that your organisation operates in - will deteriorate over the next 12 months? (to 31 December 2013)	responses	
the market will deteriorate	82	45%
the market will not deteriorate	58	32%
don't know	41	23%
total	181	

Table 45: Market conditions in 2013.

Almost three-quarters of respondents believed that at least one archaeological organisation would cease operations in the next 12 months. Only 5% were sufficiently optimistic to believe that no organisations were going to cease to operations.

do you expect any archaeological organisations to cease operations over the next 12 months (to the end of December 2013)?	responses	
yes	136	74%
no	9	5%
don't know	38	21%
total	183	

Table 46: Expectations of organisations ceasing operations in 2013.

The overwhelming majority of respondents - about 80%, employing two-thirds of archaeologists - had no plans to expand or invest in their organisation in the coming year.

This would suggest that most organisations appear to not see any advantage in investing in their business over this period. This might have been because they already had done so or because they do not see any advantage to doing so in the economic climate at the time of the survey. It could also be that given that most archaeological organisations operate with low profit margins (see Table 44) that they do not have the capital resources to make such investments.

do you have any plans to expand your business significantly over the next twelve months (to December 2013) (e.g. in premises, vehicles, capital equipment)?	organisations		archaeologists employed	
	count	percentage	count	percentage
yes	30	17%	721	35%
no	140	79%	1,325	64%
don't know	8	4%	34	2%
total	178		2,080	

Table 47: Expansion plans in 2013.

Most of the organisations that planned on expanding in the twelve months following the survey were private companies and/or were involved in field investigation and research. These organisations also tended to be larger with an average of 26 archaeologists employed by each of these organisations.

response	constituted as					
	private limited company (ltd)	public limited company (plc)	registered charity	constituent part of a local planning authority	constituent part of a university	other
plans to invest	15	0	5	2	4	4

Table 48: Organisations intending to invest, by constitution.

response	primary role			
	field investigation and research	provision of historic environment advice and information	museum and visitor / user services one	educational and academic research one
plans to invest	13	3	1	1

Table 49: Organisations intending to invest, by primary role.

Chapter 4: Archaeologists

Growth of the profession

Between the 2002-03 and 2007-08 *Profiling the Profession* surveys it was estimated that the number of people employed as archaeologists in the UK grew from 5,712 to 6,865, a 20% increase. In the five years since then all of those gains and more have been lost. It is now estimated that there were only 4,792 professional archaeologists in the UK in 2012-13, a substantial decrease.

New entrants to the profession

While the number of jobs in archaeology decreased in the five years before 2012-13, the number of potential new entrants did not significantly change. Potential new entrants in this section are considered to represent the population of graduates with degrees in archaeology. They are described as potential because not every student who obtains an archaeology degree will attempt or even want to attempt to become a professional archaeologist. Moreover, not every person interested in becoming an archaeologist will pursue a degree in the subject. Even with those caveats it is possible to create estimates, based on reasonable assumptions, which show that there is an oversupply of potential archaeologists.

Supply from Universities

Two sources of data are used here for student and graduate numbers. The first is *Universities and Colleges Admissions Service* (UCAS nd) which tracks applications and acceptance to degree programmes in archaeology. These data shows a robust demand for archaeology degrees.

In the UCAS data, archaeology is placed under two categories of Physical Sciences and History and Philosophical studies. Under Physical Sciences archaeological sciences is combined with forensic science. This combination makes it hard to identify the exact number of archaeology students; a more detailed discussion is presented below (NB application numbers are much higher than the accepted numbers as prospective students can, and normally will, apply to up to five university courses simultaneously).

	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012
Forensic and Archaeological Science- Group F Physical Sciences							
applications	8,648	8,422	7,567	8,101	9,786	10,441	8,846
accepted	1,878	1,781	1,851	2,049	2,119	2,244	2,018
Archaeology- Group V History & Philosophical studies							
applications	3,078	2,447	1,988	2,117	2,298	2,301	2,055
accepted	614	538	558	526	548	511	485

Table 50: Applications and acceptances to archaeology programmes, 2006-2012.

Figure 15: Applications and acceptances to archaeology programmes, 2006-2012. [F&A = Forensic and Archaeological Science. H&P= History & Philosophical studies].

Figures from the *Higher Education Statistics Agency* (HESA nd), the second source of data, show that there are far more students enrolled in their first year than could be extrapolated from the UCAS data (Table 51 and Table 52), largely because UCAS only tracks applications not what happens to students course choices once they have entered university.

first year students		full-time			
		postgraduate	first degree	other undergraduate	total
2009/10	forensic & archaeological science	650	2,485	365	3,505
2010/11		790	2,340	410	3,540
2011/12		625	2,555	395	3,575
2009/10	archaeology	700	1,015	45	1,760
2010/11		680	1,015	20	1,715
2011/12		710	1,035	25	1,765

Table 51: HESA data on full-time first year archaeology students.

first year students		part-time			
		postgraduate	first degree	other undergraduate	total
2009/10	forensic & archaeological science	300	45	590	930
2010/11		230	30	525	785
2011/12		225	30	310	565
2009/10	archaeology	205	80	630	915
2010/11		215	75	510	795
2011/12		210	155	290	655

Table 52: HESA data on part-time first year archaeology students.

HESA tracks graduation rates by subject area. This shows that 4,700 - 5,400 students graduated annually between 2010 and 2012 with a degree from one of the archaeology subject areas, more than the total of professional archaeologists in work in the UK in 2012-13.

degrees awarded		doctorate	other higher degree	other PG	first degree	other UG	total graduates
2009/10	F & A	60	570	120	1,710	535	2,995
	archaeology	110	565	35	880	185	1,775
2010/11	F & A	75	565	195	1,755	605	3,195
	archaeology	100	595	35	900	200	1,830
2011/12	F & A	55	755	130	1,940	700	3,580
	archaeology	135	585	40	920	150	1,830

Table 53: Degrees awarded in Forensic & Archaeological Science and Archaeology.

Figure 16: Degrees awarded in Forensic & Archaeological Science and Archaeology.

This apparently very large number of students receiving degrees in archaeology has to be considered in light of the numbers of students of forensic sciences which inflate the physical science figures. These are the main driver of the calculated increases in archaeology students as the numbers of Humanities students - those counted under the History and Philosophical studies – have been actually decreasing. This loss is mainly due to the reduction in part-time students (Rocks-Macqueen 2012a) as seen in Table 54 and Table 55. The jump in student numbers seen in 2002-03 was the result of HESA reorganising how students were classified and represents the point at which the figures for archaeology in Physical Sciences are combined with forensic sciences.

history and philosophical studies	full-time		part-time	
	postgraduate	undergraduate	postgraduate	undergraduate
1996/97	356	1,465	301	2,067
1997/98	390	1,427	418	1,891
1998/99	441	1,437	399	2,164
1999/00	430	1,490	520	2,070
2000/01	470	1,475	525	2,645
2001/02	565	1,490	610	3,115
2002/03	775	2,975	780	3,370
2003/04	815	3,105	795	2,975
2004/05	835	3,100	800	2,580
2005/06	905	3,240	815	2,495
2006/07	930	3,285	840	2,190
2007/08	935	3,155	515	1,575
2008/09	1,050	3,080	550	1,510
2009/10	1,105	3,020	565	1,390
2010/11	1,145	3,025	585	1,205
2011/12	1,135	3,030	590	920

Table 54: Full-time and part-time archaeology students - History and Philosophical Studies.

Figure 17: Full-time and part-time archaeology students - History and Philosophical Studies.

physical sciences		full-time		part-time	
		postgraduate	undergraduate	postgraduate	undergraduate
archaeology as a physical science	1996/97	282	1,004	320	30
	1997/98	399	1,280	405	50
	1998/99	479	1,292	422	54
	1999/00	460	1,240	430	80
	2000/01	615	1,250	450	55
	2001/02	625	1,420	390	125
forensic & archaeological science	2002/03	600	1,965	310	190
	2003/04	705	2,755	360	265
	2004/05	835	4,435	495	370
	2005/06	1,085	5,965	595	890
	2006/07	925	6,490	820	875
	2007/08	810	7,365	940	915
	2008/09	865	7,000	695	930
	2009/10	930	7,385	690	1,150
	2010/11	1,025	7,460	590	1,130
	2011/12	990	7,775	475	9,45

Table 55: Full-time and part-time students of archaeology – physical sciences.

Figure 18: Full-time and part-time students of archaeology – physical sciences.

This massive increase in student numbers under Forensic & Archaeological Sciences over the decade from 2002-03 appears to be driven by the forensic sciences. Table 56 suggests that

archaeological science students only make up a small percentage of the Forensic & Archaeological Sciences, although this should be treated with caution as HEIs are only required to report enrolments to Principal Level (F4 Forensic and Archaeological Science). Returns to 4 digit level are optional thus the analysis here only captures those reporting to the more detailed level. 18 - 25% of responses each year for full time undergraduates do not indicate whether they are forensic science or archaeology students. Archaeology science student numbers have stayed relatively flat while all the growth has come from forensic students in this category.

Estimates are difficult given that not all HEIs report detailed numbers but with the numbers that are known, it would appear that roughly 10% of students (potentially as many as 20%) in this category are enrolled in archaeology programmes. It is known that half of the students listed in the F4 subject area come from HEIs that do not have any archaeology programmes so at least half of these students cannot be archaeology students. The number of archaeology students also appears to be steady but is a reducing share of the total as more forensic students are enrolled. All growth in this subject appears to be driven by new forensic students.

full time undergraduate - first year								
	2007/08		2008/09		2009/10		2010/11	
(F410) Forensic Science	1,656	66%	1,551	68%	1,683	67%	1,805	73%
(F400) Forensic & Archaeological sciences	551	22%	431	19%	618	25%	430	18%
(F420) Arch.l science	109	4%	124	5%	124	5%	124	5%
(F490) Forensic & Archaeological sciences n.e.c. (not elsewhere classified)	194	8%	183	8%	92	4%	97	4%
total	2,510		2,289		2,517		2,456	
full time postgraduate taught								
(F410) Forensic Science	255	44%	279	42%	331	48%	400	52%
(F400) Forensic & Archaeological sciences	215	37%	244	37%	269	39%	260	34%
(F420) Arch. Science	94	16%	112	17%	66	10%	92	12%
(F490) Forensic & Archaeological sciences n.e.c.	21	4%	26	4%	18	3%	15	2%
total	585		661		684		767	
part time postgraduate taught								
(F410) Forensic Science	76	11%	105	23%	134	37%	181	59%
(F400) Forensic & Archaeological sciences	48	7%	54	12%	55	15%	55	18%
(F420) Arch. Science	29	4%	29	6%	23	6%	20	7%
(F490) Forensic & Archaeological sciences n.e.c.	530	78%	261	58%	150	41%	50	16%
total	683		449		362		306	

Table 56: Archaeology – physical sciences student numbers by HESA subcodes.

Taking a base of 10% of Forensic & Archaeological Science students being those that are studying archaeology, the number of new archaeology graduates each year would be around 2,000 - 2,100. If the number was 20% than it would be 2,300 - 2,400.

	category	degrees awarded
2009/10	forensic & archaeological science	(estimated) 300
	archaeology	1,775
2010/11	forensic & archaeological science	(estimated) 320
	archaeology	1,830
2011/12	forensic & archaeological science	(estimated) 358
	archaeology	1,830

Table 57: Estimated number of degrees awarded in archaeology, 2009/10 to 2011/12.

Not all of these students will have sought to pursue a career in archaeology; the numbers will have varied from year to year and from university to university. It was reported by Jackson and Sinclair (2008, 10) that the majority of students want to work in the sector - "55% of graduates reported that, upon starting their degree, they wanted to pursue a career as an archaeologist; 57% of graduates reported that, upon finishing their degree, they wanted to pursue a career as an archaeologist".

Table 58 gives a range of numbers of graduates interested in a career in archaeology on the basis of different postulated percentages of intent.

% interested in becoming an archaeologist	2100 graduates per year	2400 graduates
10%	210	240
15%	315	360
20%	420	480
25%	525	600
30%	630	720
35%	735	840
40%	840	960
45%	945	1,080
50%	1,050	1,200
55%	1,155	1,320
60%	1,260	1,440
65%	1,365	1,560
70%	1,470	1,680

Table 58: Estimated numbers of graduates potentially interested in pursuing a career in archaeology.

Table 26 and Table 27 in Chapter 3 gave rough estimations of staff turnover and those leaving the profession. Organisations reported between 235 to 470 postholders changing each year. Only an estimated 15% of those leaving those positions leave the whole field of archaeology, meaning most positions are filled by current archaeologists.

If these numbers are representative of the whole sector than from 70 to 140 positions are available to new entrants. As shown in this report the massive losses in the total number of jobs mean that over the five years before 2012-13 very few positions were created that were then filled by new entrants through the expansion of the workforce. This means if more than 10% of students plan on pursuing a career in archaeology than supply will outstrip demand. Assuming that those obtaining a postgraduate degree in archaeology would be more interested in pursuing a career in archaeology, then potentially, there are more than enough postgraduates to fill all newly vacated archaeology positions every year.

Geographical Distribution

Respondents were asked to indicate both where they, or their organisation, were headquartered. In a change from previous surveys, respondents were also asked where any other, subsidiary offices were located which resulted in a more distributed pattern of archaeological employment (Table 59).

	by headquarters location		headquarters and other office locations combined	
East of England	196	8%	295	12%
East Midlands	74	3%	81	3%
Greater London	740	29%	311	12%
North-East England	62	2%	129	5%
North-West England	43	2%	200	8%
South-East England	341	13%	423	17%
South-West England	334	13%	253	10%
West Midlands	96	4%	178	7%
Yorkshire and the Humber	195	8%	202	8%
Scotland	323	13%	335	13%
Wales	135	5%	145	6%
Northern Ireland	7	0%	8	0%
Channel Islands	no responses to this question			
Isle of Man	no responses to this question			
Total	2,546		2,560	

Table 59: Geographical distribution of archaeologists.

The distribution of archaeologists by different sectors was either directly counted, in the case of academic archaeologists, or estimated on the basis of received responses for the UK and shown in the following tables. This is shown by location of the organisations' headquarters and is not necessarily a reflection of where all archaeologists work. In some cases it may be the case that headquarters is an accurate representation of distribution, for example local authorities with local remits.

archaeologists in universities- total	by headquarters location
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East of England	50	7%
East Midlands	48	7%
Greater London	80	12%
North-East England	49	7%
North-West England	49	7%
South-East England	142	21%
South-West England	51	7%
West Midlands	21	3%
Yorkshire and the Humber	92	13%
Scotland	54	8%
Wales	38	6%
Northern Ireland	16	2%
Channel Islands	0	0%
Isle of Man	0	0%
Total	690	100%

Table 60: Geographical distribution of archaeologists working for universities.

archaeologists in local authorities- total estimated	by headquarters location	
East of England	53	11%
East Midlands	33	7%
Greater London	8	2%
North-East England	24	5%
North-West England	13	3%
South-East England	57	12%
South-West England	38	8%
West Midlands	99	20%
Yorkshire and the Humber	39	8%
Scotland	32	7%
Wales	84	17%
Northern Ireland		0%
Channel Islands	2	0%
Isle of Man	3	1%
Total	485	100%

Table 61: Geographical distribution of archaeologists working for local authorities.

archaeologists in national government organisations- total	by headquarters location	
East of England	0	0%
East Midlands	0	0%
Greater London	300	55%
North-East England	0	0%
North-West England	0	0%
South-East England	0	0%
South-West England	0	0%
West Midlands	0	0%
Yorkshire and the Humber	0	0%
Scotland	160	29%
Wales	50	9%
Northern Ireland	35	6%
Channel Islands	0	0%
Isle of Man	0	0%
total	545	0

Table 62: Geographical distribution of archaeologists working for national governments.

archaeologists in civil society organisations- estimated total	by headquarters location	
East of England	4	2%
East Midlands	4	2%
Greater London	40	24%
North-East England	6	4%
North-West England	4	2%
South-East England	12	7%
South-West England	17	10%
West Midlands	5	3%
Yorkshire and the Humber	38	22%
Scotland	25	15%
Wales	10	6%
Northern Ireland	5	3%
Channel Islands	0	0%
Isle of Man	0	0%
total	170	100%

Table 63: Geographical distribution of archaeologists working for civil society organisations.

archaeologists in museum organisations- estimated total	by headquarters location	
East of England	2	2%
East Midlands	2	2%
Greater London	25	28%
North-East England	3	3%
North-West England	6	7%
South-East England	11	12%
South-West England	3	3%
West Midlands	3	3%
Yorkshire and the Humber	5	6%
Scotland	15	17%
Wales	10	11%
Northern Ireland	5	6%
Channel Islands	0	0%
Isle of Man	0	0%
total	90	53%

Table 64: Geographical distribution of archaeologists working in museum organisations.

archaeologists in commercial organisations- estimated total	by headquarters location	
East of England	262	9%
East Midlands	150	5%
Greater London	557	20%
North-East England	167	6%
North-West England	136	5%
South-East England	430	15%
South-West England	407	14%
West Midlands	146	5%
Yorkshire and the Humber	188	7%
Scotland	210	7%
Wales	126	4%
Northern Ireland	30	1%
Channel Islands	3	0%
Isle of Man	0	0%
total	2,812	100%

Table 65: Geographical distribution of archaeologists working in commercial settings.

archaeologists in all organisations- estimated total		
East of England	371	8%
East Midlands	237	5%
Greater London	1,010	21%
North-East England	249	5%
North-West England	208	4%
South-East England	652	14%
South-West England	516	11%
West Midlands	274	6%
Yorkshire and the Humber	362	8%
Scotland	496	10%
Wales	318	7%
Northern Ireland	91	2%
Channel Islands	5	0%
Isle of Man	3	0%
total	4,792	

Table 66: Geographical distribution of all archaeologists.

The distribution of archaeological workplaces has not changed greatly over the series of *Profiling the Profession* surveys (Table 67).

geographical distribution of archaeological workforce	1997-98		2002-03		2007-08		2012-13	
East of England	265	6%	364	6%	505	7%	371	8%
East Midlands	206	5%	339	6%	500	7%	237	5%
Greater London	820	19%	798	14%	665	10%	1,010	21%
North-East England	234	5%	350	6%	319	5%	249	5%
North-West England	209	5%	295	5%	366	5%	208	4%
South-East England	687	16%	952	17%	1,091	16%	652	14%
South-West England	693	16%	934	16%	934	14%	516	11%
West Midlands	259	6%	249	4%	467	7%	274	6%
Yorkshire and the Humber	357	8%	486	9%	590	9%	362	8%
Scotland	369	8%	456	8%	848	12%	496	10%
Wales	234	5%	387	7%	422	6%	318	7%
Northern Ireland	53	1%	73	1%	126	2%	91	2%
Channel Islands	6	0%	9	0%	11	0%	5	0%
Isle of Man	3	0%	20	0%	20	0%	3	0%
Total	4,395		5,712		6,865		4,792	

Table 67: Geographical distribution of archaeologists, 1997-98 to 2012-13.

Diversity

Data were collected on archaeologists' genders, ages, ethnicities and disability statuses.

Gender balance

gender of archaeologists, 2012-13		
female	400	46%
male	471	54%
total	871	100%

Table 68: Gender balance in professional archaeology.

Responses were received that covered the gender of 870 individual archaeologists, of whom 46% were female and 54% male. Over the 15 year period since 1997-98 the proportion of women working in archaeology has steadily increased (Table 69) and is now very close to the figure for the entire UK working population (ONS 2012).

gender balance of archaeologists and UK workforce		1997-98	2002-03	2007-08	2012-13
archaeologists	female	35%	36%	41%	46%
	male	65%	64%	59%	54%
UK workforce	female		45%	46%	47%
	male		55%	54%	53%

Table 69: Gender balance of archaeologists and UK workforce, 1997-98 to 2012-13.

Figure 19: Gender balance of archaeologists, 1997-98 to 2012-13.

There is a degree of variation within the subsectors of archaeology and types of employers regarding gender distribution. Relatively, private limited companies employed least women.

archaeologists' gender by organisational basis	female		male		total
	count	percentage	count	percentage	
private limited company (ltd)	39	29%	97	71%	136
public limited company (plc)	0		0		0
registered charity	28	47%	32	53%	60
constituent part of a local planning authority	85	47%	96	53%	180
constituent part of a university	85	46%	99	54%	184
other	90	48%	97	52%	187
total	328		420		748

Table 70: Gender by employers' organisational bases.

By principal individual roles, field investigation and research (the largest of the sectoral roles) is male-dominated; museum and visitor / user services (the smallest) are mostly staffed by female archaeologists.

archaeologists' gender by individual principal roles	female		male		total
	count	percentage	count	percentage	
field investigation and research services	149	39%	235	61%	384
historic environment advice and information services	148	51%	143	49%	291
museum and visitor / user services	10	67%	5	33%	15
educational and academic research services	49	46%	56	54%	105
other	36	68%	17	32%	53
total	392		456		848

Table 71: Gender by principal individual roles.

Age

On average, professional archaeologists were aged 41.7 (41 years and 9 months). The average age for female archaeologists was 39.5; male archaeologists were aged 43.7 on average.

Over time, the average age of working archaeologists has increased, by six years over the fifteen-year period from 1997-98. Most significantly, most of this increase has been in the five years from 2007-08. While there may have been increased numbers of individuals taking retirement over those five years, that has not led to the workforce becoming

younger, suggesting that the numbers of younger entrants to the profession has not matched the levels of older archaeologists leaving.

	1997-98	2002-03	2007-08	2012-13
female archaeologists	34	36	36	39
male archaeologists	37	39	39	44
all archaeologists	36	38	38	42

Table 72: Average age by gender, 1997-98 to 2012-13.

By comparison, the average age of economically active (working) individuals across the whole UK in October-December 2012 was 40.5 years (calculated from ONS 2013b), so the age profile of archaeologists is close to, but slightly older than, the working norm. This might result from the near-necessity of gaining a degree before entering the archaeological workforce.

The gender difference in archaeology can be partly explained generationally. Most archaeologists aged under 40 are female, while there are more men in the older cohort.

	female		male		total
16-19	0	0%	0	0%	0
20-29	74	9%	40	5%	114
30-39	149	17%	130	15%	279
40-49	97	11%	155	18%	252
50-59	61	7%	109	13%	170
60+	19	2%	35	4%	54
total	400	46%	469	54%	869

Table 73: Age and gender.

Figure 20: Age and gender.

The long-term trend has been for the proportion of female archaeologists to increase over time.

age		female		male		total
16-19	1997/98	1	14%	6	86%	7
	2002/03	3	75%	1	25%	4
	2007/08	1	17%	5	83%	6
	2012/13	0	0%	0	0%	0
20-29	1997/98	188	42%	260	58%	448
	2002/03	258	51%	251	49%	509
	2007/08	370	53%	322	47%	692
	2012/13	74	65%	40	35%	114
30-39	1997/98	312	37%	523	63%	835
	2002/03	224	34%	444	66%	668
	2007/08	308	40%	465	60%	773
	2012/13	149	53%	130	47%	279
40-49	1997/98	168	29%	405	71%	573
	2002/03	155	29%	378	71%	533
	2007/08	208	35%	378	65%	586
	2012/13	97	38%	155	62%	252
50-59	1997/98	68	32%	142	68%	210
	2002/03	70	29%	175	71%	245
	2007/08	103	32%	214	68%	317
	2012/13	61	36%	109	64%	171
60+	1997/98	10	30%	23	70%	33
	2002/03	7	27%	19	73%	26
	2007/08	23	32%	48	68%	71
	2012/13	19	36%	35	64%	54

Table 74: Age and gender of archaeologists, 1997-98 to 2012-13.

If these trends continue, it can be expected that there will be gender parity in archaeology by the next iteration of this survey (in 2017-18) and that women will make up the majority of the archaeological workforce by 2022-23.

	field invest. / research		hist. environ. advice		museum visitor / user		education. academic research		admin. support		total	
16-19	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%
20-29	64	17%	32	11%	3	20%	8.3	8%	4.3	8%	111.6	13%
30-39	132	34%	94.8	32%	7	47%	30.1	29%	10	19%	273.9	32%
40-49	119	31%	85.4	29%	2	13%	30.1	29%	12	23%	248.5	29%
50-59	59	15%	67.1	23%	2	13%	21	20%	19.5	37%	168.6	20%
60+	12.2	3%	18.5	6%	1	7%	15	14%	7	13%	53.7	6%
total	386.2		297.8		15		104.5		52.8		856.3	

Table 75: Age by individual's principal role.

Organisational bases had only a slight influence on age distribution and that was primarily within organisations constituted as part of a local planning authority, which had a much higher percentage of their employees in the older age brackets.

organisational basis	16-19		20-29		30-39		40-49		50-59		60+		total
private limited company (Ltd)	0	0%	20	15%	49	36%	48	35%	18	13%	1	1%	136
public limited company (plc)	0	0%	2	3%	26	43%	16	27%	11	18%	5	8%	60
registered charity	0	0%	2	3%	26	43%	16	27%	11	18%	5	8%	60
constituent part of local planning authority	0	0%	17	9%	44	24%	44	24%	57	32%	19	10%	180
constituent part of university	2	1%	33	18%	65	35%	47	26%	21	11%	16	9%	184
other	0	0%	90	33%	18	7%	61	23%	64	24%	38	14%	271
total	2	0%	164	18%	228	26%	232	26%	182	20%	84	9%	890

Table 76: Age of archaeologists by employers' organisational bases.

Ethnic diversity

Ethnicity	paid staff		volunteers	
white	830.3	99.2%	32.2	97.0%
mixed	2	0.2%	1	3.0%
black or black british	1	0.1%	0	0.0%
asian or asian british	1	0.1%	0	0.0%
chinese	1	0.1%	0	0.0%
other ethnic group	2	0.2%	0	0.0%
total	837.3	100%	33.2	100%

Table 77: Ethnicities of archaeologists.

Archaeology is not an ethnically diverse profession. With 99% of practitioners being white (Table 77), it is even less ethnically diverse than comparable cultural heritage sectors such

as conservation (97% white [Aitchison 2013]), than the museums sector (7% BME in 2008 – Davies & Shaw 2010), the wider cultural heritage workforce (7.1% BME in 2008 - CCSkills 2009) and far less diverse than the UK workforce as a whole; 12.7% of people of working age in the UK are of black or minority ethnicities (ONS 2013a).

While the UK population has become more ethnically diverse over time, archaeology has not mirrored this over the period from 2002-03 to 2012-13 (Table 78).

ethnicity – paid staff	2002-03		2007-08		2012-13	
	count	percentage	count	percentage	count	percentage
white	2,539	99.0%	2,105	99.3%	830	99.2%
mixed	4	0.2%		0.0%	2	0.2%
black or black british	1	0.0%	4	0.2%	1	0.1%
asian or asian british	10	0.4%	4	0.2%	1	0.1%
chinese	1	0.0%		0.0%	1	0.1%
other ethnic group	10	0.4%	6	0.3%	2	0.2%
total	2,565		2,119		837	100%

Table 78: Ethnic diversity, 2002-03 to 2012-13.

Disability status

There were very few disabled people working in archaeology; in 2012-13, only 2% of the archaeological workforce was disabled. By comparison, 15% of the UK working age population in 2010-11 were disabled (ODI 2013), 48% of whom were in work (Papworth Trust 2011, 2); therefore 7% of the members of the UK workforce were disabled.

disability status reported	paid staff		volunteers	
	count	percentage	count	percentage
disabled	14	1.8%	3	9%
not disabled	785	98.2%	30	91%
total	799	100%	33	100%

Table 79: Disability status of archaeologists.

Previous iterations of the survey made reference to the concept “work-limiting disablement”, as used under the *Disability Discrimination Act 1995*; following the *Equality Act 2010* (and equivalent guidance in Scotland and Northern Ireland), the 2012-13 survey made only reference to a person being disabled or not. The former categories have been combined in Table 80 below. Over time, the percentages of the disabled people working in archaeology have remained consistently very low.

disability status reported	2002-03	2007-08	2012-2013
disabled	0.3%	1.6%	1.8%
not disabled	99.7%	98.4%	98.2%

Table 80: Disability status of archaeologists 2002-03 to 2012-13.

The *Inclusive Accessible Archaeology* project looked at disability in archaeology and found that in 2005, at sixteen of nineteen university departments who responded 282 of 2060 archaeology students, or 13.8%, had some form of disability (Phillips & Gilchrist 2005, table 8). Of the disabilities listed, the most common was dyslexia (63.1%), followed by unseen disability (15.2%). Given the nature of some archaeological work, for example fieldwork, it could be that respondents (as employers) were unaware that some of their employees had these disabilities as they may not have been affecting their work.

Countries of origin

The proportions of archaeologists working in the UK from other countries have stayed roughly the same over the five years from 2007-08 (when these data were first collected), with a slight reduction in the proportion of non-UK European Union archaeologists, which could be explained by the reduction in the number of Polish archaeologists from the level reported in 2007-08, when they represented 1.5% of archaeologists in the UK. Relatively more non-European archaeologists were working in the UK in 2012-13 than in 2007-08.

country of origin of archaeologists working in the UK			specific country of origin
UK	803	93%	Guernsey (2)
non-UK European Union	30	3%	Italy (6) Spain (6) Poland (4) Germany (3) Ireland (2) Austria (1) Belgium (1) Denmark (1) Finland (1) France (1) Netherlands (1) Portugal (1) Slovakia (1) Sweden (1)
non-EU Europe	3	<1%	Croatia (1) Serbia (1) Switzerland (1)
rest of the world	32	4%	U.S.A. (18) Canada (7) Australia (1) Botswana (1) China (1) Kenya (1) Singapore (1) Turkmenistan(1) Zimbabwe (1)
total	868		

Table 81: Countries of origin of archaeologists working in the UK, 2012-13.

country of origin of archaeologists working in the UK	2007-08		2012-2013	
	UK	2,432	93%	803
non-UK European Union	130	5%	33	3%
non-EU Europe	8	<1%	3	<1%
rest of the world	41	2%	32	4%
total	2,611		868	

Table 82: Countries of origin of archaeologists working in the UK, 2007-08 to 2012-13.

Staff qualifications

Respondents were asked what the highest level of qualifications staff members had achieved were.

The majority of archaeologists were graduates, with 92.6% of archaeologists holding at least a Bachelor's degree or higher. Around a fifth of the archaeologists held a PhD. As would be expected, the majority of archaeologists held a degree in archaeology with 12% holding their highest qualification in another subject.

highest qualification achieved	in archaeology		in another discipline		total	of all qualifications
post-doctoral qualification	3	60%	2	40%	5	0.5%
doctorate (PhD)	171.1	98%	3	2%	174.1	18.6%
postgraduate (Masters)	227.9	92%	21	8%	248.9	26.5%
first degree	400.5	91%	40.7	9%	441.2	47.0%
foundation degree or HND	4	27%	11	73%	15	1.6%
school qualifications	24	44%	30.3	56%	54.3	5.8%
total	830.5	88%	108	12%	938.5	

Table 83: Highest qualifications achieved.

The levels of qualifications held by archaeologists have changed over time, with increasing numbers of archaeologists holding post-graduate degrees.

highest qualification achieved	2002-03		2007-08		2012-2013	
post-doctoral qualification	not asked		9	0%	5	1%
doctorate (PhD)	202	10%	263	11%	174	19%
postgraduate (Masters)	412	21%	672	29%	249	27%
first degree	1,131	58%	1,227	53%	441	47%
foundation degree or HND	not asked		39	2%	15	2%
school qualifications	199	10%	97	4%	54	6%
total	1,944		2,307		939	

Table 84: Highest qualifications achieved, 2002-03 to 2012-13.

Figure 21: Highest qualifications achieved, 2002-03 to 2012-13.

age	post-doctoral		PhD		postgrad. (Masters)		first degree		foundation degree or HND		school		total
	count	%	count	%	count	%	count	%	count	%	count	%	
20-29	1	2%	10	24%	9	21%	20	48%	0	0%	2	5%	42
30-39	1	1%	32	21%	55	36%	62	41%	1	1%	1	1%	152
40-49	0	0%	34	24%	30	21%	70	49%	1	1%	7	5%	142
50-59	1	1%	30	24%	20	16%	59	48%	5	4%	8	7%	123
60+	1	3%	17	44%	5	13%	13	33%	1	3%	2	5%	39

Table 85: Qualifications by age.

Highest qualifications achieved were compared with the average salaries earned by those holding them. In 2012-13 it appeared that a Masters offered little advantage in salary over a

first degree. It could be that the increase in postgraduate degrees is the result of degree inflation and / or that higher levels of qualifications are required to obtain jobs than was the case previously.

Qualification	2002-03	2007-08	change	2012-2013	change
post-doctoral qualification		£38,549		£39,977	4%
doctorate (PhD)	£ 27,222	£30,998	14%	£37,193	20%
postgraduate (Masters)	£ 21,186	£25,608	21%	£28,430	11%
first degree	£18,835	£22,010	17%	£28,135	28%
foundation degree or HND		£22,115		£23,867	8%
school qualifications	£15,132	£18,103	20%	£23,458	30%

Table 86: Salaries by highest level of qualification achieved, 2002-03 to 2012-13

Figure 22: Salaries by highest level of qualification achieved, 2002-03 to 2012-13.

Unpaid volunteer archaeologists

Respondents were asked to provide data relating to unpaid volunteer archaeologists who worked alongside paid colleagues. The number of volunteer archaeologists reported was very low making it very hard to draw any significant trends from the results. The very small sample size means that confident conclusions cannot be drawn from these data on the diversity of volunteers; the reported figures on age, gender and ethnicity are presented in Table 87 and Table 88.

age	female	male	total
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16-19	0	0%	0	0%	0
20-29	2	5%	1	3%	3
30-39	3	8%	0	0%	3
40-49	5	13%	9	24%	14
50-59	4	11%	5	13%	9
60+	4	11%	5	13%	9
total	18	47%	20	53%	38

Table 87: Age and gender of volunteers.

ethnicity		
white	33	97.1%
mixed	1	2.9%
black or black british	0	0%
asian or asian british	0	0%
chinese	0	0%
other ethnic group	0	0%
total	34	

Table 88: Ethnic diversity of volunteers.

It is possible to look at trends over time for volunteers in archaeology, but the data sets have been very small which means that there is more potential for variability and thus they cannot be considered to be very reliable (Table 89).

age	female			male			total		
	2002-03	2007-08	2012-13	2002-03	2007-08	2012-13	2002-03	2007-08	2012-13
16-19	5%	10%	0%	5%	6%	0%	5%	8%	0%
20-29	18%	34%	11%	5%	31%	5%	12%	33%	8%
30-39	5%	15%	17%	10%	13%	0%	7%	13%	8%
40-49	14%	5%	28%	10%	13%	45%	12%	8%	37%
50-59	27%	0%	22%	15%	6%	25%	21%	3%	24%
60+	32%	39%	22%	55%	32%	25%	43%	35%	24%

Table 89: Age and gender of volunteers, 2002-03 to 2012-13.

Chapter 5: Jobs

Range of jobs

The second part of the questionnaire (post profiles) collected information on 888 archaeologists and support staff working in 389 different posts, which had a total of 236 different post titles (one post title for every 3.8 individuals). The variety of naming conventions to roles undertaken has been noted in the previous *Profiling the Profession* reports. The diversity of job roles – and post titles – was discussed by Carter and Robertson (2002a, 4). At the outset of their research they expected that ‘archaeology, like most professions, would have a central core of functions which most practitioners would be involved in and that the variance within the profession would be reflected primarily in different disciplinary contexts and, to a more limited extent by additional job functions.’ An assumption that was changed upon completion of their research, ‘the significant variations in job titles identified by Aitchison [1999] in earlier research are indicative not just of semantic confusion, but of very real diversity in work roles – to the extent that few within the profession actually share a common range of responsibilities in employment.’ ‘Practitioners evidently combine their technical / disciplinary expertise with project management, organisational management and advisory and inspection / statutory roles in very different permutations – and no robust, common pattern emerged’ (*ibid*).

The previous surveys established and refined the use of post profiles as a means of summarising information about comparable posts (Aitchison 1999, Aitchison and Edwards 2003, Aitchison and Edwards 2008). Using the methods described in Chapter 1: Introduction and Background of this report, a total of 389 jobs were summarised into 41 post profiles in Appendix 1: Post Profiles.

Table 90 presents an overview of the detailed information received on the working roles of all posts; note that this does not indicate that the overall share of working roles in professional archaeology is distributed along these lines, but these were the posts for which detailed descriptions were received.

post roles	individuals	
field investigation and research	383.2	43%
provision of historic environment advice and information	299.8	34%
museum and visitor / user services	15	2%
educational and academic research	125.1	14%
administrative support	52.8	6%
not given	12	1%
total	887.9	

Table 90: Post role details received.

Responses to the 2012-13 survey were roughly comparable with the predecessor surveys.

post roles	2002-03	2007-08	2012-13
field investigation and research	49%	48%	43%
provision of historic environment advice and information	26%	26%	34%
museum and visitor / user services	7%	11%	2%
educational and academic research	6%	12%	14%
administrative support			6%
other	13%	3%	
not given			1%

Table 91: Post role details received, 2002-03 to 2012-13.

Salaries and earnings

803 post profile responses provided usable salary data. The overall distribution of salaries in archaeology is shown in Figure 23, while a summary of earnings distribution is presented in Table 92.

Figure 23: Annual salaries in archaeology.

earnings distribution in archaeology	
lowest 10% earn less than	£ 17,500
lower 25% earn less than	£ 21,142
median (50% earn more, 50% earn less)	£ 26,000
upper 25% earn more than	£ 33,000
highest 10% earn more than	£ 40,000
average (mean)	£ 27,814
sample size	803

Table 92: Earnings distribution in archaeology.

On average, archaeologists earned £27,814 per annum in 2012-13. Median archaeological salaries were £26,000 (50% of archaeologists earned more than this, 50% earned less). By comparison, the average for all full-time UK workers at the time of the survey was £32,700 (ONS 2012, Table 1.7a). In 2012-13, the average archaeological salary was 85% of the UK average for all full-time workers.

	1997-98	2002-03		2007-08		2012-13	
avg. archaeology	£17,079	£19,161	+12%	£23,310	+22%	£27,814	+19%
med. archaeology	£15,905	£17,127	+8%	£20,792	+21%	£26,000	+25%
average UK all	£18,213	£23,341	+28%	£27,300	+17%	£32,700	+20%
median UK all		£20,376		£24,043	+18%	£26,462	+10%

Table 93: Full-time earnings in archaeology and all UK occupations, 1997-98 to 2012-13.

The distribution of salary ranges are relatively uniform across different organisation types as indicated in Table 94. Private limited companies and registered charities tend to have lower wages than those in other organisations; university archaeologists have the highest median salaries, but these are only slightly higher than those working for local planning authorities.

	private limited company (ltd)	public limited company (plc)	registered charity	constituent part of a local planning authority	constituent part of a university	other
lowest 10% earn less than	£17,200	N/A	£16,100	£19,400	£16,392	£17,500
lower 25% earn less than	£18,768	N/A	£20,000	£23,352	£21,509	£21,142
median	£25,000	N/A	£25,000	£27,054	£27,085	£27,292
higher 25% earn more than	£28,000	N/A	£32,000	£32,280	£40,000	£31,826
highest 10% earn more than	£35,000	N/A	£35,571	£37,013	£54,000	£38,956
average (mean)	£24,757	N/A	£24,716	£27,991	£27,534	£27,534
Count	132		32	161	173	161

Table 94: Earning distribution by organisation bases.

Changes in how organisations were characterised in the survey made it difficult to track changes in average and median pay over the previous decade. Historically, archaeologists working for local and national governments have typically been paid more highly than those working for other kinds of organisations.

	2002-03		2007-08		2012-2013	
	average (mean)	median	average (mean)	median	average (mean)	median
nat. gov. or agency	£23,971	£24,000	£ 29,694	£29,523		
local government	£18,756	£17,440	£23,120	£22,166	£27,054	£27,991
university	£ 22,883	£21,125	£26,293	£23,733	£27,534	£27,085
private sector	£ 17,421	£15,917	£20,916	£17,707		
private limited company (ltd)					£24,757	£25,000
other	£21,036	£20,000	£21,276	£18,903	£27,534	£27,292
registered charity					£25,000	£24,716
public limited company (plc)						

Table 95: Average and median earnings by organisational bases, 2002-03 to 2012-13.

While Table 95 shows there was some difference in average and median pay levels between types of employers, there is greater variation by areas of activity.

	field investigation and research services	historic environment advice and information services	museum and visitor / user services	educational and academic research services	admin support
lowest 10% less than	£16,392	£22,283	£18,993	£19,500	£13,000
lower 25% less than	£18,016	£25,000	£20,323	£33,500	£14,000
median	£22,965	£29,500	£26,000	£40,000	£22,375
upper 25% more than	£27,000	£34,500	£31,826	£48,000	£28,000
highest 10% more than	£32,987	£39,000	£38,956	£54,000	£42,513
average (mean)	£23,236	£30,622	£28,458	£39,744	£23,185
count	335	259	14	95	37

Table 96: Salary distribution by individual roles.

Figure 24: Salary distribution by individual roles.

Those archaeologists working in field investigation and research service roles have historically earned less on average than those working in other archaeological roles, while archaeologists working in providing educational and academic research services have consistently been the highest average earners in professional archaeology.

	2002-03	2007-08	2012-13	2002-03	2007-08	2012-13
	average (mean)			median		
field investigation and research services	£17,264	£20,686	£23,236	£15,957	£18,912	£22,965
historic environment advice and information services	£21,678	£29,553	£30,622	£20,000	£28,000	£29,500
museum and visitor / user services	£20,772	£23,232	£28,458	£22,000	£24,636	£26,000
educational and academic research services	£27,081	£30,865	£39,744	£28,000	£30,000	£40,000
administrative support			£23,185			£28,000

Table 97: Average and median earnings by post role, 2002-03 to 2012-13.

Profiling the Profession and Jobs in British Archaeology.

Chapter 2: Methodology discussed the *Jobs in British Archaeology* (JIB) series of reports. These reports present data on archaeological pay for almost 20 years (Figure 25). However, there has been limited comparison of this dataset with the data provided by the *Profiling the Profession* post profiles

Figure 25: Annual pay rates of archaeologists for the Jobs in British Archaeology series.

Differences in terminology and characterisation between the studies, as the *Profiling the Profession* post profiles are broken into 41 categories while JIB uses less than a dozen, have limited comparisons in the past. Converting the post profiles to the same categories as the JIB ones shows that both data sources match closely (Figure 26).

This was done by taking similar post profiles and combining them into a single category. For example, for excavator the profiles for archaeological assistant, excavator or site assistant and project assistant were all combined into a single excavator category and the salaries averaged. All of these positions had similar profiles e.g. junior positions, involved in fieldwork, *etc.* which indicated that while titles differed the actual work undertaken by the people working in those positions was similar or the same. For Field Officer the post profiles of Field Officer and Project Officer were combined. Other categories, like consultants, did not need to be converted and could be compared directly.

Figure 26: Comparison of salaries from Profiling the Profession and Jobs in British Archaeology.

The results of the comparison shows that data taken from job advertisements, in the case of JIB, is comparable with data collected from surveys of employment status. This would indicate that JIB is an accurate reflection of pay and can be used to estimate earnings in the years between the larger *Profiling the Profession* surveys.

IfA salary minima

At the time of the survey (in 2012-13), the IfA required that its members paid any employees at least the following minimum salaries.

- PIfA responsibilities £15,836.80
- AlfA responsibilities £18,445.77
- MIfA responsibilities £23,884.60

These were binding upon IfA Registered Organisations, and related to the level of responsibilities for particular posts, rather than to membership grades actually held by individuals.

- 97.5% of posts were paid more than the PIfA recommended minimum (in 2007-08, 94.1% of posts paid more than the then PIfA recommended minimum) ;
- 86.6% of posts were paid more than the AlfA recommended minimum;
- 66.7% of posts were paid more than the MIfA recommended minimum.

In addition to these binding figures, IfA also provided guidance on 'acceptable' salary levels: "For the guidance of employers seeking to determine appropriate starting salaries for archaeologists, we provide the following figures based on a study of salary levels in comparative professions. PIfA level responsibilities £18,700 - £20,100; AlfA level responsibilities £25,800 - £29,000; MIfA level responsibilities £31,800 - £37,000" (IfA 2012).

IfA employing members were "encouraged" and Registered Organisations were "expected" to provide a package of employment benefits, defining employer pension contributions, length of working week, paid annual leave and sick leave, and if employers do not meet these requirements they are expected to enhance remuneration in lieu of these (IfA 2009b)

Subsequent to the survey, IfA Council resolved on 31st January 2013 "that it should not continue to make compliance with minimum salary recommendations an absolute requirement of Registered Organisation status" (IfA 2013).

Earnings in other occupations

Archaeological earnings were compared with other major occupational groupings across the UK workforce (ONS 2012) and with professional conservation (Aitchison 2013) in Table 98.

industrial sector	median gross annual earnings
managers, directors and senior officials	£38,579
professional occupations	£36,369
associate professional and technical occupations	£30,120
<i>all workers</i>	£26,500
archaeology	£26,000
conservators	£26,000
administrative and secretarial occupations	£20,591
skilled trades occupations	£24,394
caring, leisure and other service occupations	£17,427
sales and customer service occupations	£16,935
process, plant and machine operatives	£22,336
elementary occupations	£17,443

Table 98: Median full-time gross earnings by major occupation groups.

Overall, the median level of earnings in archaeology is only slightly lower than the national figure for all occupations, and is effectively exactly the same as in the related profession of conservation. However, the typical archaeologist's income is far below the UK median figure for professional occupations.

Earnings by gender

Male archaeologists on average earned more than female archaeologists (Table 99). However, as discussed in Chapter Four there were more male archaeologists in the older cohorts and, as shown in Table 100 below, there is a clear correlation between age and earnings in archaeology.

	lowest 10%	lower 25%	median	higher 25%	highest 10%	mean	sample
female	£17,065	£21,142	£25,000	£29,500	£38,956	£25,479	381.5
male	£17,500	£21,509	£27,000	£34,549	£44,300	£27,628	450.8

Table 99: Earnings by gender.

Earnings by age

Table 100 shows the distribution of salaries across the age groups. On the assumption that age may serve as a proxy for experience, the logical assumption is that those with more experience are receiving higher salaries.

	lowest 10%	lower 25%	median	higher 25%	highest 10%	Mean	sample
16-19						£34,500	2
20-29	£16,392	£17,500	£19,923	£24,640	£28,000	£21,043	110.6
30-39	£17,000	£19,923	£25,000	£29,500	£35,000	£24,574	275.9
40-49	£18,144	£23,160	£27,085	£34,500	£40,500	£28,732	237.5
50-59	£18,750	£24,000	£29,000	£34,000	£40,500	£29,557	161.6
60+	£17,000	£25,000	£32,000	£44,766	£54,000	£31,283	44.7

Table 100: Earnings by age.

As shown in Table 101 the difference in salaries for genders can be considered to be the result of the distribution of genders across age groups.

age	gender	average salary	responses
16-19	female	£ -	0
	male	£ 34,500	2
20-29	female	£ 21,525	71.6
	male	£ 20,159	39
30-39	female	£ 24,566	145.9
	male	£ 24,582	130
40-49	female	£ 27,515	91.5
	male	£ 29,495	146
50-59	female	£ 28,515	57.3
	male	£ 30,130	104.3
60+	female	£ 29,162	15.2
	male	£ 26,015	29.5

Table 101: Earnings by age and gender.

Figure 27: Earnings by age and gender.

Salary scales

Most organisations, employing 86% of the archaeologists represented by this survey, used salary scales of some sort.

use of salary scales	organisations		archaeologists employed	
	count	percentage	count	percentage
yes	128	68%	1,862	86%
no	58	31%	301	14%
don't know	1	1%	1	0%
total	187		2,164	

Table 102: Use of salary scales by organisations.

A breakdown of the different scales can be seen in Table 103; over time, local authority scales have consistently been the most commonly used.

salary scale used	1997-98		2002-03		2007-08		2012-13	
civil service	12	5%	12	7%	7	5%	3	2%
local authority	133	59%	89	51%	79	55%	73	57%
university	54	24%	26	15%	23	16%	21	16%
locally-defined or own scale	21	9%	43	25%	30	21%	19	15%
other	4	2%	3	2%	4	3%	13	10%
total	224		173		143		129	

Table 103: Types of salary scale used.

Scales identified in the 'other' category

- IfA (4)
- BAJR (3)
- Own scale based on IfA and BAJR rates (2)
- Our own system
- both a local authority and a university
- Follows Welsh Archaeological Trusts Scheme (in abeyance) but grades respected, scales are tied to Local Government SPs but are currently paid at 4.89% above last agreed and published rates.

Employee rights and benefits

A total of 234 responses were obtained to the questions about employee rights and benefits. 38 of these responses did not answer any of the questions; one of the non-respondents commented that they felt that the "questions were not relevant as they were a sole trader".

Paid holiday

Paid holiday is a right not a benefit, which applies to 'employees' and 'workers' as defined in law. Employees are those working under a contract of employment, written or verbal, by which the terms and conditions of employment have been agreed. The category of workers is broader than 'employees' and normally excludes those who are self-employed. Most agency workers, short term casual workers and some freelancers are likely to be workers but not employees.

In 2012-13 the entitlement was for 5.6 weeks *per annum*, equating to 28 days for a person working five-day weeks. This right was established by the *Working Time Regulations 1998*,

as amended in 2003. This entitlement can include bank holidays. 12% of respondents reported not offering 28 days of paid holiday (Table 104). However, only 8 of these responses were from respondents that employed more than one archaeologist. It is possible that some respondents misinterpreted the “or more” wording of the question or because they are self-employed they felt that it does not apply to them. Otherwise it appears that several respondents were not aware of their legal responsibilities to their employees.

28 or more days paid holiday leave per annum	organisations		archaeologists employed	
	count	percentage	count	percentage
yes	144	73%	1,889.1	86%
no	24	12%	271.8	12%
don't know	28	14%	31	1%
total	196	100%	2,191.9	100%

Table 104: Paid holiday.

Maternity leave

Paid maternity leave over and above Statutory Maternity Leave is an employee benefit not a right, which was offered by 53% of responding organisations covering 54% of archaeologists. The legal period of Statutory Maternity Leave is 52 weeks, made up of 26 weeks Ordinary Maternity Leave and 26 weeks Additional Maternity Leave. Statutory Maternity Pay is paid for up to 39 weeks.

the opportunity to take unpaid maternity leave	organisations		archaeologists employed	
	count	percentage	count	percentage
yes	135	70%	2,046	95%
no	11	6%	24	1%
don't know	48	25%	87	4%
total	194	100%	2,157	100%

Table 105: Maternity leave.

Paternity leave

Statutory paid paternity leave consists of up to two weeks for employees who meet the relevant criteria. The employers of 50% of archaeologists offered paid paternity leave over and above the statutory minimum.

There is no statutory period of unpaid paternity leave, but fathers who meet the relevant conditions could take a proportion of their legal allowance of thirteen weeks parental leave (see above) following the birth of a child. 93% of archaeologist worked at organisations that offered fathers the opportunity to take unpaid paternity leave (Table 106).

the opportunity to take unpaid paternity leave	organisations	archaeologists
--	---------------	----------------

			employed	
yes	120	63%	1,999	93%
no	16	8%	44	2%
don't know	56	29%	108	5%
total	192	100%	2,151	100%

Table 106: Paternity leave.

Both parents of a child also have the right to parental leave, consisting of thirteen weeks off work (in total, not per year). This is given for each child, up to their fifth birthday (or up to five years after the placement date of an adopted child). For disabled children it is eighteen weeks, up to the child's 18th birthday. Parental leave is usually unpaid, is limited to employees, rather than casual or agency staff, and generally requires a year of continuous service from the same employer.

Subsistence or subsidised accommodation

Most organisations did not provide any sort of subsidised accommodation or subsistence allowance. 77% of those that provided this benefit identified field investigation and research services as their primary role.

subsidised accommodation or subsistence allowance	organisations		archaeologists employed	
yes	49	26%	1,089	51%
no	90	47%	882	41%
don't know	52	27%	157	7%
total	191	100%	2,128	100%

Table 107: Subsidised accommodation or subsistence allowance.

Other benefits

Respondents were asked whether they provided further benefits for their staff.

benefit	yes		no		don't know	
	count	percentage	count	percentage	count	percentage
occupational sick pay (paid sickness leave over required by law)	130	67%	30	15%	34	18%
paid maternity leave over and above statutory minimum	103	53%	46	24%	44	23%
paid paternity leave over and above statutory minimum	72	38%	61	32%	59	31%
the opportunity to jobshare or use other flexible working arrangements	133	69%	21	11%	39	20%

Table 98: Other benefits offered by organisations.

benefit	yes		no		don't know	
	count	percentage	count	percentage	count	percentage
occupational sick pay (paid sickness leave over required by law)	2,045.5	93%	103.6	5%	39.8	2%
paid maternity leave over and above statutory minimum	1,193	55%	925	42%	65	3%
paid paternity leave over and above statutory minimum	1,087	50%	983	45%	112	5%
the opportunity to jobshare or use other flexible working arrangements	2,013	93%	89	4%	59	3%

Table 108: Other benefits offered by numbers of archaeologists employed.

Occupational sick pay

Sick pay over and above Statutory Sick Pay is a benefit not a right, as defined by the law. The majority of employers provided this benefit.

Flexible working

'Flexible working' describes any working pattern adapted to suit an employee's needs, such as part-time, flexi-time, annualised hours, compressed hours, staggered hours or job sharing. Whilst anyone may ask their employer for flexible work arrangements, there is a statutory right for employees who are parents or carers and who meet certain conditions to ask for flexible working. Under the law the employer must seriously consider such an application, but is permitted to deny the application if there is a good business reason not to agree.

The opportunity to jobshare or to use other flexible working arrangements was offered as a benefit by the majority of employing organisations.

Trends in Employee Benefits

Most of the benefits provided by employers have stayed constant over the 15 years of the *Profiling the Profession* survey series. There has been a decrease in the numbers offering maternity leave above the required but that is most likely the result of an increase in the period of Statutory Maternity Pay.

employee rights / benefits	1997-98	2002-03	2007-08	2012-13
20 or more days paid holiday leave per annum, 28 days 2012-2013		97%	100%	86%
occupational sick pay (paid sickness leave over and above Statutory Sick Pay)	82%	92%	96%	93%
paid maternity leave over and above Statutory Maternity Pay		67%	60%	54%
the opportunity to take unpaid maternity leave		90%	80%	95%
paid paternity leave 2002-03 Paid paternity leave over and above Statutory Paternity Pay 2007-08, 2012-2013	64%	72%	63%	50%
the opportunity to take unpaid paternity leave		84%	80%	93%
the opportunity to jobshare or use other flexible working arrangements		89%	97%	93%
subsidised accommodation or subsistence allowance	55%	59%	71%	51%

Table 109: Employee rights / benefits, 1997-98 to 2012-13.

Additional benefits

Respondents were also given the opportunity to list any additional benefits that they offered to their employees, if applicable. The most frequently reported benefit was the payment of IfA subscriptions; the full list is reproduced *verbatim* below.

- 100% funding IfA subscriptions, final salary pension scheme, salary sacrifice schemes (child care vouchers, cycle-2-work), additional holiday up to 31 with service, right to request up to 5 days unpaid leave, occupational health/employee counselling service
- 50% contribution to IfA contributory pension scheme Free DSE sight tests Free PPE
- 50% subscription to IfA membership and other relevant professional bodies Membership of final salary pension scheme
- 75% IfA subscriptions. Final salary pension scheme. Protective clothing etc.
- a very good pension scheme, flexible working hours
- Additional accident benefits after one year's service

- All employees have matching employer contributions to a pension scheme. All employees have a healthcare cash plan. Private medical insurance for senior staff. IfA membership paid for all staff who are members.
- As self-employed I'm able to claim allowable expenses against tax
- Both employees are Directors and as such sacrifice most normal employee benefits to keep the Company going. The answers above reflect our desire to provide future employees with the benefits that professional graduate employees should expect
- Can't really answer this usefully. As (newly) self-employed, the first two points are dependent on building up the business. The rest are irrelevant to me.
- City Council subsidises bus and rail travel and access to sports centres.
- Council funds professional subs
- Employer recognises Prospect Union and enters into joint negotiation on all employment policies and pay.
- Employers contribution to contributory pension scheme. Union membership permitted. Paid training. Travel expenses.
- Entry to end salary pension scheme; two additional company days holiday (normally at xmas); IfA Professional Fees; also reviewing possible sickness/ill-health cover; support for distance learning costs if in training plans (fixed budget pa).
- Full cover of IfA subscriptions 2 days paid leave to attend training cover of training course up to £500
- Fund 50% IfA subscription and joining fee Final salary pension scheme with 10.3 employer contribution
- Fund IFA subscriptions (7)
- Fund IfA Subscriptions and other bodies. Occupational Pension above minima levels. Fund training courses.
- Fund IfA subscriptions Private medical for some employees Company phone Use of company vehicle when available
- fund IfA subscriptions; fund HSE Certificated First Aid courses; provide paid opportunity to attend IfA Conference and other agreed training
- Funded IFA subs; free software (MS office, adobe, etc.); 3 days additional leave at Xmas not from a/l; 5 days funded training/conference days; free training courses across a wide range of technical skills (but principally IT); various staff subsidy scheme
- Funded IfA subscriptions & conference attendance profit share scheme
- Funding ALGAO membership Pension
- funding CBA subs funding CIA subs
- Funding for Ifa subscriptions, Homeworking, pension, employee assistance programs,
- Funding, IFA Car lease scheme
- Funding IfA subscriptions (but not necessarily in 2013/14) Attendance costs for CPD courses and events (but not necessarily in 2013/14)
- Funding of professional subscriptions and membership of Society of Antiquaries of London etc
- funding professional memberships IFA IHBC etc.

- Funding professional subscriptions
- Gratuity leave over Christmas; free tea and coffee
- HS Membership, EdenRed, 20% discount on HS shops, PCS Pension Scheme, Childcare Vouchers
- I am self-employed, so I pay for everything myself, including CPD and continuing academic study
- IfA membership Benefits package which includes health insurance, life insurance, plus a variety of other options (including purchase of additional annual leave, dental cover, childcare vouchers etc)
- IFA subs (but these are tax deductible anyway so the taxman pays -so it isn't really a benefit from the employer)
- IfA subs paid, normally to include attendance at conference
- IfA subs, BUPA health insurance, salary protection insurance
- Ifa Subscription funding, Paid training days
- IfA subscription only paid for one staff
- IFA subscription PPE First Aid allowance Fire Warden allowance
- IFA subscriptions currently would be paid
- IfA subscriptions, all out of pocket expenses paid, flexible benefits including private healthcare, option to buy/sell holiday, dental insurance etc.
- IFA subscriptions, Clothing Allowance, Pensions contribution, Bonus payments when applicable, Bike to work scheme
- IFA Woolhope, Castle Studies, CBA, Newcomen
- I'm self employed so benefits are only possible if I have enough orders
- library access for research and CpD
- local authority pension scheme
- Local Government Pension Scheme, Child Care Vouchers, Cycle Scheme, Car user allowance, Free Car Parking, BUPA Cash Plan, Green Transport scheme
- Local Government pension scheme.
- local government pension.
- Mileage allowance
- na
- [*organisation name*] is a Govt Arms Length Body and as such provides excellent employee benefits: Civil Service pension; funding professional subscriptions; work clothing; supports working at home; subsidised schemes for bicycles, healthcare etc
- NB please note that where we have ticked 'no' above that is because these areas are not 'rights', but we always try to accommodate staff requests for unpaid leave where we can, and we usually go beyond statutory options where that is feasible and reason
- None
- None (no employees)
- Not applicable
- Not relevant to a sole trader
- Paid training and time in lieu for travel/overtime etc.
- Pay travel to the office if by public transport, although this is tax-deductable.

- pension
- Pension Scheme Funding IfA Subscription
- Pension; Life Assurance; Childcare vouchers; Eye care scheme; Season ticket loans; Cycle Scheme; funding IfA applications/subscriptions;
- pensions
- Private health care (qualifying period)
- Professional fees and subscriptions are business expenses, and therefore tax deductible.
- Professional Subscriptions paid Employer pension contribution Car Allowance for Senior and above (but lower mileage rate) Private health cover Travel insurance
- Profit related bonus
- Provision of PPE. Training courses
- Regarding above last question: provided on 'away' jobs only. Payment for IfA membership is open to all employees.
- Shared decision-making in the co-operative
- sole trader so fund all benefits and subs myself
- subscription funding
- Subscriptions paid for professional membership of relevant organisations (e.g. IfA), Attendance at conferences paid (fee, accommodation, time)
- Subsidised cycle purchase/car loans, subsidised gym subscriptions.
- Training, IfA and other subscriptions are funded, volunteering on work time opportunities, etc. (Local Authority benefits are myriad).
- travel expenses
- We are a partnership, so both self-employed, we aim to run our business to ensure we are available for our families when needed. The business pays for our IfA membership
- We fund membership of relevant professional organisations including the IfA and Institute of Archaeologists of Ireland. We fund all relevant CPD such as attendance at conference and training courses required by the business.
- Wet weather clothing allowance given to all staff. Mileage paid when staff use their own cars & take other staff to excavation sites
- Wide ranging benefits package

Comments on rights and benefits

General comments on benefits and to the specific questions fall into two rough categories. The first category was comments from those who responded about their particular work situation and why they found it hard to answer questions about benefits:

- am sole trader so most of this is not applicable
- As a sole trader I am responsible for my own welfare and wellbeing, when I work as an employee I am only too aware of how companies avoid their responsibilities to staff especially regarding paid travel and other overtime

- At the moment none of the above applies as there is only me as Director!
- Being self-employed we are in a completely different world and the questionnaire is hard to fill in meaningfully. We can't even reflect that in the choice of type of organisation
- I am a self-employed single-trader
- I am self-employed; my business is not formally constituted.
- If we had the money we would offer more benefits
- I'm sole trader, I employ archaeologists and specialists on specific projects only and as other self employed people
- our organisation is a coop of self-employed people, it is hard to quantify employee rights in this context
- self employed so no formal benefits
- self-employed
- We are self employed in a registered partnership

The second category consisted of specific details on some benefits offered or concerns about the future of benefits:

- The profession falls woefully short of providing acceptable employment standards for the level of education and experience that it requires from its staff. The problem is endemic and shows no sign of abating at the current time.
- Under threat/erosion, in common with most LAs
- Very progressive employee rights
- We are very concerned that without an IFA minimum for field staff salaries will tumble across the board. Payed accommodation and subsistence, if working away from contracted place of work, should, in all cases be fully paid - commercial competition is no excuse
- As a local Authority the paid holiday starts at c 22days per year plus 3 statutory days and rises after 5 years employment
- Currently the County Council are trying to take away occupational sick pay for the first three days, force us to take unpaid leave and drop out of national pay bargaining
- no employers sick pay for 1st 2 days of absence
- prices for work have fallen - caused by an influx of workers from Europe -so wages will fall.
- Sick pay entitlement is lower than it used to be. Now 3 days unpaid, then 90% salary. Used to be 100% salary for 6 months.

One respondent mentioned an influx of workers from Europe but the responses to country of origin for the workforce in Chapter Four did not show any significant increase of European archaeologists working for the respondents.

Pensions

From October 2012, employers began to be obliged to automatically enrol workers into pension schemes and to make contributions (DWP 2012). On the survey date for this research (14th December 2012), only organisations with over 30,000 individuals on their payroll were obliged to do this. None of the respondents to this survey reported that their workforces were of such a size.

Pension data was gathered from the post profiles, which covers fewer archaeologists than the organisation response dataset. The results are summarised in Table 101.

organisations contributing to pensions	number of staff	
yes	663	82%
no	122.4	15%
don't know	26	3%
total	811.4	

Table 110: Employer pension contributions.

Private companies and charities were the least likely to offer a pension contribution, while universities and local planning authorities tended to be more likely to contribute to employees' pensions.

organisational base	yes		No		don't know		total
private limited company (ltd)	90	69%	40	31%	0	0	130
public limited company (plc)	0	0%	0		0	0%	0
registered charity	21	48%	18	41%	5	11%	44
constituent part of a local planning authority	146.2	87%	20.4	12%	2	1%	168.6
constituent part of a university	164.8	89%	2	1%	18	10%	184.8
other	143	84%	27	16%	1	1%	171

Table 111: Employer pension contributions by organisational bases.

Whether organisations contributed to employee’s pensions varied by the seniority of the posts concerned, with those in senior posts more likely to be in receipt of employer contributions than those in junior posts.

seniority of posts and pension contributions	yes		no		don’t know		total
	count	percentage	count	percentage	count	percentage	
senior staff	195.5	77%	33	13%	25	10%	253.5
medium ranking	112.5	70%	49	30%	0	0%	161.5
junior staff	49.6	61%	30.4	38%	1	1%	81

Table 112: Level of seniority of posts and pension contributions.

The reported frequency of employer pension contributions was higher in 2012-13 than in the predecessor surveys (Table 113). While this represents an improvement in working conditions, it is also possible that may be a consequence of more junior posts – which were less likely to benefit from employer pension contributions - being lost in the five years prior to the survey.

pension contributions	1997-98	2002-03	2007-08	2012-13
employees receiving employer pension contributions	71%	74%	69%	82%

Table 113: Pension contributions, 1997-98 to 2012-13.

Job security

Respondents were asked about both the length of contracts that individual employees held and about how long they had worked for that organisation (not necessarily in the same post).

Length of contract

Over time, contracts that archaeologists are employed under have typically lengthened. In 2012-13, 82% of archaeologists were employed on permanent or open-ended contracts, and therefore only 18% of individual archaeologists were on short-term, fixed contracts.

length of contract	1997-98		2002-03		2007-08		2012-2013	
up to 3 months	234	11%	182	9%	119	5%	30	4%
3 - 6 months	139	7%	68	3%	113	4%	12.2	1%
6 - 12 months	195	9%	176	9%	213	8%	37.5	5%
12 - 24 months	49	2%	79	4%	89	3%	22	3%
more than 24 months	90	4%	74	4%	87	3%	48	6%
permanent / open-ended	1,394	66%	1,450	71%	1,859	73%	676.1	82%
other					69	3%		
total	2101		2029		2549		825.8	

Table 114: Length of contract, 1997-98 to 2012-13.

The overwhelming majority of posts were described as being permanent or open-ended contracts. The survey did not allow distinctions to be made between the two, and it is recognised that these may represent different cohorts of the working population; permanent staff may be working year round while those on open-ended contracts may only work on an *ad hoc* basis for a shorter period.

Extremely short-term (under three months) temporary contracts were most commonly reported in the field investigation and research area of work (Table 115). The movement of workers from one temporary position to another has been well-known as the “digger’s circuit” of junior fieldwork posts.

working role	< 3 months		3 - 6 months		6 - 12 months		12 - 24 months		> 24 months		open ended permnt.	total	
field investigation and research	27	7%	3	1%	22	6%	11	3%	14	4%	298	79%	375
provision of historic environment advice and information	2	1%	4	1%	10	3%	5	2%	29	10%	237	83%	288
museum and visitor / user services	0	0%	1	7%	0	0%	0	0%	3	20%	11	73%	15
educational and academic research	1	1%	4	4%	6	5%	4	4%	2	2%	88	84%	105
administrative support	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	1	3%	0	0%	37	97%	39

Table 115: Length of contract by working role.

Over time, the percentage of posts in museum and visitor / user services that have been permanent positions has decreased, while increased percentages of posts in field investigation and research and in educational and academic research have become

permanent positions. This may represent organisational responses to the changed economic situation since 2007-08.

proportion of permanent contracts by working role	2002-03		2007-08		2012-2013	
	Count	Percentage	Count	Percentage	Count	Percentage
field investigation and research services	862	66%	1,186	68%	298	79%
historic environment advice and information services	266	83%	387	90%	237.3	83%
museum and visitor / user services	77	92%	95	80%	11	73%
educational and academic research services	95	68%	140	71%	88	84%

Table 116: Proportion of permanent contracts by working role, 2002-03 to 2012-13.

Figure 28: Proportion of permanent contracts by working role, 2002-03 to 2012-13.

Length of employment to date

Respondents were asked how long the employees had worked for their organisation, either in paid employment or as volunteers.

length of employment to date	paid		volunteer	
up to 3 months	39	5%	4	11%
3 - 6 months	33	4%	9	24%
6 - 12 months	56	7%	0	0%
12 - 24 months	63	7%	3	8%
2 - 5 years	144	17%	16	40%
5 - 10 years	203	24%	4	9%
10 - 20 years	191	23%	2	5%
more than 20 years	106	13%	1	3%
	835		39	

Table 117: Length of employment to date.

16% of archaeologists had been in post for a year or less at the time of the survey, indicating the level of 'churn' in the workforce is consistent with that suggested by the responses to the question about staff turnover (Table 26).

As with length of contracts there is some variation by working roles. However, given the small sample size and the range of possible responses the opportunities to discern patterns are limited (Table 118).

length of employ by role	< 3 months		3 - 6 months		6 - 12 months		12 - 24 months		2 - 5 years		5 - 10 years		10 - 20 years		> 20 years	
field research	28	7%	22	6%	23	6%	33	9%	70	19%	81	22%	84	22%	34	9%
historic environment advice	5	2%	7	2%	17	6%	20	7%	50	17%	87	30%	63	22%	37	13%
museum services	2	13%	0	0%	0	0%	2	13%	3	20%	4	27%	2	13%	2	13%
educational research	4	4%	3	3%	9	9%	3	3%	13	13%	18	17%	28	27%	27	26%
admin support	0	0%	0	0%	6	15%	4	10%	6	15%	73	19%	11	27%	5	13%

Table 118: Length of employment to date by working role.

There was very little difference between organisation type and the typical length of employment to date (Table 119).

length of employment	private limited company		public limited company	registered charity		constituent part of a local planning authority		constituent part of a university		other	
	count	percentage		count	percentage	count	percentage	count	percentage	count	percentage
< 3 m	4	3%	0	1	2%	4	2%	25	14%	4	2%
3 - 6 m	8	6%		5	8%	14	8%	9	5%	5	3%
6 - 12 m	14	10%		1	2%	5	3%	15	8%	8	4%
12 - 24 m	12	9%		5	8%	8	4%	18	10%	11	6%
2 - 5 y	31	23%		24	40%	19	10%	30	16%	37	20%
5 - 10 y	35	26%		11	18%	37	20%	29	16%	54	30%
10 - 20 y	27	20%		9	15%	52	28%	37	20%	46	25%
> 20 y	5	4%		4	7%	45	25%	21	11%	17	9%
total	136			60		183		184		182	

Table 119: Length of employment to date by organisation type, all staff.

Due to changes in how data were collected it is not possible to see detailed long term trends in the length of employment for archaeologists. Prior to the 2007-08 survey respondents were only given a single category of >24months which covered the majority of responses. Over time, the surveys have always found that most people have been employed by the same organisation for over two years; in 2012-13, 36% of individuals had been working for the same organisation for ten years or more (Table 120).

length of employment	1997-98		2002-03		2007-08		2012-13	
up to 3 months	206	10%	231	10%	149	6%	39	5%
3 - 6 months	105	5%	145	7%	179	7%	33	4%
6 - 12 months	111	6%	232	10%	226	9%	55.2	7%
12 - 24 months	183	9%	212	10%	356	15%	62	8%
>24 months	1,407	70%	1,401	63%				
2 - 5 years					609	25%	144	17%
5 - 10 years					380	16%	202	24%
10 - 20 years					361	15%	191	23%
more than 20 years					170	7%	106	13%
total	2,012		2,221		2,430		832	

Table 120: Length of employment to date, 1997-98 to 2012-13.

Full-time and part-time work

Historically, the definition of part-time work in UK law was based on the number of hours worked but this is no longer the case. 'Part-time workers are (generally) defined as those whose hours of work are less than the normal hours of work of a comparable full time worker' (Lourie 2000). Since 2000 part-time workers in the UK must not be treated less favourably than their full-time colleagues, as established by the *Part-time Workers (Prevention of Less Favourable Treatment) Regulations 2000*. Further amendments to these regulations in 2002 entitled part-time workers to the same hourly rates of pay, the same access to company pension schemes, the same entitlements to annual leave and maternity/parental leave on a pro rata basis, the same entitlement to contractual sick pay and no less favourable treatment in access to training (BERR 2008).

In common with past *Profiling the Profession* surveys a question was asked about full-time or part-time workers. To ensure consistency, the definition employed by National Statistics until 2003 continued to be used, whereby full-time was considered to be 30 hours or more per week, and part time less than 30 hours per week (National Statistics 2003, appendix 1).

paid staff			volunteers		
full time (>=30h per week)	part time (<30 hours per week)	total	full time (>=30h per week)	part time (<30 hours per week)	total
691	145.6	836.6	2	34.2	36.2
83%	17%		6%	94%	

Table 121: Full-time and part-time work, all staff.

The overwhelming majority of archaeologists worked in a full time capacity. This was seen across all roles, except in administrative support where there was a much higher rate of part-time workers.

role	full time (>=30h per week)		part time (<30 hours per week)		total
field investigation and research	321	85%	55	15%	376
provision of historic environment advice and information	226	78%	63	22%	289
museum and visitor / user services	14	93%	1	7%	15
educational and academic research	95	90%	11	10%	106
administrative support	24	61%	16	39%	50

Table 122: Full-time and part-time work by role.

Employer organisational bases do not have a significant bearing on full time or part time work.

organisation basis	full time (>=30h per week)		part time (<30 hours per week)		total
	count	percentage	count	percentage	
private limited company (ltd)	132	74%	47	26%	179
public limited company (plc)	174	95%	10	5%	183.5
registered charity	139	81%	32	19%	171.1
constituent part of a local planning authority	38	86%	6	14%	44
constituent part of a university	0		0		0
other	118	87%	18	13%	136

Table 123: Full-time and part-time work by organisation basis.

Women are slightly more likely to work part-time in archaeology than men are.

gender	paid		Volunteer		paid		volunteer		total
	count	percentage	count	percentage	count	percentage	count	percentage	
	full time (>=30h per week)				part time (<30 hours per week)				
female	356	89%	0	0%	43	11%	2	0%	401
male	439	94%	1	0%	24	5%	2	0%	466

Table 124: Full-time and part-time work by gender.

Sources of funding

Respondents were asked whether posts were funded from establishment income or from project grants and/or contracting income. Table 125 summarises the responses for all posts and Table 126 summarises by post role.

establishment income		project or contract income		total
count	percentage	count	percentage	
349	46%	409	54%	758

Table 125: Post funding.

There are significant differences in how positions are funded in the different sub-sectors of archaeology. Field investigation and research positions are mainly funded through projects and contracts while posts in every other subsector are normally funded through establishment income.

post role	establishment income		project or contract income		total
field investigation and research	52	15%	283	85%	334
provision of historic environment advice and information	169	64%	95	36%	264
museum and visitor / user services	9	60%	6	40%	15
educational and academic research	87	85%	15	15%	102
administrative support	29	76%	9	24%	38

Table 126: Post funding, by job role.

Differing sources of primary funding for posts can also be seen by organisation types as well. Private companies and charities obtain most of their funding from projects and contracts.

organisation basis	establishment income		project or contract income		total
private limited company (ltd)	34	29%	82	71%	116
public limited company (plc)	0		0		0
registered charity	12	27%	32	73%	44
constituent part of a local planning authority	96	63%	56	37%	152
constituent part of a university	86	52%	79	48%	165
other	92	58%	67	42%	159

Table 127: Post funding, by organisation basis.

Over the period since 2002-03 the typical funding sources for most job roles had not changed significantly. Field investigation and research posts have stayed very close to the 85 to 15 ratio of project to established income.

post role	2002-03		2007-08		2012-2013	
	establish. income	project or contract income	establish. income	project or contract income	establish. income	project or contract income
field investigation and research services	17%	83%	15%	85%	15%	85%
historic environment advice and information services	68%	32%	64%	36%	64%	36%
museum and visitor / user services	91%	9%	81%	19%	60%	40%
educational and academic research services	70%	30%	58%	42%	85%	15%
archaeological management			82%	18%		
administrative support	32%	48%	74%	26%	76%	24%
Total	36%	66%	33%	67%	46%	54%

Table 128: Post funding, by job role, 2002-03 to 2012-13.

Vacancies

In a working environment where many archaeological jobs had been lost in the previous five years, very few organisations or sectors were having difficulty filling positions. Only a few positions were reported as being difficult to fill.

vacancies difficult to fill and job role	yes		no		don't know		total
	count	percentage	count	percentage	count	percentage	
field investigation and research	2	1%	133	99%	0	0%	135
provision of historic environment advice and information	3	2%	156	96%	3	2%	162
museum and visitor / user services	0	0%	11	100%	0	0%	11
educational and academic research	1	4%	26	96%	0	0%	27
administrative support	0	0%	23	100%	0	0%	23
total	6		349				

Table 129: Difficult to fill vacancies by post role.

No single type of organisation appeared to be having difficulties filling positions.

organisation basis	yes		no		don't know		total
	count	percentage	count	percentage	count	percentage	
private limited company (ltd)	2	3%	57	97%	0	0%	59
public limited company (plc)	0		0		0		0
registered charity	0	0%	24	100%	0	0%	24
constituent part of a local planning authority	3	3%	103	97%	0	0%	106
constituent part of a university	1	3%	29	97%	0	0%	30
other	0	0%	86	100%	0	0%	86
total	6		349		0		

Table 130: Difficult to fill vacancies by organisational basis.

The low number of “difficult to fill” vacancies in 2012-13 represents a clear reduction from previous survey results.

	2002-03	2007-08	2012-13
number of vacancies difficult to fill	38	59	6

Table 131: Number of difficult to fill vacancies, 2002-03 to 2012-13.

Trade Unions

Trade unions were recognised in 63% of workplaces where a total of 83% of archaeologists worked. Union recognition was universal in national government agency workplaces as well as at those organisations within local government and universities that employ archaeologists.

union representation in the workplace	organisations		archaeologists employed	
yes	117	63%	1,801	83%
no	59	32%	358	16%
don't know	9	5%	18	1%
total	185	100%	2,177	100%

Table 132: Trade Union recognition.

trade unions recognised	organisations		archaeologists employed	
Prospect	19	11%	1,117	42%
Unison	86	51%	373	14%
UCU (University and College Union)	25	15%	692	26%
Unite	19	11%	246	9%
Other	19	11%	233	9%
Total	168	100%	2,663	100%

Table 133: Trade Unions recognised by archaeological employers.

Unions reported under the 'other' category:

- GMB (10)
- EIS (Educational Institute for Scotland)
- Local authority recognises employees' right to belong to a union of choice
- Not applicable as I am the only employee at present
- PCS
- PCS and FDA
- T&GW
- Teaching unions - NASUWT, NUT, etc.(Local Authority)
- TGWU. Also Teachers' Unions.
- The staff have never asked us to recognise any of the above

There have been significant levels of union recognition since 1997-98 and this has steadily increased over time (Table 134).

archaeologists working for organisations which recognise one or more trade union	1997-98	2002-03	2007-08	2012-13
Trade Union recognised	72%	71%	78%	83%

Table 134: Archaeologists working for organisations which recognise trade unions, 1997-98 to 2012-13.

Figure 29: Archaeologists working for organisations which recognise trade unions, 1997-98 to 2012-13.

Chapter 6: Training

Introduction

Training has long been an area of considerable concern for the archaeological profession, and skills needs and training investment has been tracked in the *Profiling the Profession* surveys. Unlike most other professions, there is no overall skills mix that is 'typical' for an individual archaeologist (Carter & Robertson 2002a). Archaeologists working in different parts of the sector have very different roles and sometimes they do not even perform any common activities (ATF 2003). Historically, a number of factors have been considered to have worked against the successful provision of training in archaeology (Bishop, Collis and Hinton 1999; Aitchison 2002), and these continue to structure ongoing discussion:

- an underdeveloped professional career structure
- a lack of formal or in some cases informal training
- inadequate documentation of the skills required to practice in a given role
- insufficient value being placed on training
- insufficient resources given to training

Training demand

Over the full period that the *Profiling the Profession* projects have been reporting there has been a debate about the objectives of training in archaeology and its outcomes; Chitty (1999) found that vocational training for archaeologists was unregulated, diverse and unrelated to the core competencies needed for archaeological work. Since that date, considerable effort has been made in developing vocational training structures, but the principal mechanism by which archaeological practitioners receive their initial training remains through the academic matrix of university degrees.

The established paradigm is that employers complain that graduates are insufficiently skilled while universities protest that it is not their job to focus on applied practice (Aitchison, 2004). Archaeological employers outside academia believe that undergraduate and postgraduate degree courses fall short of preparing graduates to work in archaeology. Moreover, they believe that students not only lack practical field experience and technical expertise, but also the conceptual, analytical and interpretative skills required to work as an archaeologists. Lecturers in archaeology, by contrast, generally believe that the curriculum should deliver knowledge about the past and how it has and should be interpreted, not specific field experience or technical expertise. This needs to be done within a sound theoretical and methodological framework, though grounded in practical experience where possible. Even if only a small proportion of archaeology students will pursue a career in archaeology they still expect their degree to enhance their generic employment prospects, a view not shared by all archaeology lecturers (after Aitchison and Giles 2006, 2).

In the early 1970s, oversupply was not yet a problem, with RESCUE and the CBA calling for "... universities to increase their output of graduate and postgraduate archaeologists" (RESCUE & CBA, 1974: 17). That document also considered that the establishment of a professional institution would "enable those working in non-professional capacities in excavation teams and units to acquire professional qualifications through on-the-job training combined with study through extra-mural departments and other further education organisms" (*ibid.*, 17-18), and hoped that the Open University would introduce archaeological courses as soon as possible (*ibid.*, 18) – suggesting that the authors still could not envisage a non-university trained profession.

The rapid expansion of professional archaeology since the start of the 1980s then led to a widespread training deficit, as it occurred without due consideration for the vocational development of the practitioners involved (Bishop *et al.*, 1999). One of the mechanisms that has been utilised to attempt to develop a skilled archaeological workforce has been vocational qualifications. An attempt to develop these was made in the early 1990s, with the *NVQ and SVQ in Environmental Conservation (Archaeology and Field Archaeology)* (COSQUEC, 1994).

However, that qualification failed to gain currency as neither employers nor aspirant practitioners recognised it as bringing them benefits, and it fell into abeyance. Following Chitty's (1999) recommendations, the Archaeology Training Forum encouraged the development of National Occupational Standards (NOS) for Archaeological Practice, benchmarks of competence demonstrable in the workplace. These Standards can be used in multiple contexts (Carter and Robertson, 2002b), particularly as performance criteria for a vocational qualification (NVQ) in Archaeological Practice (Carter and Robertson, 2002a).

The Archaeology Training Forum's *Vision for Training and Career Development in Archaeology* recognised that "... the introduction of the NVQ will not be an immediate panacea" (Aitchison, 2008: 30), but it was hoped that it would become a tool to assert archaeologists' professional competence.

Frameworks for training

National Occupational Standards

National Occupational Standards (NOS) in Archaeological Practice are benchmarks of performance. They set out what skilled practitioners need to be able to do in order to demonstrate their competence in particular archaeological tasks, primarily in the workplace. These skills encompass both technical, archaeological skills and the other workplace skills that an archaeologists would need in their work. They were prepared in 2002 (Carter & Robertson 2002a) and formally accepted by QCA (Qualifications and Curriculum Authority), SQA (Scottish Qualifications Authority) and ACCAC (now part of Welsh Assembly Government Department of Education and Skills) in 2003. They were restructured (although their content was not changed) by Creative and Cultural Skills in 2006, creating a common architecture for NOS in Archaeological Practice and Cultural Heritage.

National Vocational Qualifications

National Vocational Qualifications (NVQs) are vocational qualifications developed from the National Occupational Standards. The NVQ in Archaeological Practice was launched in April 2007, is awarded by Education Development International (EDI), part of the Pearson Group and is accredited at Level 3 of the QCF (Qualifications and Credit Framework). The formal title for this qualification is the *EDI Level 3 NVQ Certificate in Archaeological Practice*; its current accreditation period ends on 31 December 2013 (EDI 2012), and standalone adult funding from the Skills Funding Agency will continue until 31 July 2014 (Edexcel 2013).

In 2012-13, only two assessment centres (the Institute for Archaeologists and the V&A Training Development Department) were offering this qualification to candidates. As of June 2013, a total of only 35 individuals had been awarded the qualification (Kate Geary, pers. comm. 11th June 2013 and Pat McCann, pers. comm. 19th June 2013). Nearly 100 further candidates were registered with the Institute for Archaeologists assessment centre and so were working towards the qualification.

QAA Benchmark Statement

The Quality Assurance Agency for Higher Education (QAA) establishes benchmarks that set out expectations and standards of degrees in a variety of subject areas.

The *Benchmark Statement for Archaeology* (QAA 2007) sets out that the content of undergraduate degree courses varies considerably between programmes and ‘Particular degree programmes will be located at different points within a triangle drawn between the complementary archaeologies of the humanities, sciences and professional practice’ (*ibid.*, 2.18). Taught postgraduate courses (Masters level) will offer more focused instruction about particular aspects of life in the past or of archaeological practice. In some cases these courses can deliver much more detailed technical skills. There is currently no Benchmark Statement for Masters courses in Archaeology.

The employability of graduates is increasingly important to higher education institutions. The Benchmark Statement for Archaeology sets out that:

“The broad-based nature of the subject and of the skills it gives graduates provide a strong grounding for a wide range of career paths: the archaeology graduate is extremely well equipped with transferable skills from the mix of humanities and science training, engagement with theory and practice, and individual and team-based learning, together with the intellectual curiosity to continue learning, and the skills to benefit from challenging work environments” (*ibid.*, 1.9).

Continuing Professional Development

Many archaeologists seek training opportunities in order to further their career opportunities. A common way to structure this training is through Continuing Professional Development (CPD), the process by which individual professionals develop and maintain their skills throughout their working lives. Corporate members of the IfA are required to undertake 50 hours of relevant professional development over a rolling two-year period (IfA 2009a).

Training delivery

Universities

Currently, the principal vehicles for the delivery of teaching and training for archaeologists are higher education institutions. Undergraduate degrees typically deliver academic knowledge about human life in the past together with a range of generic, transferable skills related to research and independent working. This training includes a limited range of archaeologically specific technical skills.

University archaeology and continuing education departments also deliver a small number of short (one-day, two-day or week-long) technical, skills-based courses. These off-job learning experiences are often marketed towards practitioners. Continuing education departments at some universities also offer a number of weekly (evening) courses that are almost universally focussed on academic knowledge rather than skills; the number of such courses being taught declined from 39 universities offering a total of 1,327 courses in 1999-00 to 28 universities offering 515 courses in 2008-09 (Lee 2009).

Non-university training courses

A small number of non-academic based archaeological organisations have diversified their work to include offering weekend workshops and training courses. Larger organisations, such as English Heritage also offer training courses on a range of subjects of varying length but usually not more than a week long. Community archaeology organisations such as the CBA and Archaeology Scotland also run their own training courses. Many learned societies, specialist associations and professional associations, most notably the IfA, run annual conferences involving training workshops for their members.

Workplace learning and apprenticeships

In archaeology, there are currently two principal approaches by which learning is delivered in the workplace:

- Mentoring - a system whereby a more experienced employee works with a new or less experienced colleague, sharing their knowledge or expertise and offering support. Stephenson (2004) sets out a structured framework for implementing coach-mentoring in a fieldwork context
- Workplace Learning - where a learner is placed in the workplace and they then have a structured experience of learning skills on-the-job. Such a system can, and has, been described as an apprenticeship – it is important to note that “Apprenticeship” is now a technically defined phrase (“Modern Apprenticeship” in Scotland) and can only be used to describe a workplace learning experience that is structured under a formal Apprenticeship Framework and which leads to vocational qualifications (Alliance of SSCs nd). In May 2013 there were no Apprenticeship Frameworks that incorporated archaeologically-specific qualifications.

A system of ‘apprenticeships’ has been identified as the preferred method for archaeological specialists to pass on their skills (Aitchison 2000). This is especially true of specialists who are often working alone or with minimal support, and so find it difficult to invest in the training of other staff. Supported apprenticeships may be the best means for this expertise to be passed on to new specialists.

Since 2006, the Heritage Lottery Fund (HLF) has supported work placement programmes in archaeology, funded by their *Workplace Learning Bursaries* and *Skills for the Future* initiatives, which have been delivered by both the Institute for Archaeologists and the Council for British Archaeology. In these programmes the salary of the participating archaeologist, who is at an early stage in their career, is funded in return for a host organisation providing a structured learning work-placement of six months to one year. In some cases, the host organisation also makes a partial contribution towards salary costs. While these cannot technically be called apprenticeships, they are effectively a model whereby the bursary holder is in all effect working as an apprentice. This has been mirrored by English Heritage providing comparable internal placement schemes (EPPIC and HET).

Employers’ commitment to qualifications and training

Organisational attitudes towards training

Survey respondents were asked a range of questions relating to their attitudes towards training. The results are shown in Table 135.

Typically, archaeological organisations identify training needs for individual members of staff and for the organisation as a whole, they provide training opportunities for paid members of staff and they encourage individuals to engage in continuing professional development. They are likely to have a training budget, but they do not normally have a formal training plan. While they will normally record the amount of time employees spend on training activities, they then typically do not evaluate the impact of that training on either the individual or the on the organisation as a whole.

	yes		no		don't know		total
does your organisation identify training needs for individuals?	166	91%	16	9%	0	0%	182
do you (as an organisation) identify training needs for the organisation as a whole?	134	75%	40	22%	5	3%	179
do you provide training or other development opportunities for paid staff?	162	90%	19	10%	0	0%	181
do you provide training or other development opportunities for unpaid volunteers?	93	55%	68	40%	8	5%	169
does your organisation have a formal training plan?	81	46%	86	48%	11	6%	178
does your organisation have a training budget?	109	61%	65	36%	5	3%	179
is your training budget under your organisation's direct control?	100	61%	58	35%	7	4%	165
do you record how much time employees spend being trained?	119	67%	46	26%	13	7%	178
do you formally evaluate the impact of training on individuals?	80	45%	84	48%	12	7%	176
do you formally evaluate the impact of training on the organisation?	45	26%	106	61%	22	13%	173
does your organisation operate a performance appraisal scheme?	112	64%	62	36%	0	0%	174
does your organisation encourage individuals to engage in their continuing professional development (CPD)?	150	86%	22	13%	3	2%	175

Table 135: Organisations' attitudes towards training.

In comparison with workplaces across the whole UK economy, archaeological employers are very well placed in terms of commitment to training. 38% of employers in all sectors have a training plan, and only 29% have a training budget (UKCES 2012, 107).

Preferred methods of training

When asked about the types of training that organisations preferred for their paid staff, all approaches were clearly valued, with a slight overall preference for formal, off-the-job training.

preferred methods of training for paid staff	organisations		archaeologists employed
formal off-job training (eg outside training course)	143	90%	1,952
formal in-job training (eg in-house training course)	132	83%	2,017
informal off-job training (eg supported individual research and learning)	130	82%	1,774
informal in-job training (eg mentoring)	130	82%	1,890
total responses	159		

Table 136: Preferred methods of training for paid staff.

The range of responses for training methods preferred for unpaid staff was much more limited. In-house training was preferred to external training, with very few respondents indicating that they preferred formal off-job training, perhaps reflecting a perceived cost in doing this that organisations are not prepared to incur in order to train volunteers (Table 137).

preferred methods of training for unpaid staff	organisations	
formal off-job training (eg outside training course)	9	13%
formal in-job training (eg in-house training course)	41	59%
informal off-job training (eg supported individual research and learning)	34	49%
informal in-job training (eg mentoring)	54	78%
total responses	69	

Table 137: Preferred methods of training for unpaid staff.

Support for Vocational Qualification

Respondents were asked if they have previously supported a member of staff, or would consider supporting a member of staff to obtain a vocational qualification in archaeological practice (NVQ). 30 respondents reported having previously supported a member of staff to obtain a NVQ. Nearly half of the respondents, employing 1,350 archaeologists, would be prepared to consider supporting a member of their staff to obtain an NVQ in the future. There was no correlation between organisation role or constitution and responses to the question about future support. However, as with most questions about training the size of an organisation made a difference. The median size of the organisations that would support staff in the future was five employees, compared with a median size of two for those that would not support a staff member in doing this.

have you or would you consider supporting a member of staff to gain a vocational qualification in archaeological practice (NVQ)?				
have previously supported a member of staff	organisations		archaeologists employed	
yes	30	21%	853.9	44%
no	100	68%	930.05	48%
don't know	16	11%	144.75	8%
total	146		1,928.7	
would support a member of staff in the future	organisations		archaeologists employed	
yes	83	49%	1,348.85	66%
no	44	26%	541.3	26%
don't know	41	24%	157.55	8%
total	168		2,047.7	

Table 138: Organisational support for NVQ in Archaeological Practice.

Skills gaps and shortages

For clarification of terms used in this report, the terms skills 'gaps' and 'shortages' are not interchangeable but represent different problems. "skills gaps are skills that existing staff need but lack, as opposed to skills shortages, which mean that employers cannot find job applicants with the right skills" (CCSkills 2010).

A skills 'gap' occurs in an area where existing workforce members have lower skill levels than are necessary to meet the business' or the industry's objectives, or where new entrants lack some of the skills they need; skills gaps mean that the sector is underskilled, so these identify training priorities. A skills 'shortage' is where there aren't enough suitably skilled individuals in the workplace; rather than an under-provision of skills, this is where there is an absence of skills, and this can often only be addressed by bringing in external specialists (after Creative Skillset 2001).

On this basis a skills gap will usually affect an individual organisation but a skills shortage may affect a whole sector.

Skills gaps and shortages were identified in both technical, archaeological skills and in generic, professional skills. The severity of these gaps and shortages was categorised as significant, where more than 25% of respondents to the question had identified a problem or serious, where more than 50% of respondents to the question had identified a problem.

skills area	skills gap	skills shortage
post-fieldwork analysis	significant skills gap	serious skills shortage
fieldwork (invasive or non-invasive)	significant skills gap	significant skills shortage
information technology	significant skills gap	significant skills shortage
people management	significant skills gap	
project management	significant skills gap	
artefact or ecofact conservation		significant skills shortage

Table 139: Identified skills gaps and shortages.

These areas of skills gaps and shortages are discussed in further detail below.

Some changes to the way data on skills issues have been collected have been made since 2007-08, following developments of data collection in the *State of the Archaeological Market* series of surveys.

In 2007-08 and 2002-03, questions about fieldwork skills were much more detailed – they asked separately about conducting and contributing to fieldwork projects, and separated intrusive and non-intrusive fieldwork, then even further separating non-intrusive fieldwork into geophysical survey and other non-intrusive fieldwork. The varied answers received explain why ranges are given for the historical data on fieldwork skills gaps and shortages in Table 140 and Table 141. Furthermore, data were separately obtained historically on “other” archaeological skills and “other” generic professional skills; this was combined in 2012-13.

Information under the specific categories of “post-fieldwork analysis”, “providing advice to clients” and “data management” was not gathered in 2002-03 or 2007-08.

skills gaps	2002-03	2007-08	2012-13
fieldwork (invasive or non-invasive)	9-25%	10-19%	25%
post-fieldwork analysis			25%
artefact or ecofact conservation	15%	17%	12%
providing advice to clients			14%
desk-based or environmental assessment	40%	36%	17%
data management			22%
leadership	16%	28%	14%
business skills	21%	30%	21%
project management	54%	48%	27%
education / training	24%	36%	24%
information technology	74%	68%	35%
people management	25%	40%	25%
other	5%-24%	18-19%	12%

Table 140: Skills gaps, 2002-03 to 2012-13.

Over time, in terms of technical, archaeologically specific skills, the level of fieldwork skills gaps have remained relatively consistent; the levels of gaps in artefact or ecofact conservation and desk-based or environmental assessment have come down.

There has also been a downward trend in the level of skills gaps across generic, professional skills, although it is noteworthy that there was a peak in the levels of skills gaps reported in 2007-08 for leadership, business skills, education / training and people management, possibly representing skills that were in particularly acute demand at the height of the pre-recessionary boom period.

In terms of skills shortages over time, the same caveats relating to the changes in the way data have been collected apply.

skills shortages	2002-03	2007-08	2012-13
fieldwork (invasive or non-invasive)	18%-52%	8%-42%	41%
post-fieldwork analysis			51%
artefact or ecofact conservation	48%	38%	43%
providing advice to clients			2%
desk-based or environmental assessment	39%	31%	10%
data management			9%
Leadership	13%	5%	1%
business skills	14%	14%	5%
project management	23%	10%	3%
education / training	33%	21%	11%
information technology	67%	53%	25%
people management	23%	10%	5%
other	15%-22%	16%-18%	12%

Table 141: Skills shortages, 2002-03 to 2012-13.

Fieldwork and artefact or ecofact conservation skills have consistently been frequently bought in over time. Desk-based or environmental assessment skills were much less frequently provided by external consultants in 2012-13 than previously.

In terms of generic, professional skills, over time less and less organisations have bought in such skills. This is the case in all of the areas examined - leadership, business, project management, education / training, information technology and people management skills.

Skills lost

The loss of skills from an organisation does not automatically identify a particular skills gap or shortage; this may also be the recognition of a skills area becoming redundant if an organisation no longer needs it.

in the last twelve months (during the course of 2012) has your organisation lost skills in any of these areas?	organisations		archaeologists employed
fieldwork (invasive or non-invasive)	13	33%	542
post-fieldwork analysis	10	25%	240
artefact or ecofact conservation	7	18%	100
providing advice to clients	11	28%	144.5
desk-based or environmental assessment	6	15%	160
data management	10	25%	75.5
leadership	12	30%	180
business skills	5	13%	71
project management	6	15%	85
education / training	7	18%	106
information technology	7	18%	90.5
people management	7	18%	71
other	3	8%	21
responses	40		

Table 142: Skills lost.

Only 40 respondents completed this question. No single category was identified as an area where skills had been lost by a majority of respondents, with fieldwork the most frequently recognised area where a third of respondents identified that they had lost skills. Other categories listed and general comments made (reproduced *verbatim*) were:

- High level management
- Artefact and ecofact study
- Artefact identification and analysis
- The profession has suffered a considerable loss of skilled individuals in the last few years. My recent experience of most units is that they unfortunately have considerable skills gaps across the board.
- knowledge of the legal and regulatory systems which affect archaeology, and their powers and limitations
- Archiving
- Health & Safety

Skills gaps

Areas where organisations address skills deficits by investing in training their staff are skills gaps.

Significantly more organisations reported having invested in skills (114 organisations) than reported losses (40).

In the last twelve months (during 2012) has your organisation invested in skills training in any of these areas?	organisations		archaeologists employed
fieldwork (invasive or non-invasive)	29	25%	767.5
post-fieldwork analysis	28	25%	727
artefact or ecofact conservation	14	12%	431
providing advice to clients	16	14%	380.5
desk-based or environmental assessment	19	17%	644
data management	25	22%	219.4
leadership	16	14%	333.8
business skills	24	21%	393
project management	31	27%	619.1
education / training	27	24%	362.5
information technology	40	35%	866.1
people management	29	25%	838.3
other	14	12%	218.6
total	114		

Table 143: Skills training investment.

The other reported areas of training investment were:

- Aerial Photographic Analysis
- Community archaeology
- fieldwork safety; health & safety; GIS mapping; filming
- Health & Safety (3)
- historic environment conservation and management; archaeological research
- legal training;
- materials handling
- Public inquiry training
- research (IfA Conference), professional skills, artefacts and ecofacts study
- Various HELM courses attended, Joint statement conference

The areas where more than 25% of respondents identified that there was a skills gap can be considered to be significant gaps; any areas where more than 50% of respondents identified a gap could be considered to be serious gaps.

Serious skills gaps were not identified in any areas of either specialist archaeological skills or transferable professional skills.

In specialist archaeological skills, there were significant skills gaps in

- Fieldwork (invasive or non-invasive)
- Post-fieldwork analysis

In transferable professional skills, there were significant skills gaps in

- Project management
- Information technology
- People management

Skills shortages

Skills that an organisation does not have but that it buys in from external providers are areas of skills shortages. 110 organisations provided information on skills that had been bought in during 2012.

archaeological skills bought in	organisations		archaeologists employed
fieldwork (invasive or non-invasive)	45	41%	506.7
post-fieldwork analysis	56	51%	945.5
artefact or ecofact conservation	47	43%	904.75
providing advice to clients	2	2%	10.2
desk-based or environmental assessment	11	10%	77
data management	10	9%	67.7
leadership	1	1%	17
business skills	6	5%	198
project management	3	3%	283
education / training	12	11%	208.6
information technology	27	25%	790
people management	5	5%	456
other	13	12%	107.8
total	110		

Table 144: Skills bought in.

The additional skills that were bought in were:

- Antiquities conservation
- Ecology, hydrology, bat survey, conservation engineering, landscape architect
- Finance and accounting
- Graphic design

- historical researchers/groundworkers/machine operators
- illustration (2)
- survey
- Site management
- Specialist advice on pottery from outside my area of expertise
- The company currently operates via a network of subcontractors

The areas where more than 25% of respondents identified that there was a skills shortage can be considered to be in significant shortage; the areas where more than 50% of respondents identified a shortage can be considered to be in serious shortage.

In specialist archaeological skills, there was a serious skills shortage in

- Post-fieldwork analysis

In specialist archaeological skills, there were significant skills shortages in

- Fieldwork (invasive or non-invasive)
- Artefact or ecofact conservation

In transferable professional skills, there was a significant skills shortage in

- Information technology

Perceived skills gaps or shortages across the archaeological sector

As well as being asked about issues directly affecting their own organisation, respondents were also asked if they thought that there were any sector-wide skills gaps or shortages. The most frequent responses were in business skills, the broad area of post-fieldwork analysis and in people management.

thinking beyond your organisation, do you think there are skills gaps or shortages across the archaeological sector in any of these areas?		
fieldwork (invasive or non-invasive)	35	28%
post-fieldwork analysis	60	47%
artefact or ecofact conservation	39	31%
providing advice to clients	32	25%
desk-based or environmental assessment	25	20%
data management	35	28%
leadership	39	31%
business skills	62	49%
project management	44	35%
education / training	36	28%
information technology	27	21%
people management	51	40%
other	7	6%
total	127	

Table 145: Perceived skills gaps or shortages across the archaeological sector.

“Other” responses identified that there were skills issues in the following areas:

- archiving
- artefact and ecofact study
- artefact identification and analysis
- health & safety
- high level management
- knowledge of the legal and regulatory systems which affect archaeology, and their powers and limitations

Sectorally, there is a perception that several areas of transferable, professional skills are significantly in deficit – data management, leadership, business skills, education and training – but these are not recognised as being significant or serious skills gaps or shortages by individual employer organisations; these are all areas where the level of reported shortages have reduced over time – so there is a mismatch between what respondents think about the sector as a whole, where they see problems, and what they think about their own organisations, where they do not consider that they have these problems.

This assessment can be interpreted as representing widely-held views that the sector as a whole is underskilled in the transferable professional skills needed to run organisations, but that the sector is not addressing these needs.

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Appendix 1: Post Profiles

All

Individuals	889		Roles		
Volunteers	31		Field investigation and research	382	45%
			Historic environment advice and information	290	34%
Employment			Museum and visitor / user	15	2%
Full-Time	693	80%	Educational and academic research	126	15%
Part-Time	178	20%	Administrative support	40	5%
Salary			Gender		
Minimum	£1,100		Female	396	46%
Average	£27,875		Male	469	54%
Maximum	£125,000				
Length of Service			Age		
up to 3 months	40	5%	16-19	1	0%
3 - 6 months	42	5%	20-29	115	13%
6 - 12 months	56	6%	30-39	276	32%
12 - 24 months	66	8%	40-49	248	29%
2 - 5 years	160	18%	50-59	172	20%
5 - 10 years	207	24%	60 and over	53	6%
10 - 20 years	193	22%			
20 + years	107	12%	Qualifications		
			Post-doctoral	5	1%
Contract Lengths			Doctorate (PhD or DPhil)	174	20%
up to 3 months	30	4%	Postgraduate (Masters)	229	27%
3 - 6 months	13	2%	First degree	392	46%
6 - 12 months	38	5%	Foundation degree or HND	14	2%
12 - 24 months	22	3%	School qualifications	36	4%
More than 24 months	48	6%			
Permanent / open-ended	676	82%	Employer contributes to pension	666	78%
Seniority			Post Funding		
Junior	265	31%	Project or contract income	412	54%
Medium	348	41%	Established income	353	46%
Senior	244	28%			

Academic staff

Individuals	111		Roles		
Volunteers	0		Field investigation and research	20	18%
			Historic environment advice and information	-	-
Employment			Museum and visitor / user	-	-
Full-Time	87	96%	Educational and academic research	91	82%
Part-Time	4	4%	Administrative support	-	-
Salary			Gender		
Minimum	£27,854		Female	39	43%
Average	£40,829		Male	51	57%
Maximum	£125,000				
Length of Service			Age		
up to 3 months	4	4%	16-19	-	-
3 - 6 months	5	6%	20-29	14	16%
6 - 12 months	9	10%	30-39	26	29%
12 - 24 months	8	9%	40-49	25	28%
2 - 5 years	9	10%	50-59	12	13%
5 - 10 years	14	15%	60 and over	13	15%
10 - 20 years	26	29%			
20 + years	15	17%	Qualifications		
			Post-doctoral	1	1%
Contract Lengths			Doctorate (PhD or DPhil)	85	94%
up to 3 months	-	-	Postgraduate (Masters)	5	5%
3 - 6 months	2	2%	First degree	-	-
6 - 12 months	5	5%	Foundation degree or HND	-	-
12 - 24 months	4	4%	School qualifications	-	-
More than 24 months	15	17%			
Permanent / open-ended	65	72%	Employer contributes to pension	91	100%
Seniority			Post Funding		
Junior	38	34%	Project or contract income	20	23%
Medium	41	37%	Established income	68	77%
Senior	32	29%			

Administrator

Individuals	27		Roles		
Volunteers	-		Field investigation and research	-	-
			Historic environment advice and information	-	-
Employment			Museum and visitor / user	-	-
Full-Time	15	57%	Educational and academic research	-	-
Part-Time	12	46%	Administrative support	27	100%
Salary			Gender		
Minimum	£12,000		Female	27	100%
Average	£19,090		Male	-	-
Maximum	£31,754				
Length of Service			Age		
up to 3 months	-	-	16-19	-	-
3 - 6 months	-	-	20-29	5	16%
6 - 12 months	6	23%	30-39	7	27%
12 - 24 months	3	11%	40-49	5	19%
2 - 5 years	5	19%	50-59	6	23%
5 - 10 years	5	16%	60 and over	4	15%
10 - 20 years	6	23%			
20 + years	2	8%	Qualifications		
			Post-doctoral	-	-
Contract Lengths			Doctorate (PhD or DPhil)	-	-
up to 3 months	-	-	Postgraduate (Masters)	2	8%
3 - 6 months	-	-	First degree	8	30%
6 - 12 months	-	-	Foundation degree or HND	3	11%
12 - 24 months	-	-	School qualifications	14	51%
More than 24 months	-	-			
Permanent / open-ended	27	100%	Employer contributes to pension	21	77%
Seniority			Post Funding		
Junior	13	47%	Project or contract income	21	84%
Medium	7	27%	Established income	4	16%
Senior	7	27%			

Archaeological Assistant

Individuals	8		Roles		
Volunteers	2		Field investigation and research	6	75%
			Historic environment advice and information	2	25%
Employment			Museum and visitor / user	-	-
Full-Time	6	75%	Educational and academic research	-	-
Part-Time	2	25%	Administrative support	-	-
Salary			Gender		
Minimum	£17,802		Female	3	38%
Average	£18,545		Male	5	63%
Maximum	£21,519				
Length of Service			Age		
up to 3 months	-	-	16-19	-	-
3 - 6 months	-	-	20-29	-	-
6 - 12 months	-	-	30-39	3	38%
12 - 24 months	1	13%	40-49	4	50%
2 - 5 years	-	-	50-59	1	13%
5 - 10 years	6	75%	60 and over	-	-
10 - 20 years	1	13%			
20 + years			Qualifications		
			Post-doctoral	-	-
Contract Lengths			Doctorate (PhD or DPhil)	-	-
up to 3 months	-	-	Postgraduate (Masters)	1	13%
3 - 6 months	-	-	First degree	5	63%
6 - 12 months	-	-	Foundation degree or HND	-	-
12 - 24 months	-	-	School qualifications	2	25%
More than 24 months	-	-			
Permanent / open-ended	6	100%	Employer contributes to pension	2	25%
Seniority			Post Funding		
Junior	6	75%	Project or contract income	2	33%
Medium	2	25%	Established income	4	67%
Senior					

Archaeological Officer

Individuals	14		Roles		
Volunteers			Field investigation and research	1	7%
			Historic environment advice and information	13	93%
Employment			Museum and visitor / user	-	-
Full-Time	10	71%	Educational and academic research	-	-
Part-Time	4	29%	Administrative support	-	-
Salary			Gender		
Minimum	£20,000		Female	4	29%
Average	£27,324		Male	10	71%
Maximum	£37,000				
Length of Service			Age		
up to 3 months	-	-	16-19	-	-
3 - 6 months	-	-	20-29	-	-
6 - 12 months	1	7%	30-39	2	14%
12 - 24 months	1	7%	40-49	5	36%
2 - 5 years	-	-	50-59	6	43%
5 - 10 years	5	36%	60 and over	1	7%
10 - 20 years	3	21%			
20 + years	4	29%	Qualifications		
			Post-doctoral	-	-
Contract Lengths			Doctorate (PhD or DPhil)	2	14%
up to 3 months	1	7%	Postgraduate (Masters)	3	21%
3 - 6 months	-	-	First degree	7	50%
6 - 12 months	-	-	Foundation degree or HND	-	-
12 - 24 months	1	7%	School qualifications	2	14%
More than 24 months	-	-			
Permanent / open-ended	12	86%	Employer contributes to pension	13	93%
Seniority			Post Funding		
Junior	2	14%	Project or contract income	3	21%
Medium	5	36%	Established income	11	79%
Senior	7	50%			

Archaeological Scientist

Individuals	5		Roles		
Volunteers			Field investigation and research	3	60%
			Historic environment advice and information	1	20%
Employment			Museum and visitor / user	-	-
Full-Time	5	100%	Educational and academic research	1	20%
Part-Time	-	-	Administrative support	-	-
Salary			Gender		
Minimum	£16,315		Female	4	80%
Average	£19,965		Male	1	20%
Maximum	£21,415				
Length of Service			Age		
up to 3 months	-	-	16-19	-	-
3 - 6 months	-	-	20-29	-	-
6 - 12 months	-	-	30-39	1	20%
12 - 24 months	1	20%	40-49	-	-
2 - 5 years	1	20%	50-59	4	80%
5 - 10 years	-	-	60 and over	-	-
10 - 20 years	1	20%			
20 + years	2	40%	Qualifications		
			Post-doctoral	-	-
Contract Lengths			Doctorate (PhD or DPhil)	-	-
up to 3 months	-	-	Postgraduate (Masters)	2	40%
3 - 6 months	-	-	First degree	3	60%
6 - 12 months	-	-	Foundation degree or HND	-	-
12 - 24 months	-	-	School qualifications	-	-
More than 24 months	-	-			
Permanent / open-ended	4	100%	Employer contributes to pension	2	40%
Seniority			Post Funding		
Junior	-	-	Project or contract income	3	100%
Medium	3	75%	Established income	-	-
Senior	1	25%			

Archaeologist

Individuals	64		Roles		
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Volunteers			Field investigation and research	44	68%
			Historic environment advice and information	21	32%
Employment			Museum and visitor / user	-	-
Full-Time	58	89%	Educational and academic research	-	-
Part-Time	7	11%	Administrative support	-	-
Salary			Gender		
Minimum	£15,725		Female	24	38%
Average	£22,724		Male	40	63%
Maximum	£36,366				
Length of Service			Age		
up to 3 months	5	8%	16-19	-	-
3 - 6 months	2	3%	20-29	12	19%
6 - 12 months	-	-	30-39	27	42%
12 - 24 months	-	-	40-49	14	22%
2 - 5 years	23	35%	50-59	10	16%
5 - 10 years	17	26%	60 and over	1	2%
10 - 20 years	15	23%			
20 + years	3	5%	Qualifications		
			Post-doctoral		
Contract Lengths			Doctorate (PhD or DPhil)	5	8%
up to 3 months	-	-	Postgraduate (Masters)	19	29%
3 - 6 months	1	2%	First degree	39	60%
6 - 12 months	6	9%	Foundation degree or HND	1	2%
12 - 24 months	-	-	School qualifications	1	2%
More than 24 months	-	-			
Permanent / open-ended	57	89%	Employer contributes to pension	54	83%
Seniority			Post Funding		
Junior	45	69%	Project or contract income	27	61%
Medium	15	23%	Established income	17	39%
Senior	5	8%			

Archives Officer

Individuals	5		Roles		
Volunteers			Field investigation and research	1	20%

			Historic environment advice and information	4	80%
Employment			Museum and visitor / user		
Full-Time	4	80%	Educational and academic research		
Part-Time	1	20%	Administrative support		
Salary			Gender		
Minimum	£19,621		Female	2	40%
Average	£25,078		Male	3	60%
Maximum	£28,685				
Length of Service			Age		
up to 3 months	-	-	16-19	-	-
3 - 6 months	1	20%	20-29	4	80%
6 - 12 months	-	-	30-39	-	-
12 - 24 months	-	-	40-49	1	20%
2 - 5 years	1	20%	50-59	-	-
5 - 10 years	2	40%	60 and over	-	-
10 - 20 years	1	20%			
20 + years	-	-	Qualifications		
			Post-doctoral	-	-
Contract Lengths			Doctorate (PhD or DPhil)	1	20%
up to 3 months	-	-	Postgraduate (Masters)	3	60%
3 - 6 months	-	-	First degree	1	20%
6 - 12 months	-	-	Foundation degree or HND	-	-
12 - 24 months	-	-	School qualifications	-	-
More than 24 months	1	20%			
Permanent / open-ended	4	80%	Employer contributes to pension	5	100%
Seniority			Post Funding		
Junior	4	80%	Project or contract income	4	100%
Medium	1	20%	Established income	-	-
Senior					

Buildings Archaeologist

Individuals	2		Roles		
Volunteers			Field investigation and research	2	100%
			Historic environment advice and information	-	-

Employment			Museum and visitor / user	-	-
Full-Time	2	100%	Educational and academic research	-	-
Part-Time	-	-	Administrative support	-	-
Salary			Gender		
Minimum	£22,221		Female	1	50%
Average	£29,631		Male	1	50%
Maximum	£36,298				
Length of Service			Age		
up to 3 months	-	-	16-19	-	-
3 - 6 months	-	-	20-29	-	-
6 - 12 months	-	-	30-39	-	-
12 - 24 months	-	-	40-49	1	50%
2 - 5 years	-	-	50-59	-	-
5 - 10 years	-	-	60 and over	1	50%
10 - 20 years	1	50%			
20 + years	1	50%	Qualifications		
			Post-doctoral	1	50%
Contract Lengths			Doctorate (PhD or DPhil)	-	-
up to 3 months	-	-	Postgraduate (Masters)	-	-
3 - 6 months	-	-	First degree	1	50%
6 - 12 months	-	-	Foundation degree or HND	-	-
12 - 24 months	-	-	School qualifications	-	-
More than 24 months	-	-			
Permanent / open-ended	2	100%	Employer contributes to pension	2	100%
Seniority			Post Funding		
Junior	-	-	Project or contract income	2	100%
Medium	2	100%	Established income	-	-
Senior	-	-			

Computing Officer

Individuals	7		Roles		
Volunteers	0		Field investigation and research	-	-
			Historic environment advice and information	7	100%
Employment			Museum and visitor / user	-	-

Full-Time	5	71%	Educational and academic research	-	-
Part-Time	2	29%	Administrative support	-	-
Salary			Gender		
Minimum	£27,604		Female	3	43%
Average	£31,719		Male	4	57%
Maximum	£36,300				
Length of Service			Age		
up to 3 months	-	-	16-19	-	-
3 - 6 months	-	-	20-29	3	43%
6 - 12 months	-	-	30-39	2	29%
12 - 24 months	2	29%	40-49	1	14%
2 - 5 years	2	29%	50-59	-	-
5 - 10 years	2	29%	60 and over	1	14%
10 - 20 years	1	14%			
20 + years	-	-	Qualifications		
			Post-doctoral	-	-
Contract Lengths			Doctorate (PhD or DPhil)	2	29%
up to 3 months	-	-	Postgraduate (Masters)	3	49%
3 - 6 months	-	-	First degree	2	29%
6 - 12 months	-	-	Foundation degree or HND	-	-
12 - 24 months	2	29%	School qualifications	-	-
More than 24 months	2	29%			
Permanent / open-ended	3	43%	Employer contributes to pension	7	100%
Seniority			Post Funding		
Junior	5	29%	Project or contract income	6	86%
Medium	2	71%	Established income	1	14%
Senior	-	-			

Conservator

Individuals	4		Roles		
Volunteers			Field investigation and research	1	25%
			Historic environment advice and information	-	-
Employment			Museum and visitor / user	3	75%
Full-Time	4	100%	Educational and academic research	-	-

Part-Time	-	-	Administrative support	-	-
Salary			Gender		
Minimum	£24,000		Female	2	50%
Average	£27,340		Male	2	50%
Maximum	£36,298				
Length of Service			Age		
up to 3 months	-	-	16-19	-	-
3 - 6 months	-	-	20-29	-	-
6 - 12 months	-	-	30-39	2	50%
12 - 24 months	-	-	40-49	1	25%
2 - 5 years	1	25%	50-59	1	25%
5 - 10 years	1	25%	60 and over	-	-
10 - 20 years	1	25%			
20 + years	1	25%	Qualifications		
			Post-doctoral	-	-
Contract Lengths			Doctorate (PhD or DPhil)	1	25%
up to 3 months	-	-	Postgraduate (Masters)	2	50%
3 - 6 months	1	25%	First degree	1	25%
6 - 12 months	-	-	Foundation degree or HND	-	-
12 - 24 months	-	-	School qualifications	-	-
More than 24 months	-	-			
Permanent / open-ended	3	75%	Employer contributes to pension	4	100%
Seniority			Post Funding		
Junior	-	-	Project or contract income	3	75%
Medium	3	75%	Established income	1	25%
Senior	1	25%			

Conservation Archaeologists

Individuals	4		Roles		
Volunteers			Field investigation and research	-	-
			Historic environment advice and information	4	100%
Employment			Museum and visitor / user	-	-
Full-Time	2	50%	Educational and academic research	-	-

Part-Time	2	50%	Administrative support	-	-
Salary			Gender		
Minimum	£15,000		Female	1	25%
Average	£26,842		Male	3	75%
Maximum	£40,000				
Length of Service			Age		
up to 3 months	-	-	16-19	-	-
3 - 6 months	1	25%	20-29	-	-
6 - 12 months	-	-	30-39	2	50%
12 - 24 months	-	-	40-49	1	25%
2 - 5 years	-	-	50-59	1	25%
5 - 10 years	1	25%	60 and over	-	-
10 - 20 years	1	25%			
20 + years	1	25%	Qualifications		
			Post-doctoral		
Contract Lengths			Doctorate (PhD or DPhil)		
up to 3 months	-	-	Postgraduate (Masters)	2	50%
3 - 6 months	1	25%	First degree	2	50%
6 - 12 months	-	-	Foundation degree or HND		
12 - 24 months	-	-	School qualifications		
More than 24 months	-	-			
Permanent / open-ended	3	75%	Employer contributes to pension	4	100%
Seniority			Post Funding		
Junior	1	25%	Project or contract income		
Medium	2	50%	Established income	4	100%
Senior	1	25%			

Consultant

Individuals	15		Roles		
Volunteers			Field investigation and research	4	28%
			Historic environment advice and information	11	72%
Employment			Museum and visitor / user	-	-
Full-Time	12	85%	Educational and academic research	-	-
Part-Time	3	15%	Administrative support	-	-

Salary			Gender		
Minimum	£19,000		Female	6	37%
Average	£26,955		Male	9	63%
Maximum	£40,000				
Length of Service			Age		
up to 3 months	-	-	16-19	-	-
3 - 6 months	2	14%	20-29	4	28%
6 - 12 months	1	7%	30-39	4	28%
12 - 24 months	7	44%	40-49	5	35%
2 - 5 years	3	21%	50-59	2	8%
5 - 10 years	1	7%	60 and over	-	-
10 - 20 years	1	7%			
20 + years	-	-	Qualifications		
			Post-doctoral	-	-
Contract Lengths			Doctorate (PhD or DPhil)	1	7%
up to 3 months	-	-	Postgraduate (Masters)	10	70%
3 - 6 months	2	8%	First degree	4	23%
6 - 12 months	-	-	Foundation degree or HND	-	-
12 - 24 months	-	-	School qualifications	-	-
More than 24 months					
Permanent / open-ended	13	92%	Employer contributes to pension	12	85%
Seniority			Post Funding		
Junior	4	28%	Project or contract income	15	100%
Medium	5	30%	Established income		
Senior	6	42%			

County or Regional Archaeologist

Individuals	8		Roles		
Volunteers			Field investigation and research	1	17%
			Historic environment advice and information	5	83%
Employment			Museum and visitor / user		
Full-Time	8	100%	Educational and academic research		
Part-Time	-	-	Administrative support		

Salary			Gender		
Minimum	£21,000		Female	4	50%
Average	£30,833		Male	4	50%
Maximum	£40,000				
Length of Service			Age		
up to 3 months	-	-	16-19		
3 - 6 months	1	13%	20-29		
6 - 12 months	-	-	30-39	2	25%
12 - 24 months	-	-	40-49	1	13%
2 - 5 years	1	13%	50-59	4	50%
5 - 10 years	-	-	60 and over	1	13%
10 - 20 years	3	38%			
20 + years	3	38%	Qualifications		
			Post-doctoral	1	13%
Contract Lengths			Doctorate (PhD or DPhil)	4	50%
up to 3 months	-	-	Postgraduate (Masters)	2	25%
3 - 6 months	-	-	First degree	1	13%
6 - 12 months	-	-	Foundation degree or HND	-	-
12 - 24 months	1	13%	School qualifications	-	-
More than 24 months	-	-			
Permanent / open-ended	7	88%	Employer contributes to pension	8	100%
Seniority			Post Funding		
Junior	-	-	Project or contract income	1	14%
Medium	3	43%	Established income	6	86%
Senior	4	57%			

Director or Manager

Individuals	54		Roles		
Volunteers	1		Field investigation and research	37	71%
			Historic environment advice and information	11	21%
Employment			Museum and visitor / user	-	-
Full-Time	45	83%	Educational and academic research	4	8%
Part-Time	9	17%	Administrative support	-	-
Salary			Gender		

Minimum	£7,488		Female	15	28%
Average	£31,065		Male	39	72%
Maximum	£57,660				
Length of Service			Age		
up to 3 months	1	2%	16-19	-	-
3 - 6 months	-	-	20-29	1	2%
6 - 12 months	5	9%	30-39	18	34%
12 - 24 months	1	2%	40-49	16	30%
2 - 5 years	8	15%	50-59	14	26%
5 - 10 years	18	34%	60 and over	4	8%
10 - 20 years	14	26%			
20 + years	6	11%	Qualifications		
			Post-doctoral	-	-
Contract Lengths			Doctorate (PhD or DPhil)	12	22%
up to 3 months	1	2%	Postgraduate (Masters)	16	30%
3 - 6 months	-	-	First degree	24	44%
6 - 12 months	-	-	Foundation degree or HND	-	-
12 - 24 months	-	-	School qualifications	2	4%
More than 24 months	2	4%			
Permanent / open-ended	51	94%	Employer contributes to pension	35	65%
Seniority			Post Funding		
Junior	-	-	Project or contract income	29	60%
Medium	7	13%	Established income	19	40%
Senior	47	87%			

Education and Outreach Posts

Individuals	15		Roles		
Volunteers	-		Field investigation and research	3	20%
			Historic environment advice and information	4	27%
Employment			Museum and visitor / user	1	7%
Full-Time	14	93%	Educational and academic research	7	47%
Part-Time	1	7%	Administrative support	-	-
Salary			Gender		
Minimum	£15,000		Female	10	67%

Average	£21,559		Male	5	33%
Maximum	£40,500				
Length of Service			Age		
up to 3 months	3	20%	16-19	-	-
3 - 6 months	3	20%	20-29	6	40%
6 - 12 months	4	27%	30-39	7	47%
12 - 24 months	-	-	40-49	-	-
2 - 5 years	2	13%	50-59	1	7%
5 - 10 years	1	7%	60 and over	1	7%
10 - 20 years	1	7%			
20 + years	1	7%	Qualifications		
			Post-doctoral	-	-
Contract Lengths			Doctorate (PhD or DPhil)	4	27%
up to 3 months	-	-	Postgraduate (Masters)	5	33%
3 - 6 months	2	13%	First degree	6	40%
6 - 12 months	8	53%	Foundation degree or HND		
12 - 24 months	2	13%	School qualifications		
More than 24 months	1	7%			
Permanent / open-ended	2	13%	Employer contributes to pension	8	53%
Seniority			Post Funding		
Junior	11	73%	Project or contract income	-	-
Medium	3	20%	Established income	14	93%
Senior	1	7%			

Editor

Individuals	1		Roles		
Volunteers	-		Field investigation and research	-	-
			Historic environment advice and information	-	-
Employment			Museum and visitor / user	-	-
Full-Time	1	100%	Educational and academic research	1	100%
Part-Time			Administrative support	-	-
Salary			Gender		
Minimum	£36,300		Female	1	100%

Average	£36,300		Male	-	-
Maximum	£36,300				
Length of Service			Age		
up to 3 months	-	-	16-19	-	-
3 - 6 months	-	-	20-29	-	-
6 - 12 months	-	-	30-39	-	-
12 - 24 months	-	-	40-49	1	100%
2 - 5 years	-	-	50-59	-	-
5 - 10 years	-	-	60 and over	-	-
10 - 20 years	1	100%			
20 + years	-	-	Qualifications		
			Post-doctoral	-	-
Contract Lengths			Doctorate (PhD or DPhil)	-	-
up to 3 months	-	-	Postgraduate (Masters)	1	100%
3 - 6 months	-	-	First degree	-	-
6 - 12 months	-	-	Foundation degree or HND	-	-
12 - 24 months	-	-	School qualifications	-	-
More than 24 months	-	-			
Permanent / open-ended	1	100%	Employer contributes to pension	1	100%
Seniority			Post Funding		
Junior	-	-	Project or contract income	1	100%
Medium	1	100%	Established income	-	-
Senior	-	-			

Excavator or Site Assistant

Individuals	18		Roles		
Volunteers			Field investigation and research	18	100%
			Historic environment advice and information	-	-
Employment			Museum and visitor / user	-	-
Full-Time	18	100%	Educational and academic research	-	-
Part-Time	-	-	Administrative support	-	-
Salary			Gender		
Minimum	£15,658		Female	8	44%

Average	£16,392		Male	10	56%
Maximum	£16,540				
Length of Service			Age		
up to 3 months	15	83%	16-19	-	-
3 - 6 months	-	-	20-29	9	50%
6 - 12 months	2	11%	30-39	8	44%
12 - 24 months	1	6%	40-49	-	-
2 - 5 years	-	-	50-59	1	6%
5 - 10 years	-	-	60 and over	-	-
10 - 20 years	-	-			
20 + years	-	-	Qualifications		
			Post-doctoral	-	-
Contract Lengths			Doctorate (PhD or DPhil)	1	6%
up to 3 months	17	94%	Postgraduate (Masters)	11	61%
3 - 6 months	1	6%	First degree	6	33%
6 - 12 months	-	-	Foundation degree or HND	-	-
12 - 24 months	-	-	School qualifications	-	-
More than 24 months	-	-			
Permanent / open-ended	-	-	Employer contributes to pension	0	0%
Seniority			Post Funding		
Junior	18	100%	Project or contract income	18	100%
Medium	-	-	Established income	-	-
Senior	-	-			

Field Officer

Individuals	19		Roles		
Volunteers			Field investigation and research	19	100%
			Historic environment advice and information	-	-
Employment			Museum and visitor / user	-	-
Full-Time	10	53%	Educational and academic research	-	-
Part-Time	9	47%	Administrative support	-	-
Salary			Gender		
Minimum	£13,920		Female	16	84%

Average	£23,098		Male	3	16%
Maximum	£27,887				
Length of Service			Age		
up to 3 months	-	-	16-19	-	-
3 - 6 months	-	-	20-29	5	26%
6 - 12 months	-	-	30-39	6	32%
12 - 24 months	5	26%	40-49	4	21%
2 - 5 years	4	21%	50-59	3	16%
5 - 10 years	3	16%	60 and over	1	5%
10 - 20 years	7	37%			
20 + years	-	-	Qualifications		
			Post-doctoral	-	-
Contract Lengths			Doctorate (PhD or DPhil)	1	5%
up to 3 months	-	-	Postgraduate (Masters)	-	-
3 - 6 months	-	-	First degree	17	89%
6 - 12 months	-	-	Foundation degree or HND	-	-
12 - 24 months	-	-	School qualifications	1	5%
More than 24 months	-	-			
Permanent / open-ended	19	100%	Employer contributes to pension	12	63%
Seniority			Post Funding		
Junior	12	67%	Project or contract income	9	47%
Medium	6	33%	Established income	10	53%
Senior	-	-			

Finds Officer

Individuals	12		Roles		
Volunteers	1		Field investigation and research	8	73%
			Historic environment advice and information	1	9%
Employment			Museum and visitor / user	2	18%
Full-Time	6	50%	Educational and academic research	-	-
Part-Time	6	50%	Administrative support	-	-
Salary			Gender		
Minimum	£4,500		Female	8	67%
Average	£18,863		Male	4	33%

Maximum	£28,636				
Length of Service			Age		
up to 3 months	2	17%	16-19	-	-
3 - 6 months	-	-	20-29	1	8%
6 - 12 months	-	-	30-39	5	42%
12 - 24 months	1	8%	40-49	2	17%
2 - 5 years	4	33%	50-59	4	33%
5 - 10 years	2	17%	60 and over	-	-
10 - 20 years	2	17%			
20 + years	1	8%	Qualifications		
			Post-doctoral	-	-
Contract Lengths			Doctorate (PhD or DPhil)	4	36%
up to 3 months	1	9%	Postgraduate (Masters)	3	27%
3 - 6 months	-	-	First degree	2	18%
6 - 12 months	-	-	Foundation degree or HND	2	18%
12 - 24 months	-	-	School qualifications		
More than 24 months	2	18%			
Permanent / open-ended	6	55%	Employer contributes to pension	8	73%
Seniority			Post Funding		
Junior	2	18%	Project or contract income	6	75%
Medium	6	55%	Established income	2	25%
Senior	3	27%			

Historic Environment Record Officer

Individuals	51		Roles		
Volunteers	1		Field investigation and research	-	-
			Historic environment advice and information	49	100%
Employment			Museum and visitor / user	-	-
Full-Time	40	78%	Educational and academic research	-	-
Part-Time	11	22%	Administrative support	-	-
Salary			Gender		
Minimum	£17,161		Female	32	64%
Average	£25,533		Male	18	36%

Maximum	£34,500				
Length of Service			Age		
up to 3 months	2	4%	16-19	-	-
3 - 6 months	-	-	20-29	6	12%
6 - 12 months	3	6%	30-39	16	32%
12 - 24 months	3	6%	40-49	16	32%
2 - 5 years	4	8%	50-59	8	16%
5 - 10 years	17	33%	60 and over	4	8%
10 - 20 years	12	24%			
20 + years	10	20%	Qualifications		
			Post-doctoral		
Contract Lengths			Doctorate (PhD or DPhil)	2	4%
up to 3 months	1	2%	Postgraduate (Masters)	20	39%
3 - 6 months	-	-	First degree	29	57%
6 - 12 months	3	6%	Foundation degree or HND		
12 - 24 months	2	4%	School qualifications		
More than 24 months	1	2%			
Permanent / open-ended	42	86%	Employer contributes to pension	43	88%
Seniority			Post Funding		
Junior	9	18%	Project or contract income	13.6	32%
Medium	34	69%	Established income	28.4	68%
Senior	6	12%			

Illustrator

Individuals	9		Roles		
Volunteers			Field investigation and research	6	86%
			Historic environment advice and information	-	-
Employment			Museum and visitor / user	-	-
Full-Time	6	67%	Educational and academic research	-	-
Part-Time	3	33%	Administrative support	1	14%
Salary			Gender		
Minimum	£19,621		Female	5	56%
Average	£24,411		Male	4	44%
Maximum	£40,000				

Length of Service			Age		
up to 3 months	-	-	16-19	-	-
3 - 6 months	-	-	20-29	-	-
6 - 12 months	1	11%	30-39	1	11%
12 - 24 months	-	-	40-49	4	44%
2 - 5 years	-	-	50-59	4	44%
5 - 10 years	1	11%	60 and over	-	-
10 - 20 years	3	33%			
20 + years	4	44%	Qualifications		
			Post-doctoral	-	-
Contract Lengths			Doctorate (PhD or DPhil)	-	-
up to 3 months	-	-	Postgraduate (Masters)	1	11%
3 - 6 months	-	-	First degree	6	67%
6 - 12 months	-	-	Foundation degree or HND	1	11%
12 - 24 months	-	-	School qualifications	1	11%
More than 24 months	-	-			
Permanent / open-ended	9	100%	Employer contributes to pension	9	100%
Seniority			Post Funding		
Junior	2	22%	Project or contract income	7	78%
Medium	6	67%	Established income	2	22%
Senior	1	11%			

Inspector

Individuals	7		Roles		
Volunteers			Field investigation and research	-	-
			Historic environment advice and information	7	100%
Employment			Museum and visitor / user	-	-
Full-Time	6	86%	Educational and academic research	-	-
Part-Time	1	14%	Administrative support	-	-
Salary			Gender		
Minimum	£25,700		Female	3	43%
Average	£38,057		Male	4	57%
Maximum	£55,400				

Length of Service			Age		
up to 3 months	1	14%	16-19	-	-
3 - 6 months	-	-	20-29	-	-
6 - 12 months	-	-	30-39	2	29%
12 - 24 months	1	14%	40-49	4	57%
2 - 5 years	2	29%	50-59		
5 - 10 years	-	-	60 and over	1	14%
10 - 20 years	2	29%			
20 + years	1	14%	Qualifications		
			Post-doctoral	-	-
Contract Lengths			Doctorate (PhD or DPhil)	1	14%
up to 3 months	-	-	Postgraduate (Masters)	5	71%
3 - 6 months	-	-	First degree	1	14%
6 - 12 months	-	-	Foundation degree or HND	-	-
12 - 24 months	-	-	School qualifications	-	-
More than 24 months	-	-			
Permanent / open-ended	7	100%	Employer contributes to pension	7	100%
Seniority			Post Funding		
Junior			Project or contract income	-	-
Medium	4	57%	Established income	7	100%
Senior	3	43%			

Junior Posts

Individuals	21		Roles		
Volunteers			Field investigation and research	19	90%
			Historic environment advice and information	2	10%
Employment			Museum and visitor / user	-	-
Full-Time	20	95%	Educational and academic research	-	-
Part-Time	1	5%	Administrative support	-	-
Salary			Gender		
Minimum	£15,725		Female	9	43%
Average	£20,558		Male	12	57%
Maximum	£42,000				
Length of Service			Age		

up to 3 months			16-19	-	-
3 - 6 months	3	14%	20-29	7	33%
6 - 12 months	-	-	30-39	6	29%
12 - 24 months	3	14%	40-49	7	33%
2 - 5 years	6	29%	50-59	1	5%
5 - 10 years	6	29%	60 and over	-	-
10 - 20 years	1	5%			
20 + years	2	10%	Qualifications		
			Post-doctoral	-	-
Contract Lengths			Doctorate (PhD or DPhil)	2	10%
up to 3 months	-	-	Postgraduate (Masters)	3	14%
3 - 6 months	-	-	First degree	14	67%
6 - 12 months	-	-	Foundation degree or HND	-	-
12 - 24 months	-	-	School qualifications	2	10%
More than 24 months	1	5%			
Permanent / open-ended	20	95%	Employer contributes to pension	15	71%
Seniority			Post Funding		
Junior	17	81%	Project or contract income	19	90%
Medium	-	-	Established income	2	10%
Senior	4	19%			

Museum Archaeologist

Individuals	6		Roles		
Volunteers			Field investigation and research	-	-
			Historic environment advice and information	-	-
Employment			Museum and visitor / user	6	100%
Full-Time	6	100%	Educational and academic research	-	-
Part-Time	-	-	Administrative support	-	-
Salary			Gender		
Minimum	£17,613		Female	5	83%
Average	£30,875		Male	1	17%
Maximum	£41,822				
Length of Service			Age		
up to 3 months	-	-	16-19	-	-

3 - 6 months	-	-	20-29	-	-
6 - 12 months	-	-	30-39	4	67%
12 - 24 months	1	17%	40-49	2	33%
2 - 5 years	1	17%	50-59	-	-
5 - 10 years	3	50%	60 and over	-	-
10 - 20 years	1	17%			
20 + years	-	-	Qualifications		
			Post-doctoral	-	-
Contract Lengths			Doctorate (PhD or DPhil)	1	17%
up to 3 months	-	-	Postgraduate (Masters)	1	17%
3 - 6 months	-	-	First degree	4	67%
6 - 12 months	-	-	Foundation degree or HND	-	-
12 - 24 months	-	-	School qualifications	-	-
More than 24 months	-	-			
Permanent / open-ended	6	100%	Employer contributes to pension	6	100%
Seniority			Post Funding		
Junior	1	17%	Project or contract income	-	-
Medium	5	83%	Established income	6	100%
Senior					

Other posts

Individuals	69		Roles		
Volunteers	15		Field investigation and research	16	30%
			Historic environment advice and information	28	52%
Employment			Museum and visitor / user	1	2%
Full-Time	39	57%	Educational and academic research	5	9%
Part-Time	30	43%	Administrative support	4	7%
Salary			Gender		
Minimum	£15,444		Female	35	51%
Average	£26,406		Male	33	49%
Maximum	£42,000				
Length of Service			Age		
up to 3 months	-	-	16-19		
3 - 6 months	2	3%	20-29	14	21%

6 - 12 months	6	9%	30-39	19	28%
12 - 24 months	6	9%	40-49	19	28%
2 - 5 years	23	33%	50-59	13	19%
5 - 10 years	25	36%	60 and over	3	4%
10 - 20 years	2	3%			
20 + years	5	7%	Qualifications		
			Post-doctoral		
Contract Lengths			Doctorate (PhD or DPhil)	14	20%
up to 3 months	-	-	Postgraduate (Masters)	27	39%
3 - 6 months	-	-	First degree	24	35%
6 - 12 months	3	6%	Foundation degree or HND	2	3%
12 - 24 months	1	2%	School qualifications	2	3%
More than 24 months	6	11%			
Permanent / open-ended	44	81%	Employer contributes to pension	42	61%
Seniority			Post Funding		
Junior	17	31%	Project or contract income	24	46%
Medium	27	49%	Established income	28	54%
Senior	11	20%			

Other support posts

Individuals	3		Roles		
Volunteers			Field investigation and research	-	-
			Historic environment advice and information	-	-
Employment			Museum and visitor / user	-	-
Full-Time	1	33%	Educational and academic research	-	-
Part-Time	2	67%	Administrative support	3	100%
Salary			Gender		
Minimum	£1,100		Female	2	67%
Average	£10,854		Male	1	33%
Maximum	£31,463				
Length of Service			Age	-	-
up to 3 months	-	-	16-19	-	-
3 - 6 months	-	-	20-29	-	-
6 - 12 months	-	-	30-39	-	-

12 - 24 months	-	-	40-49	-	-
2 - 5 years	1	33%	50-59	2	67%
5 - 10 years	-	-	60 and over	1	33%
10 - 20 years	2	67%			
20 + years			Qualifications		
			Post-doctoral	-	-
Contract Lengths			Doctorate (PhD or DPhil)	-	-
up to 3 months	-	-	Postgraduate (Masters)	1	33%
3 - 6 months	-	-	First degree	-	-
6 - 12 months	-	-	Foundation degree or HND	-	-
12 - 24 months	-	-	School qualifications	2	67%
More than 24 months	-	-			
Permanent / open-ended	3	100%	Employer contributes to pension	1	33%
Seniority			Post Funding		
Junior	2	67%	Project or contract income	1	33%
Medium	-	-	Established income	2	67%
Senior	1	33%			

Planning Archaeologist

Individuals	49		Roles		
Volunteers	9		Field investigation and research	1	3%
			Historic environment advice and information	39	98%
Employment			Museum and visitor / user		
Full-Time	25	51%	Educational and academic research		
Part-Time	24	49%	Administrative support		
Salary			Gender		
Minimum	£17,161		Female	26	52%
Average	£30,955		Male	24	48%
Maximum	£66,800				
Length of Service			Age		
up to 3 months	-	-	16-19	1	2%
3 - 6 months	7	14%	20-29	4	8%
6 - 12 months	1	2%	30-39	14	28%
12 - 24 months	1	2%	40-49	12	24%

2 - 5 years	5	10%	50-59	11	22%
5 - 10 years	15	31%	60 and over	8	16%
10 - 20 years	12	24%			
20 + years	8	16%	Qualifications		
			Post-doctoral	1	3%
Contract Lengths			Doctorate (PhD or DPhil)	3	8%
up to 3 months	-	-	Postgraduate (Masters)	14	35%
3 - 6 months	2	5%	First degree	20	50%
6 - 12 months	1	3%	Foundation degree or HND	1	3%
12 - 24 months	-	-	School qualifications	1	3%
More than 24 months	2	5%			
Permanent / open-ended	35	88%	Employer contributes to pension	35	88%
Seniority			Post Funding		
Junior	4	10%	Project or contract income	9.5	27%
Medium	27	66%	Established income	25.5	73%
Senior	10	24%			

Project Assistant

Individuals	30		Roles		
Volunteers	1		Field investigation and research	25	86%
			Historic environment advice and information	4	14%
Employment			Museum and visitor / user	-	-
Full-Time	26	87%	Educational and academic research	-	-
Part-Time	4	13%	Administrative support	-	-
Salary			Gender		
Minimum	£16,982		Female	15	50%
Average	£19,103		Male	15	50%
Maximum	£32,500				
Length of Service			Age		
up to 3 months	2	7%	16-19	-	-
3 - 6 months	8	27%	20-29	9	30%
6 - 12 months	1	3%	30-39	11	37%
12 - 24 months	9	30%	40-49	7	23%
2 - 5 years	3	10%	50-59	3	10%

5 - 10 years	7	23%	60 and over	-	-
10 - 20 years	-	-			
20 + years	-	-	Qualifications		
			Post-doctoral		
Contract Lengths			Doctorate (PhD or DPhil)	1	3%
up to 3 months	4	14%	Postgraduate (Masters)	3	10%
3 - 6 months	-	-	First degree	23	77%
6 - 12 months	8	28%	Foundation degree or HND		
12 - 24 months	7	24%	School qualifications	1	3%
More than 24 months	-	-			
Permanent / open-ended	10	34%	Employer contributes to pension	16	53%
Seniority			Post Funding		
Junior	27	93%	Project or contract income	16	57%
Medium	2	7%	Established income	12	43%
Senior					

Project Officer

Individuals	51		Roles		
Volunteers			Field investigation and research	38	75%
			Historic environment advice and information	12	24%
Employment			Museum and visitor / user	-	-
Full-Time	45	88%	Educational and academic research	-	-
Part-Time	6	12%	Administrative support	1	2%
Salary			Gender		
Minimum	£16,000		Female	21	41%
Average	£23,713		Male	30	59%
Maximum	£28,650				
Length of Service			Age		
up to 3 months	2	4%	16-19	-	-
3 - 6 months	5	10%	20-29	5	10%
6 - 12 months	1	2%	30-39	22	43%
12 - 24 months	5	10%	40-49	19	37%
2 - 5 years	15	29%	50-59	4	8%
5 - 10 years	6	12%	60 and over	1	2%

10 - 20 years	16	31%			
20 + years	1	2%	Qualifications		
			Post-doctoral		
Contract Lengths			Doctorate (PhD or DPhil)	5	10%
up to 3 months	-	-	Postgraduate (Masters)	18	37%
3 - 6 months	1	2%	First degree	22	45%
6 - 12 months	2	4%	Foundation degree or HND	2	4%
12 - 24 months	2	4%	School qualifications	2	4%
More than 24 months	12	24%			
Permanent / open-ended	34	67%	Employer contributes to pension	35	69%
Seniority			Post Funding		
Junior	8	16%	Project or contract income	33	80%
Medium	39	76%	Established income	8	20%
Senior	4	8%			

Project Manager

Individuals	38		Roles		
Volunteers			Field investigation and research	25	66%
			Historic environment advice and information	13	34%
Employment			Museum and visitor / user	-	-
Full-Time	34	92%	Educational and academic research	-	-
Part-Time	3	8%	Administrative support	-	-
Salary			Gender		
Minimum	£25,320		Female	5	13%
Average	£33,438		Male	32	84%
Maximum	£61,834				
Length of Service			Age		
up to 3 months			16-19	-	-
3 - 6 months			20-29	-	-
6 - 12 months	1	3%	30-39	9	24%
12 - 24 months	1	3%	40-49	23	61%
2 - 5 years	3	8%	50-59	5	13%
5 - 10 years	13	35%	60 and over	-	-

10 - 20 years	14	38%			
20 + years	5	14%	Qualifications		
			Post-doctoral		
Contract Lengths			Doctorate (PhD or DPhil)	3	9%
up to 3 months	-	-	Postgraduate (Masters)	8	23%
3 - 6 months	-	-	First degree	24	69%
6 - 12 months	-	-	Foundation degree or HND		
12 - 24 months	-	-	School qualifications		
More than 24 months	-	-			
Permanent / open-ended	37	100%	Employer contributes to pension	34	89%
Seniority			Post Funding		
Junior	-	-	Project or contract income	34	92%
Medium	2	5%	Established income	3	8%
Senior	36	95%			

Researcher

Individuals	12		Roles		
Volunteers			Field investigation and research	3	25%
			Historic environment advice and information	-	-
Employment			Museum and visitor / user	-	-
Full-Time	10	83%	Educational and academic research	9	75%
Part-Time	2	17%	Administrative support	-	-
Salary			Gender		
Minimum	£8,947		Female	6	50%
Average	£25,594		Male	6	50%
Maximum	£47,441				
Length of Service			Age		
up to 3 months	-	-	16-19	-	-
3 - 6 months	1	8%	20-29	1	8%
6 - 12 months	2	17%	30-39	6	50%
12 - 24 months	1	8%	40-49	3	25%
2 - 5 years	4	33%	50-59	2	17%
5 - 10 years	1	8%	60 and over	-	-
10 - 20 years	2	17%			

20 + years	1	8%	Qualifications		
			Post-doctoral	-	-
Contract Lengths			Doctorate (PhD or DPhil)	3	25%
up to 3 months			Postgraduate (Masters)	2	17%
3 - 6 months			First degree	7	58%
6 - 12 months	2	17%	Foundation degree or HND	-	-
12 - 24 months			School qualifications	-	-
More than 24 months	1	8%			
Permanent / open-ended	9	75%	Employer contributes to pension	11	92%
Seniority			Post Funding		
Junior	2	17%	Project or contract income	6	50%
Medium	7	58%	Established income	6	50%
Senior	3	25%			

Rural Advice

Individuals	3		Roles		
Volunteers			Field investigation and research	-	-
			Historic environment advice and information	3	100%
Employment			Museum and visitor / user	-	-
Full-Time	2	67%	Educational and academic research	-	-
Part-Time	1	33%	Administrative support	-	-
Salary			Gender		
Minimum	£27,000		Female	1	33%
Average	£30,000		Male	2	67%
Maximum	£34,000				
Length of Service			Age		
up to 3 months	-	-	16-19	-	-
3 - 6 months	-	-	20-29	-	-
6 - 12 months	-	-	30-39	1	33%
12 - 24 months	-	-	40-49	1	33%
2 - 5 years	-	-	50-59	1	33%
5 - 10 years	2	67%	60 and over	-	-
10 - 20 years	1	33%			

20 + years	-	-	Qualifications		
			Post-doctoral	-	-
Contract Lengths			Doctorate (PhD or DPhil)	-	-
up to 3 months	-	-	Postgraduate (Masters)	2	67%
3 - 6 months	-	-	First degree	1	33%
6 - 12 months	-	-	Foundation degree or HND	-	-
12 - 24 months	-	-	School qualifications	-	-
More than 24 months	-	-			
Permanent / open-ended	3	100%	Employer contributes to pension	3	100%
Seniority			Post Funding		
Junior	-	-	Project or contract income		
Medium	2	67%	Established income	3	100%
Senior	1	33%			

Senior Archaeologists

Individuals	42		Roles		
Volunteers			Field investigation and research	24	57%
			Historic environment advice and information	13	31%
Employment			Museum and visitor / user	-	-
Full-Time	37	88%	Educational and academic research	5	12%
Part-Time	5	12%	Administrative support	-	-
Salary			Gender		
Minimum	£22,069		Female	25	60%
Average	£28,284		Male	17	40%
Maximum	£41,822				
Length of Service			Age		
up to 3 months	-	-	16-19	-	-
3 - 6 months	1	2%	20-29	1	2%
6 - 12 months	-	-	30-39	15	36%
12 - 24 months	-	-	40-49	11	26%
2 - 5 years	10	24%	50-59	12	29%
5 - 10 years	6	14%	60 and over	3	7%
10 - 20 years	13	31%			
20 + years	12	29%	Qualifications		

			Post-doctoral	1	2%
Contract Lengths			Doctorate (PhD or DPhil)	2	5%
up to 3 months	-	-	Postgraduate (Masters)	12	29%
3 - 6 months	-	-	First degree	25	60%
6 - 12 months	-	-	Foundation degree or HND	1	2%
12 - 24 months	-	-	School qualifications	1	2%
More than 24 months	-	-			
Permanent / open-ended	42	100%	Employer contributes to pension	41	98%
Seniority			Post Funding		
Junior	-	-	Project or contract income	24	57%
Medium	34	81%	Established income	17	40%
Senior	8	19%			

Senior posts

Individuals	68		Roles		
Volunteers			Field investigation and research	27	40%
			Historic environment advice and information	31	46%
Employment			Museum and visitor / user	2	3%
Full-Time	53	78%	Educational and academic research	3	4%
Part-Time	15	22%	Administrative support	4	6%
Salary			Gender		
Minimum	£23,000		Female	19	28%
Average	£33,510		Male	48	72%
Maximum	£61,500				
Length of Service			Age		
up to 3 months	2	3%	16-19	-	-
3 - 6 months	1	1%	20-29	2	3%
6 - 12 months	7	10%	30-39	11	16%
12 - 24 months	2	3%	40-49	21	31%
2 - 5 years	6	9%	50-59	29	43%
5 - 10 years	12	18%	60 and over	4	6%
10 - 20 years	19	28%			
20 + years	18	27%	Qualifications		
			Post-doctoral	-	-

Contract Lengths			Doctorate (PhD or DPhil)	13	19%
up to 3 months	1	2%	Postgraduate (Masters)	22	33%
3 - 6 months	-	-	First degree	30	45%
6 - 12 months	-	-	Foundation degree or HND	1	1%
12 - 24 months	-	-	School qualifications	1	1%
More than 24 months	2	3%			
Permanent / open-ended	62	95%	Employer contributes to pension	64	94%
Seniority			Post Funding		
Junior	-	-	Project or contract income	29	46%
Medium	25	38%	Established income	34	54%
Senior	40	62%			

Supervisor

Individuals	31		Roles		
Volunteers	1		Field investigation and research	30	100%
			Historic environment advice and information	-	-
Employment			Museum and visitor / user	-	-
Full-Time	30	97%	Educational and academic research	-	-
Part-Time	1	3%	Administrative support	-	-
Salary			Gender		
Minimum	£17,161		Female	4	13%
Average	£23,872		Male	27	87%
Maximum	£77,459				
Length of Service			Age		
up to 3 months	-	-	16-19	-	-
3 - 6 months	-	-	20-29	2	6%
6 - 12 months	4	13%	30-39	16	52%
12 - 24 months	1	3%	40-49	10	32%
2 - 5 years	10	32%	50-59	3	10%
5 - 10 years	13	42%	60 and over	-	-
10 - 20 years	3	10%			
20 + years	-	-	Qualifications		
			Post-doctoral	-	-
Contract Lengths			Doctorate (PhD or DPhil)	-	-

up to 3 months	4	15%	Postgraduate (Masters)	4	13%
3 - 6 months	-	-	First degree	26	84%
6 - 12 months	-	-	Foundation degree or HND	-	-
12 - 24 months	-	-	School qualifications	1	3%
More than 24 months	-	-			
Permanent / open-ended	22	85%	Employer contributes to pension	9	30%
Seniority			Post Funding		
Junior	9	30%	Project or contract income	25	100%
Medium	20	67%	Established income	-	-
Senior	1	3%			

Warden

Individuals	6		Roles		
Volunteers			Field investigation and research	-	-
			Historic environment advice and information	6	100%
Employment			Museum and visitor / user	-	-
Full-Time	-	-	Educational and academic research	-	-
Part-Time	6	100%	Administrative support	-	-
Salary			Gender		
Minimum	£21,120		Female	5	83%
Average	£23,160		Male	1	17%
Maximum	£25,200				
Length of Service			Age		
up to 3 months	-	-	16-19	-	-
3 - 6 months	-	-	20-29	-	-
6 - 12 months	-	-	30-39	-	-
12 - 24 months	-	-	40-49	2	33%
2 - 5 years	2	33%	50-59	4	67%
5 - 10 years	-	-	60 and over	-	-
10 - 20 years	4	67%			
20 + years	-	-	Qualifications		
			Post-doctoral	-	-
Contract Lengths			Doctorate (PhD or DPhil)	1	17%
up to 3 months	-	-	Postgraduate (Masters)	1	17%

3 - 6 months	-	-	First degree	4	67%
6 - 12 months	-	-	Foundation degree or HND	-	-
12 - 24 months	-	-	School qualifications	-	-
More than 24 months	-	-			
Permanent / open-ended	6	100%	Employer contributes to pension	6	100%
Seniority			Post Funding		
Junior	6	100%	Project or contract income	-	-
Medium	-	-	Established income	6	100%
Senior	-	-			

Appendix 2: Comments

Comments received from respondents are reproduced *verbatim*, with the exception of organisation names which have been removed.

I think there is a problem where one-person or other very small companies try to meet standards developed for larger organisations. This has arisen with both IfA registration and Achilles UVDB accreditation

I am a sole trader, providing a range of site, PX, training and illustration services. I have only been back trading since May this year after a 2 year employed stint at a major RO, although I did run my own business 2008-2010 when it was broadly successful despite starting in August 2008! I also work on a short contract PAYE basis as I am only just getting my freelance business back up. For me I am hoping to grow my business, however I am in a bit of a niche(s), and starting from a low turnover. I do feel that although some employers will close or be taken over (e.g. council units) -and it is very possible that a very large unit will fail- that there is every reason for cautious confidence in the sector growing. I feel the main cause of business failure is the undercharging for contracts, often at 10-15% on a consistent basis. This has placed those larger companies under great stress and diminished their reserves. Ultimately it is failed business models and high overheads rather than the recession that has caused these companies stress. There are many companies which will instantly take advantage of any resultant gap in the market, plus new sole trader start ups from the ashes. The big danger for the profession is that we continue the race to the bottom in terms of standards, of pay and continue to ignore training. As a site archaeologist I am appalled at the levels of skill/knowledge deemed acceptable on sites across the country and exhibited by all levels of staff.. Re training I believe that the majority of site staff are not given sufficient training at the start of their careers, and only receive training once they are deemed 'valuable' to the employer. I believe we need to develop ways of training all staff at all points of their career, and that this should be accredited, preferably tied to NOS and the NVQ, although maybe not formally. A lot of the questions are not applicable but have answered as best I could.

Responses are from the viewpoint of a single specialist officer within a local planning authority, not from an archaeological service (such as a county HES) or company.

Following a very bad year, 2013 appears to be tighter, with tendering for jobs very difficult. A wave of unprofessional box ticking and low quotations is flooding the market. Investment in large civil engineering projects by the government is the only way ahead

Universities still producing graduates that in some cases unfit for the workplace, unable to write English and express themselves adequately and have totally unrealistic expectations of archaeology as a career or profession. I feel that the heritage sector and undergraduates are currently being let down (in general terms - there are still very good departments and individuals at some universities) badly by UK universities as they have

become detached and distant from the 'real' archaeological and professional world beyond University-based archaeology. Many courses are irrelevant to the needs of the profession, too many undergraduates are advised to undertake post-graduate degrees with the false promise that it will help them get a job in archaeology and too few graduates have a positive mental attitude to work, what is required of them and what they can contribute.

You didn't give chance to explain, but archaeol only forms a small part of what i and my org does. But i answered the questions for the org as a whole.

Could probably do with a few more questions about using self employed staff, which we predominately do. We can pay them better and generally they are better archaeologists.

Obviously Im a self employed consultant so you will need to take that into account. In general employment numbers appear to have stabilised, with possibly an uptick being seen if advertised work is an indicator. Many organisation will have taken the opportunity to shed staff/skills no longer required, and some will have re-organised. However, the very difficult trading environment means many organisations will still have little to spend on training and staff development, and unfortunately, many still think of this as a cost, not as an investment. Very few archaeological contractors have much experience or expertise in training with senior staff largely having learned on the job. Until this changes the profession will struggle to fully professionalise.

This survey is not that appropriate for freelance/ sole trader finds specialists

It has been difficult to respond meaningfully to most of these questions because they do not sit well with the University's main function as a teaching and research body.

My company has only been operating for a little over 12 months and I work part-time. I don't employ permanent staff and only employ staff when I need to, therefore I found it difficult/impossible to answer some of the questions, especially regarding training.

The biggest problems faced by the industry are appalling margins and loss of skills - it is just not as much fun as it used to be (at all levels). Margins have a direct bearing on both confidence and salaries and we still feel that some companies are buying work at unsustainably low rates. Not a strategy that helps anybody in the long term. Without the margin there is no confidence to invest in staff, training or equipment. On the salaries front we just do not understand why some ROs feel the need to put pressure on the IFA minima specifically and salaries in general. We compete with other ROs on the majority of larger projects and are all in the same boat! We have found recruitment difficult in some areas. This is particularly acute where client advice is needed rather than more academic/hands on archaeology. However, this is exactly the environment where supply and demand should start to push salaries up in some areas. This has to be good going forward although difficult to manage in the short term. It does, however, require that people have the confidence to move jobs occasionally - difficult of course when your

current employer has seen you through hard times. As for the fun - we just have to pick our selves up and inject some of that locked-up enthusiasm back into the system.

Couple of points - survey not well set out for one person organisations (e.g. £m turnover!?, use of volunteers etc.). As for IFA questions - interesting choice of answers, I have found that some IFA reg organisations are the worst for record keeping and as employers for temp staff so dinna want to be included in with them, also reg org status seems like more 'stamp collecting' like ISO 9001 stuff. One ISO reg company I know is the biggest burecratic nightmare I have ever come across.

As I work as a self-employed sole trader, some of the questions are difficult to answer, so have been left blank. Membership of a union would not be relevant. The NVQ qualification is not relevant (although I am an NVQ Assessor). I do not use volunteers, so the questions relating to unpaid staff are not relevant. My view that the market for the work I carry out will deteriorate is based on the expectation that the public sector will shrink. Much of my work has come from this sector.

Faster move to a chartered profession covering the whole of the historic environment not the IFA/IHBC split

We have noticed the rise of 0 hours contracts as a response to huge fluctuations in work load and a proliferation of 'one man bands' able to carry out small scale works very cheaply. Projects are increasingly difficult to programme, the level of very small projects appears relatively constant, medium and large scale projects are increasingly difficult to price competitively. It is not so much that there are many more organisations competing, but there are fewer pieces of work making each job a much more critical 'must win'.

The survey seems massively biased in favour of larger organisations with several tiers of management and specialists and considerably larger budgets and I do not feel it will reflect smaller organisations very well if at all.

I didn't answer the question on turnover as we have not reached over £1m in turnover in the last 3 years, the figures would be more along the line of £500000, then £350000 and last year £200000. We finding there is a lack of training in people coming directly from uiverrrsity, they have no field experience and those that do come from a research training background which is totally different from the 'rescue' archaeology commerical companies undertake.

A lot of this questionnaire is geared towards commercial units. To make it more useful as a survey, it should have encompassed a wider range of questioning with a broader remit to assess everyone working in the profession properly. As a local authority planning advice service, our answers have needed to be "best fit" rather than accurate in a lot of cases - this will affect your results. The financial section in particular is irrelevant, but there is no field to fill in indicating that so it will simply look like we've declined to answer which is not the case. Sole traders and not-for-profit archaeological organisations and practitioners will find this a difficult surevy to address and might not bother answering.

Difficult to reply to many questions when our service is only a tiny part of a larger organisation (local government)

No comment

In general, I think business will improve over the next few months and years and the industry will probably grow. However, the quality of archaeological work has and will continue to slip as costs continue to be cut and the competitive tender process that drives the industry inevitably erodes standards.

I remain pessimistic. Currently there is a threat to wage levels in my organisation due to single status where a number of posts, including my own, are under threat of downgrading.

almost all of the questions do not apply to me - work from home

The question about salaries, we put decreased, but this is due to our employer imposing 3 days of mandatory unpaid holiday. This results in annual salaries dropping, but staff are still paid the same rate per day. Perhaps we should have put unchanged?

After taking early retirement/redundancy from EH in 2010 I set up as self-employed and have earned only a small amount since then on a consultancy basis. This is why my response is so lacking in data as most of the questions do not really apply.

Some archaeology is excellent but unfortunately much falls well short of desirable standards. If Archaeologists wish to be treated as a profession, then they must do more to introduce consistent standards, training and conduct

[*location*] Museum is part of the Culture and Leisure Dept of the [*authority*]

Much of this survey is not really relevant to a sole-trader

I am a freelance lithic specialist. Over the past 5 years I have also undertaken temporary teaching contracts in a university.

You haven't got time to hear my views.....

Notes: I'm basically a one-man band, with part-time admin support. I went freelance after losing my job. I am doing better on my own than I would be in an equivalent level job though; and with much better prospects.

Archaeological services within [*local planning authority*] were re-organised in 2012 with the amalgamation of the Archaeology Service (contract archaeology) and the archaeology section of the Historic Environment Team (planning advice) and so comparison with previous surveys not applicable.

Local authorities are fighting a constant battle to maintain planning advice services in a climate of ongoing real-term reductions in funding streams. Many services are

operating at their limits, and are vulnerable to cuts, restructuring and loss of influence which may have serious knock-on effects on the commercial sector.

Please note that a number of questions are not relevant to a local authority and so have been left blank.

This survey seems to have been drawn up so as to exclude those of us offering specialist services (in my case pottery analysis and reporting) and the role of the sole trader / free lance operator and as such will not be a reliable source of figures on these aspects of the profession

1. following a service delivery review, the management of the Sites and Monuments Record (job-share) post has been (August 2012) transferred to Collections and Archives, but within the same Directorate, and with continuing 'content' involvement with the rest of the county archaeology service, with which it is planned to be relocated/co-located in 2014/15. 2. The financial assessment part of this form was not filled in because, as has so often been the case in the past, the assumption appears to be that income is derived from commercial operations. [company name] secures over 50% of its funding (c.£185,000 in 2011/12; slightly less in 2012/13), and supports 'short-term contract' staff (none of whom has currently had less than seven years' continuous employment, and one of whom is beginning their fourth three-year contract) from external income generated from grant-aid and partnership working, and some limited commissioning (usually today following tender submission). This is a largely unacknowledged 'business model' for archaeological organisations nationally, perhaps because it generates a relatively small percentage of national funding totals. In Herefordshire, it ensures that some rather than no community heritage/historic conservation/archaeological research information is gained incrementally each year for parts of the county that experience no (or vanishingly little) development-related archaeological work. It also enables local tax-payers to have a sense that their heritage is both important and supported - at least for the time being.

I answered question 2, 3, and 4 in the staffing section in relation to archaeological staff and not the organisations overall staff as this would have been irrelevant. I also could not answer question 6 in relation to pay as there was not an option for below inflation pay rise.

Our reporting on volunteers is a little misleading. At the time of the survey we have only two volunteers, but over the course of a year we have engaged with over 100 volunteers, some for a week or two and others for longer periods.

In this survey I have responded as though the term "organisation" relates purely to the archaeological team rather than County Council.

As we all know there are some differences between a local authority advisory service and a more commercial contracting organisation and therefore some of the questions are not directly relevant but I have offered an answer where appropriate. Good luck with it all - the situation is only going to get worse before it will get any better. Time

to batten down the hatches and consolidate what we have and stop the organisational melt downs that are being forced upon local authorities due to reductions in funding. If local authority archaeological services are not working effectively it will knock on across the whole commercial sector of archaeology and the historic environment. Here endeth the lesson.

As a sole trader with no staff, some of this is difficult to fill in sensibly. The formal skills/training section is an example - it is true that it is done formally, but in the context of my personal IFA CPD, and as there is only me much of the response is probably highly misleading. The increase in salary section reflects that fact that I actually made some money (the previous few months were basically set-up), but that is probably not what is really meant by this section. You might need a few more 'not applicable' options in the future - perhaps with a section to permit explanation.

As I work for a multi-disciplinary Govt environmental body I find the term 'archaeological employment' very narrow. Our organisation employs expert level historic environment advisers, with a combination of strengths in landscape archaeology, field archaeology, historic building conservation, intrusive and non-intrusive excavation techniques, project management, IT, data management, sector partnership working etc. I think this survey needs more to recognise that archaeology is one discipline within many professions, from central to local govt, consultancy to contracting, education to media.

[*organisation name*] was closed down by [*parent organisation name*] in March 2012, 2.5 staff (out of 4) who deliver the archaeology advisory service and HER for the [*local planning authority*] were re-employed by the [*parent organisation name*] to provide the same service but as [*organisation name*], initially for 6 months but now for a further 3 years (from 1st Jan).

As a single-person organisation, some of the questions are difficult to answer in a helpful way

I am a self-employed archaeologist and buildings analyst. I do not have the constraints of a large organisation and I can be self-determining. I am not tied into a top heavy (and rather self important) management structure that makes the cost of the real work artificially high. This is one of the reasons I can make a living from producing high quality archaeological reports rather than just conforming to a minimum standard.

Many of the questions do not apply to my organisation (a local authority planning department). Its core business is not archaeology and thus training needs have to fit in with corporate training. This is good in areas such as IT and management but non-existent for specialist interests. However, we do encourage attendance at (free) English Heritage training events. Future prospects are uncertain with cuts in local government a certainty. We only have 2 staff dealing with archaeology, one of whom now works part-time, having opted for flexible retirement. It is unlikely that he will be replaced when he fully retires.

Please note that our employment figures for 2007 compared to 2012 are misleading. In 2007, our archaeology service included a large field team, which was

externalised in 2008, leaving only the curatorial team in house. The curatorial team in 2007 employed 9 people

After significant downsizing and restructuring in 2010 and 2011 the imposition of a risk-averse business model necessitates a cautious but confident growth plan based on local market dominance and maintaining first-rate CPD, training and staff benefits

The survey seems to be directed to archaeological contractors working in the commercial environment. It is difficult to answer from the perspective of a local authority curatorial service, particularly where that service is embedded within a larger Development Management Team and so does not have control over budgets, training and policy which are dealt with at the Service level. In order to provide an accurate profile of the profession in future it would be helpful if the questions could be framed to reflect the diversity of archaeological employers.

I am finding trading in the UK archaeological sector to be so difficult at present that I spent half of 2012 working overseas. This year I plan to emigrate with my partner as we are both heritage professionals and prospects for us are very poor in the UK, but very good overseas.

(This may be a duplicate submission as my browser crashed when on point of completing)

The recession is going to have repercussions for many years to come, even though it has been stated that we are now out of recession. We reviewed our tenders for projects from pre-crash in 2008 to what we are quoting for schemes now and it is clear that tenders are approximately at 50% the level they were previously. With increasing costs and salary rises this really is not a sustainable model; however it is not possible to simply raise fee proposals to cover this plummet in profit as the market will not support it (i.e. another company will be granted the contract by putting in an artificially low bid). We have seen many examples of this where even the largest ROs out there have put in what can only be described as 'loss-leader' quotations which have clearly not been sufficient to provide even a minimally adequate level of service to fulfil a project brief (recently we were informed by a consultant that a quotation we provided was approximately 33% higher than that provided by two of the largest ROs). This slashing of tenders and raising of costs has seen our profits drop sharply from approximately 25% to below 10% (and a subsequent profit warning from our accountants), which clearly does not allow a business to grow. Staffing levels need to be sufficient to cover schemes and equipment still needs to be purchased however; leaving the company in an ever increasingly precarious position financially. The lack of resources available also means that the company directors have to spend increasingly longer hours striving to maintain the company at its current levels. Yes, the turnover has increased significantly; however profits are non-existent and currently the directors are working 6-7 days a week, averaging over 60 hrs a week. I am at a loss to see how the situation can be changed significantly in the next few years (possibly even the next decade) as the commercial market is driven by cost and not quality.

This has been completed with some assistance from HR but they found it difficult

to dis-aggregate specific archaeologists from other members of staff.

As a consultant operating as a sole trader most of what you ask is not relevant to me. However after a grim couple of years I feel that things are starting to look a little better.

Have ignored budget questions as they are not very relevant to our position as part of a [*local planning authority*] - element of local government. Staffing figures just relate to Archaeology element of integrated HE team other than counting the HER staff member (who also supports Building conservation aspects) as archaeology FTE

Because we are tied to a University grading system we need to be 'creative' in finding ways to adjust to IFA salary recommendations. For example short-contract staff can not be given additional incremental awards (as is the case for all permanent staff, whom we are therefore able to migrate onto new spine points). The only way to address this is to terminate contracts and then rehire (after one month interruption of service) on higher grades. Two of the staff submitted were below the IFA minima since we deemed it fairer to extend contracts rather than terminate their employment. We consequentlu juggle with 'overtime' payments in order to redress.

I have responded in relation to the Conservation And Archaeology Team at [*local planning authority*], not on behalf of the whole organisation. I have included the team manager and other two staff in the overall employee count but have not counted them as 'archaeologists' as your definition is too loose and unhelpful in this context. As Conservation Officers they probably fit your description, but they are not in any sense members of the same profession. I'll leave it to the IHBC to collect data on this profession.

This questionnaire is not really suited to small businesses like ourselves. We are two people - we do not intend to grow beyond this and our small size is part of our business plan. So the turnover question in terms of £m is laughable. We make around £25,000 a year. Are we meant not to answer or are we going to be filtered out? All very confusing and could be better thought out in future

We only currently employ Lecturing staff, no commercial staff

A tricky survey to answer for us, due to the somewhat complex nature of operating as an integrated consultancy unit [*organisation name*] and HE department - further complicated by being part of both the local council and a federated university. Have answered with most representative answer wherever possible, but not always possible to accurately reflect the reality within in a checkbox answer

The survey has been filled in for a small conservation unit working within a univerity, offering commercial conservation services, so some of the questions were not answered as they did not really seem relevant. Only one person is employed by the University providing these services, with additionla conservators being contracted in as projects require.

Not all the questions had suitable options to give an accurate response, or at least not a misleading response. For example you asked about the surplus the organisation had been running recently. We have been in deficit for 4 years now and the nearest to that was less than 5%. Well it is less than 5%, but the implication of the answer was that we were making a profit. We are not in terms of the university's financial model (of course this is not real, but it is our accounting framework).

We find it discouraging that your turnover is only measured in millions of pounds. Most archaeological contractors are much smaller operators. Ours has varied from £12,000-70,000 in the last three years and has only made slim profit in one of those years, losses in the other two. Our Directors work for less than national minimum wage (family business), only our non- Directors get lFA pay minima.

I think as a profession we are in a serious state of decline. Pricing for work is in freefall and many companies including Registered Organisations are pricing on below minimum wages.

Difficult to answer some of the questions when we are a small team within a much much larger organisation eg finance questions). Also, re IIP, we were accredited until end Dec 2012, but NYCC will not be re-applying due to the cost implications - this scenario did not fit your predetermined drop down list.

We are a group of unpaid volunteers, who provide artefact assessment and final reports, for organisations who donate agreed sums to help support our agreed research and publication objectives - please disregard our input, if our data is inconsistent from that of your target recipients.

As I work for a local authority the impact of the reduced settlement for local government, along with other changes to local authority finance, announced in December 2012 are bound to have an impact on numbers of historic environment staff they employ though this is as yet unquantifiable. The role of local authority archaeology services needs to be incorporated into university archaeology courses.

Training will depend on level of funding available in the future.

The financial section was not really applicable for me as a single person within a Local Authority...

I have omitted financial sections as these appear to be aimed at commercial rather than local government organisations.

Obviously I'm a very small organisation and have actually lost one staff member but after your end date for the year. Hoping to replace them though

Questions largely irrelevant to one person business - I may spend a few hours studying some particular technical point (and thereby learning), but this is not formal training and is an integral part of day-to-day archaeology where every project is a learning

experience. In terms of employment I now sub contract all my additional staff needs (and where possible get the client to pay the additional staff directly). Employment law has made it impractical to employ a small flexible workforce in the UK. I can see a future where all private sector archaeologists will be self employed.

Large numbers of qualified archaeologists have recently come here from Europe to work. They often have had a good (free) Socialist education in Poland. This has led to a reduction in the price of trenched evaluations which has in turn led to a reduction in prices for geophysical surveys. Geophysics organisations are increasingly devoting time to locating drains rather than archaeology in order to survive.

I am a Scottish council archaeologist (basically the County Archaeologist for [*local planning authority*]). The team consists of me and a half-time SMR officer. Our work is almost exclusively planning-based although we do supply a general historic environment advisory service. Being a council, we are not a commercial organisation. We are historic environment advisors and project managers, not a listed unit. We don't generate income although we do bring in grant for THI, CARS and SRDP work.

Our organisation has been trying to expand for some time, but finds it very hard to find hard to identify candidates who have or would like to acquire the necessary business and people skills in addition to the knowledge needed for the jobs on offer. Or are willing to engage with the financial risk in being self-employed.

Some questions quite difficult to answer as a single archaeologist working in a local authority planning department, but alongside a whole university department growing research and commercial services. I am getting some assistance this year starting today! I do not expect it to amount to more than 0.2fte

a lot of the questions remain blank as I am a sole trader/self employed - sorry

Most of this is irrelevant to a small two person consultancy which turned over £20600 last year (so I could not enter the amount). Occasionally we give casual work to one or two fieldworkers.

Appendix 3: Planning Applications

Given that employment in applied archaeological practice has historically demonstrated strong links to the planning system (Aitchison 2012a: Chapter Three – Demand), an examination of granted planning applications was used as a proxy indicator. Examining the figures for England (only) between 2005 and the final quarter of 2012 showed an aggregate decline of around 30% in the number of permissions granted.

Financial Year	Quarter	Granted ('000s)	% change over year	% change from 2007-08 to 2012-13
2005-06	Jun	130		
	Sep	125		
	Dec	112		
	Mar	105		
2006-07	Jun	123	-5%	
	Sep	122	-2%	
	Dec	111	-1%	
	Mar	107	2%	
2007-08	Jun	124	1%	
	Sep	126	3%	
	Dec	116	5%	
	Mar	102	-5%	
2008-09	Jun	114	-8%	
	Sep	108	-14%	
	Dec	91	-22%	
	Mar	73	-28%	
2009-10	Jun	84	-26%	
	Sep	90	-17%	
	Dec	85	-7%	
	Mar	77	5%	
2010-11	Jun	91	8%	
	Sep	97	8%	
	Dec	89	5%	
	Mar	78	1%	
2011-12	Jun	89	-2%	
	Sep	95	-2%	
	Dec	89	0%	
	Mar	82	5%	
2012-13	Jun	90	1%	-27%
	Sep	90	-5%	-29%
	Dec	85	-4%	-27%

Table 146: Planning applications granted in England, June 2005 to December 2012.

Figure 30: Planning applications and decisions in England, June 2005 to December 2012. (DCLG 2013).

	householder		housing (local)		business & industry (local)		other (local)		further consents		major applications	
2006-07	25,707		9,103		3,876		6,107				1,944	
2007-08	24,821	-3%	9,085	0%	3,560	-8%	6,592	8%			2,078	7%
2008-09	20,941	-16%	8,037	-12%	3,055	-14%	6,340	-4%	6,664		1,778	-14%
change in data definitions												
2009-10	17,977	-14%	6,128	-24%	2,690	-12%	6,092	-4%	5,966	-10%	959	-46%
2010-11	18,194	1%	6,561	7%	2,677	0%	6,061	-1%	6,690	12%	500	-48%
2011-12	16,460	-10%	5,896	-10%	2,696	1%	6,046	0%	6,742	1%	442	-12%

Table 147: Planning applications by type in Scotland, 2006-07 to 2011-12. (Scottish Government 2013)

	received		withdrawn		decided		approved	
2002-03	29,561		2,388		22,805		21,601	
2003-04	34,270	16%	2,649	11%	24,036	5%	22,328	3%
2004-05	36,593	7%	2,960	12%	27,443	14%	24,809	11%
2005-06	35,356	-3%	3,535	19%	30,161	10%	25,095	1%
2006-07	27,077	-23%	1,713	-52%	29,084	-4%	24,009	-4%
2007-08	27,096	0%	1,917	12%	26,580	-9%	24,353	1%
2008-09	20,469	-24%	1,566	-18%	24,637	-7%	23,211	-5%
2009-10	19,557	-4%	1,238	-21%	20,223	-18%	19,016	-18%
2010-11	16,768	-14%	1,268	2%	16,191	-20%	14,456	-24%
2011-12	13,680	-18%	722	-43%	14,509	-10%	13,384	-7%
change 2007-08 to 2011-12		-50%		-62%		-45%		-45%

Table 148: Planning Applications and decisions in Northern Ireland, 2002-03 to 2011-12. (Northern Ireland Statistics and Research Agency 2013).

Figure 31: Planning applications and decisions in Northern Ireland, 2002-03 to 2011-12.

	quarter	received		decided		withdrawn		carried forward	
2008	Mar	8,362		7,644		555		9,989	
	Jun	9,000		8,132		607		10,013	
	Sep	7,710		7,787		569		9,187	
	Dec	6,053		6,728		485		8,035	
2009	Mar	6,157	-26%	5,598	-27%	461	-17%	7,995	-20%
	Jun	6,261	-30%	6,084	-25%	399	-34%	7,576	-24%
	Sep	6,295	-18%	5,969	-23%	319	-44%	7,316	-20%
	Dec	5,727	-5%	5,671	-16%	393	-19%	7,495	-7%
2010	Mar	6,081	-1%	5,281	-6%	318	-31%	7,907	-1%
	Jun	6,563	5%	5,858	-4%	304	-24%	7,140	-6%
	Sep	6,954	10%	6,343	6%	336	5%	8,190	12%
	Dec	5,222	-9%	5,832	3%	345	-12%	7,152	-5%
2011	Mar	5,747	-5%	4,955	-6%	405	27%	7,132	-10%
	Jun	6,149	-6%	5,692	-3%	346	14%	6,995	-2%
	Sep	6,191	-11%	5,862	-8%	406	21%	6,693	-18%
	Dec	5,602	7%	5,489	-6%	331	-4%	6,491	-9%
2012	Mar	6,010	5%	5,127	3%	374	-8%	6,641	-7%
	Jun	5,986	-3%	5,355	-6%	323	-7%	6,890	-2%
	Sep	5,658	-9%	5,643	-4%	312	-23%	6,389	-5%
	Dec	5,185	-7%	5,322	-3%	315	-5%	6,152	-5%
2013	Mar	6,314	5%	5,573	9%	384	3%	6,135	-8%
change 2008 to 2012	Mar		-28%		-33%		-33%		-34%
	Jun		-33%		-34%		-47%		-31%
	Sep		-27%		-28%		-45%		-30%
	Dec		-14%		-21%		-35%		-23%

Table 149: Planning application and decisions in Wales, 2008 to 2013.
(Welsh Government 2013).

Figure 32: Planning applications and decisions in Wales, 2008 to 2013.

Appendix 4: Questionnaire

Profiling the Profession 2012-13

Dear Colleague,

Profiling the Profession 2012-13 is a survey of employment and training in professional archaeology in the United Kingdom.

This is the fourth in a series of surveys, the results of which can be seen at profilingtheprofession.org.uk.

The scale and nature of employment in UK archaeology changed dramatically during the course of the 1990s and the first decade of the 21st century following the introduction of the developer-funding model, and then has been transformed again following the global economic decline which began in 2007-08.

The most recent of this series of studies captured data from employers in August 2007, immediately before the effects of the global economic changes had serious and adverse effects upon archaeological employment in the UK .

Capturing and analysing data again in 2012-13 will quantify the changes that the economic transformations have brought; the purpose of collecting, analysing and sharing this information is to support employers, individual workers and training providers who are seeking to address these changes.

This project is funded by English Heritage, Historic Scotland, Cadw, Northern Ireland Environment Agency: Built Heritage and is supported by the Lifelong Learning Programme of the European Union.

Your responses are fully confidential and will not be seen by anyone outside the Landward Research Ltd project team.

If you require further advice or information, please email kenneth.aitchison@landward.eu.

Please complete the questionnaire by 27th January 2013. Your contribution is enormously valued.

Landward Research Ltd is Registered as a Data Controller with the Information Commissioner's Office. All data received will be used only for research purposes. No information that could be used to identify any individual or organisation will be available to any other organisation.

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Profiling the Profession 2012-13

1. Please enter the name of the organisation that you are providing data for (to avoid duplicate entries being made)

2. Where is the head office of your organisation located?

3. Are you also answering on behalf of any subsidiary offices? If so, please indicate where they are located.

East of England	East Midlands	Greater London	North East England
North West England	South East England	South West England	West Midlands
Yorkshire and the Humber	Scotland	Wales	Northern Ireland
outside the UK			

4. How is your organisation legally constituted?

5. Please indicate the principal area (or areas) of your organisation's activity

select one or indicate broad %

field investigation and research

provision of historic environment advice and information

museum and visitor / user services

educational and academic research

6. In which year did your organisation first start operating in archaeology?

Profiling the Profession 2012-13

Staffing

When completing this set of questions, please consider that 'archaeological staff' should be interpreted broadly as anyone using their professional expertise and capabilities to work directly or indirectly (such as in a managerial, commissioning or curatorial position) with the investigation, conservation or interpretation of the historic environment.

1. How many people were working for your organisation on 14th December 2012?
paid staff unpaid volunteers

archaeological staff
non-archaeological staff

2. How many members of staff did your organisation have on 13th August 2007 (the census date of *Profiling the Profession: Archaeology Labour Market Intelligence 2007-08*)?

3. Relative to this year, how many staff did you have in previous years - and how many do you anticipate having in the future?

Please ensure that all staff, including those on short-term or temporary contracts, are included.

more than now the same as now less than now none don't know

five years ago - 2007-08 paid staff
volunteers

three years ago - 2009-10 paid staff
volunteers

last year - 2011-12
paid staff
volunteers

next year - 2013-14
paid staff
volunteers

in three years time - 2015-16 paid
staff
volunteers

4. What level of staff turnover have you experienced in the last year (since the start of 2012) - in terms of how many of your members of staff are new?

5. If you have lost staff in the course of 2012, do you believe that these people left the archaeological profession or did they stay within it with different employers?

6. Have salaries at your organisation typically risen or fallen since January 2012? (NB - this is thinking about individual salaries, not the total salary bill)

Profiling the Profession 2012-13

The Workplace

This page of questions asks about the setup in your organisation's workplace.

1. Which of the following rights and benefits are provided to employees? If you are self-employed, please answer as well as you are able.

yes no don't know or not applicable

- 28 or more days paid holiday leave per annum
- occupational sick pay (paid sickness leave over and above Statutory Sick Pay)
- paid maternity leave over and above Statutory Maternity Leave
- the opportunity to take unpaid maternity leave
- paid paternity leave over and above Statutory Paternity Leave
- the opportunity to take unpaid paternity leave
- the opportunity to jobshare or use other flexible working arrangements
- subsidised accommodation or subsistence allowance

please list any other employee benefits that you provide (eg funding IfA subscriptions)

2. do you have any further comments you would like to make about employee rights or benefits?

3. Are salaries within the organisation tied to any scale system?

4. If a salary scale is used, then what kind of a system is this?

5. Are any trade unions recognised in the organisation's workplace?

6. Which trade unions are recognised in your workplace (please check all that apply)

Prospect	UCU (University and College Union)
Unison	Unite
other (please specify)	

7. Does your organisation use a formal Quality System?

8. If you do employ a Quality System, please check all that apply

Investors in People	Registered Museum
IfA Registered Organisation	ISO 9001
other system (please specify)	

9. Thinking about Investors in People (IiP), is your organisation:

10. If your organisation has not committed to IIP, which of the following is the main reason for that?

11. Thinking now about IfA Registered Organisation status, is your organisation:

12. If your organisation has not committed to IfA Registration, which of the following is the main reason for that?

13. Is your organisation a member of FAME (the Federation of Archaeological Managers and Employers)?

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Profiling the Profession 2012-13

Financial Performance

This page of the questionnaire asks a series of questions about your organisation's past financial performance.

Please note - you can consider answering the questions on this page to be optional, but if you can give indicative figures these will be extremely valuable

1. What was your annual turnover (in £m) for each of the last three financial years?

2009-10 2010-11 2011-12 turnover (£m)

2. What level of profit or surplus has your organisation generated in the financial year to date? (the nine months since April 2012)

3. Broadly, what percentages of your turnover this financial year (in the nine months since April 2012) have been generated through each of the following areas of activity?

field research, including invasive and non-invasive fieldwork together with post-fieldwork analysis and reporting

provision of advice or information to clients or customers (including desk-based or environmental assessment)

education or training services

museum or visitor services

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Profiling the Profession 2012-13

Business Confidence

The questions on this page ask about your feelings regarding your organisation and the archaeological sector as a whole. Please feel free to answer these questions as you see fit - whether you feel you are giving answers that apply to the whole professional archaeological sector or whether they relate to your particular area, these answers are very valuable and help to track sentiment across our whole sector.

1. Do you believe that market conditions - in the sense of the environment that your organisation operates in - will deteriorate over the next 12 months? (to 31 December 2013)
2. Do you expect any archaeological organisations to cease operations over the next 12 months (to the end of December 2013)?
3. Do you have any plans to expand your business significantly over the next twelve months (to December 2013) (e.g. in premises, vehicles, capital equipment)?

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Profiling the Profession 2012-13

Skills, Training and Qualifications

This page of questions asks about skills your organisation has and wants, the training to get those skills and qualifications to validate them.

1. Organisational training needs and plans

yes no don't know

does your organisation identify training needs for individuals?

do you (as an organisation) identify training needs for the organisation as a whole?

do you provide training or other development opportunities for paid staff?

do you provide training or other development opportunities for unpaid volunteers?

2. If you do provide training or other development opportunities, please indicate how you do this (check all that apply)

paid staff unpaid volunteers

formal off-the-job training (eg external training courses)

formal in-job training (eg in-house training courses)

informal off-the-job training (eg supported individual research and learning)

informal in-job training (eg mentoring)

3. Training planning

yes no don't know

does your organisation have a formal training plan?

does your organisation have a training budget?

is your training budget under your organisation's direct control?

do you record how much time employees spend being trained?

do you formally evaluate the impact of training on individuals?

do you formally evaluate the impact of training on the organisation?

does your organisation operate a performance appraisal scheme?

does your organisation encourage individuals to engage in their continuing professional development (CPD)?

4. In the last twelve months (during the course of 2012) has your organisation lost skills in any of these areas?

fieldwork (invasive or non-invasive)	post-fieldwork analysis	artefact or ecofact conservation
providing advice to clients	desk-based or environmental assessment	data management
leadership	business skills	project management
education / training	information technology	people management
other		

5. In the last twelve months (during 2012) has your organisation had to buy in skills (eg by hiring consultants or external contractors) in any of these areas?

fieldwork (invasive or non-invasive)	post-fieldwork analysis	artefact or ecofact conservation
providing advice to clients	desk-based or environmental assessment	data management
leadership	business skills	project management
education / training	information technology	people management

other		
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6. In the last twelve months (during 2012) has your organisation invested in skills training in any of these areas?

fieldwork (invasive or non-invasive)	post-fieldwork analysis	artefact or ecofact conservation
providing advice to clients	desk-based or environmental assessment	data management
leadership	business skills	project management
education / training	information technology	people management
other		

7. Thinking beyond your organisation, do you think there are skills gaps or shortages across the archaeological sector in any of these areas?

fieldwork (invasive or non-invasive)	post-fieldwork analysis	artefact or ecofact conservation
providing advice to clients	desk-based or environmental assessment	data management
leadership	business skills	project management
education / training	information technology	people management
other		

8. Have you or would you consider supporting a member of staff to gain a vocational qualification in archaeological practice (NVQ)?

yes no don't know

have previously supported a member of staff

would support a member of staff in the future

Profiling the Profession 2012-13

Further Comments

This concludes the first part of the survey. If you have any further comments on your responses, or on archaeological employment and training in general or specific, please let us know.

If you would like to be sent a copy of the final Profiling the Profession 2012-13 report when it is published, please provide us with your email address

Please now complete the survey by providing information about the people working for your organisation, please choose "complete post profile"

Please complete your response by Sunday 27th January 2013

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Profiling the Profession 2012-13

Post Profiles

This page asks a series of detailed questions about the individuals working for your organisation.

It should be completed once for each post title within the organisation rather than once for every individual - it is expected that each page might relate to a number of individuals. Once the page is complete, you will be asked if you want to complete another sheet for a different post title.

1. Please enter the name of the organisation that you are providing data for (to allow us to associate these replies with the organisational responses)

2. What is the title of the post that you are providing information about?

3. How many individuals work in this particular post?

individuals number of paid individuals employed in this post
number of individuals volunteering in this post on an unpaid basis

4. Level of seniority

senior staff medium ranking junior staff

how many of these people are:

6. Please indicate the principal role of the individuals working in this post

(please select one only)

- field investigation and research services
- historic environment advice and information services
- museum and visitor / user services
- educational and academic research services
- administrative support

4. Please indicate the how many people work in this post by their age and gender

paid staff			volunteers	
male	female		male	female
		aged 16-19		
		aged 20-29		
		aged 30-39		
		aged 40-49		
		aged 50-59		
		aged 60 and over		

7. How much are the gross salaries received by people working in this post?

self-employed respondents: please enter your taxable income, ie your annual turnover less all business expenses

salary if this includes a weighting allowance, how much is this?

minimum
maximum
average

2. Does the organisation contribute to the pensions of individuals working in this post?

please complete in terms of numbers of individuals

individuals

yes

no

don't know

7. How many of these people work full- or part-time? *please*

complete in terms of numbers of individuals

paid staff unpaid staff

full time (>=30h per week)

part time (<30 hours per week)

9. What are the lengths of contract for paid staff working in this post?

individuals

up to 3 months

3 - 6 months

6 - 12 months

12 - 24 months

more than 24 months

permanent / open-ended

14. How many of the paid posts are funded by establishment income or by project grants / contracting income? *please*

complete in terms of numbers of individuals

individuals

establishment income

project or contract income

12. How long have these individuals been working for the organisation (or, for unpaid staff, how long have they been volunteering)?

paid staff unpaid volunteers

up to 3 months

3 - 6 months

6 - 12 months

12 - 24 months

2 - 5 years

5 - 10 years

10 - 20 years

more than 20 years

4. Please indicate the highest level of qualification held by individuals working in this post, and specify whether this was in archaeology or another subject. Please also indicate where these qualifications were obtained.

please complete in terms of numbers of individuals

what subject was this qualification in?

where was this qualification obtained?

in archaeology in another subject in the UK elsewhere in the EU elsewhere in the world

post-doctoral qualification

doctorate (PhD or DPhil)

postgraduate (Masters)

first degree

foundation degree or HND

school qualifications

14. What are the ethnic origins of the people working in this post (please complete in terms of numbers of individuals)?

paid staff unpaid staff

White

Black or Black British

Asian or Asian British

Chinese

Mixed

other ethnic group

4. Please tell us the countries of origin of any individuals who are not from the UK (please also let us know the numbers of individuals)

5. What are the disability statuses of the people working in this post?

A person is disabled under the Equality Act 2010 if they have a physical or mental impairment that has a 'substantial' and 'long-term' negative effect on their ability to do normal daily activities.

numbers of individuals

paid staff volunteers

disabled

not disabled

6. In the past year, have there been vacancies for this post that have been difficult to fill (eg the post had to be re-advertised)?

7. To now complete another post profile, giving information about people working for your organisation in a different post, please choose "complete another post profile"

Please complete your response by Sunday 27th January 2013